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**International Symposium on Metal Complexes
Florence, June 3-7, 2018**

Acta of the International Symposia on Metal Complexes

UNIVERSITÀ
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**International Symposium on Metal Complexes
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Edited by:

Antonio Bianchi

University of Florence (Italy)

Chairman of the Organizing Committee of ISMEC 2018

President of the ISMEC Group

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Foreword

On behalf of the International Scientific Committee and of the Local Organization Committee, it is my great pleasure to welcome you in Florence for the 2018 edition of the **International Symposium on Metal Complexes (ISMEC 2018)**. ISMEC 2018 is the 45th edition of a series of meetings that begun in Florence in 1974 as the annual congress of the Italian group of "Thermodynamics of Metal Complexes". In 1988 it became an Italian-Spanish, or Spanish-Italian congress with annual meetings alternating between Italy and Spain. From 2010, participation was widened at an international level and the meeting took the name of International Symposium on Metal Complexes. The participation in ISMEC 2018 of scientists from all over the world confirms the international vocation of these meetings and the worldwide interest for their core subject which focuses on the thermodynamic and the kinetic properties of metal complexes and related applications in the fields of Analytical, Biomedical, Environmental, Inorganic and Physical Chemistry. Main topics include, but are not limited to:

- Complexation thermodynamics and kinetics
- Solution equilibria and coordination chemistry
- Complexation processes in supramolecular chemistry
- Metal-based reactivity and catalysis
- Metal-complex interactions with biomolecules
- Metals in diseases: transport, homeostasis and toxicity
- Metal-based drugs: diagnosis and therapy
- Metal complexes of environmental and biological interest
- Nanostructured metal complexes
- Analytical methods and sensors based on complexation equilibria
- Computer methods for equilibrium analysis

The "Acta of ISMEC Symposia" has been published since 2011, immediately after each symposium, to highlight the ongoing interest in the covered topics and to provide an overview of the most recent progresses in the field.

I like to express my highest appreciation for the work done by the members of the local organizing committee. Without them, this symposium would not have been possible.

Antonio Bianchi

*Chairman of ISMEC 2018
President of the ISMEC Group*

June 2018

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Acta website: <http://www.gtc2014.com>

Conference Program

Sunday, June 3rd

18:00-20:00 Registration at Grand Hotel Baglioni (Piazza dell'Unità Italiana, 6)

20:30-22:00 **Welcome Cocktail on the Terrace of the Grand Hotel Baglioni**

Monday, June 4th

8:00-8:30 Registration at the Italian Military Geographic Institute (via C. Battisti, 10)

8:30-9:00 Opening Ceremony

Chairperson: Enrique García-España

9:00-9:45 **PL 1:** Control and crystallization in supramolecular gels

Jonathan W. STEED

9:45-10:00 **OC 1:** Non-covalent interactions in the coordination sphere of the uranyl ion: an experimental and theoretical study

Stefano NUZZO, Robert BAKER, Brendan TWAMLEY, James PLATTS

10:00-10:15 **OC 2:** Robson-type metallomacrocycles acting in second-sphere: selective complexation of cuprate ions

Sara SCHMORL, Berthold KERSTING

10:15-10:30 **OC 3:** Intramolecular interactions in transition metal bis(dicarbollide) complexes and their role in design of molecular switches

Igor B. SIVAEV, Sergey A. ANUFRIEV, Kyrill Yu. SUPONITSKY

10:30-11:00 **Coffee break**

Chairperson: Maurizio Remelli

11:00-11:30 **KN 1:** From simple to complex: supramolecular anion coordination

Kristin BOWMAN-JAMES

11:30-11:45 **OC 4:** Gastrointestinal speciation and mineral bioavailability: dietary management of vegetable-based meals

Nicolás VEIGA, Julia TORRES, Carlos KREMER

11:45-12:00 **OC 5:** Anion encapsulation drives the formation of dimeric Ln^{III}[15-metallacrown-5]³⁺ complexes in neutral aqueous solution

Carmelo SGARLATA, Rossella MIGLIORE, Valeria ZITO, Evan R. TRIVEDI, Vincent L. PECORARO, Giuseppe ARENA

12:00-12:15 **OC 6:** Porous metallacrown frameworks: crystal engineering through a mindful ligand design

Vittoria MARZAROLI, Luciano MARCHIO', Giulia SPIGOLON, Giulia LICINI, Vincent L. PECORARO, Matteo TEGONI

12:15-12:30 **OC 7:** NMR and structural characterization of paramagnetic metallacrown architectures containing lanthanides

Vittoria MARZAROLI, Rosy POLISICCHIO, Lorenzo DI BARI, Curtis M. ZALESKI, Vincent L. PECORARO, Matteo TEGONI

12:30-13:00 **Pulidori Prize:** Equilibrium and thorough spectroscopic characterization of the complex formation processes of NiSOD enzyme fragments

Norbert LIHI, Balázs PATAKI, Gizella CSIRE, István FÁBIÁN, Imre SÓVÁGÓ

13:00-14:30 **Lunch**

Chairperson: José M. Leal

- 14:30-15:00 **KN 2:** Development of non destructive analytical methodologies for the conservation diagnosis of urban built heritage based on spectroscopy and thermodynamic modelling
Maria Ángeles OLAZABAL, Olivia GOMEZ-LASERNA
- 15:00-15:15 **OC 8:** Monitoring chicken meat spoilage: from pH indicators to on-package labels
Lisa Rita MAGNAGHI, Giancarla ALBERTI, Raffaella BIESUZ
- 15:15-15:30 **OC 9:** Extraction of toxic metals: from fundamental advances in macrocyclic chemistry to soft materials incorporated in ultra-sensitive detectors
Michel MEYER
- 15:30-15:45 **OC 10:** A new approach for arsenic speciation in natural waters through complexation with a dithiophosphinic acid derivative incorporated in a polymer inclusion membrane
Donatella CHILLÉ, Enriqueta ANTICÓ, Eva MARGUÍ, Claudia FOTI, Clàudia FONTÀS
- 15:45-16:00 **OC 11:** Biospeciation and anti-diabetic effects of oxidovanadium(IV) complexes
Vital UGIRINEMA, Carminita FROST, Zenixole TSHENTU
- 16:00-18:00 **Coffee break and Poster Session**

Tuesday, June 5th

Chairperson: Marilena Tolazzi

- 8:30-9:15 **PL 2:** Design and testing of metal-based MRI reporters
Silvio AIME
- 9:15-9:30 **OC 12:** ¹H NMR relaxometric study of Eu(II)-containing cryptates in aqueous solution
Fabio CARNIATO, Chamika U. LENORA, Matthew J. ALLEN, Mauro BOTTA
- 9:30-9:45 **OC 13:** Towards high relaxivity in MRI: design and synthesis of new gadolinium complexes based on HP-DO3A
Valeria BOI, Sonia COLOMBO SERRA, Alberto FRINGUELLO MINGO, Giovanni Battista GIOVENZANA, Luciano LATTUADA, Paolo MINAZZI, Roberta NAPOLITANO
- 9:45-9:50 **New. J. Chem. special issue announcement**
Michel Meyer
- 9:50-10:00 **Featured Sponsor**
Dietmar GLINDEMANN
- 10:00-10:15 **OC 14:** AAZTA: An ideal chelating agent for the development of ⁴⁴Sc PET imaging agents
Zsolt BARANYAI, Gábor NAGY, Dezső SZIKRA, György TRENCSENYI, Anikó FEKETE, Ildikó GARAI, Arianna M. GIANI, Roberto NEGRI, Norberto MASCIOCCHI, Alessandro MAIOCCHI, Fulvio UGGERI, Imre TÓTH, Silvio AIME, Giovanni B. GIOVENZANA
- 10:15-10:30 **OC 15:** Pyclyen-based ligands with pendant picolinate arms as attractive rare earth chelators for diagnostic and therapy
Maryline BEYLER, Mariane LE FUR, Gyula TIRCSO, Carlos PLATAS-IGLESIAS, Olivier ROUSSEAU, Raphaël TRIPIER
- 10:30-11:00 **Coffee break**

Chairperson: Nicolás Veiga

- 11:00-11:30 **KN 3:** Nanoparticles with biomedical applications
M. Teresa ALBELDA, Juan Carlos FRÍAS, Michael J. LIPINSKI, Stasia A. ANDERSON, Wei SUN, Dror LUGER, Andrew A. ARAI, Stephen E. EPSTEIN, Isabel PONT, Enrique GARCÍA-ESPAÑA, Amadeo TEN, Laura CUBAS, Jessica CASTILLO, Sara GARCÍA
- 11:30-11:45 **OC 16:** Cobalt(III) ternary complexes of hydroxamate-based compounds
Etelka FARKAS, Péter BUGLYÓ, István KACSIR, Máté KOZSUP, Imre NAGY, Sándor NAGY
- 11:45-12:00 **OC 17:** Ciprofloxacin-metal complexes –stability and toxicity tests in the presence of humic substances
Agnieszka CUPRYS, Rama PULICHARLA, Joanna LECKA, Satinder K. BRAR, Patrick DROGUI, R.Y. SURAMPALLI
- 12:00-12:15 **OC 18:** pH-Dependent modulation of reactivity in ruthenium(II) organometallics
Timothy J. PRIOR, Huguette SAVOIE, Ross W. BOYLE, Benjamin S. MURRAY
- 12:15-12:30 **OC 19:** Phosphine-peptide(SarGlyOH) conjugate attached to CuI complex contra breast cancer – physicochemical and biological characteristics
Urszula K. KOMARNICKA, Sandra KOZIEŁ, Radosław STAROSTA, Agnieszka KYZIOŁ
- 12:30-12:45 **OC 20:** An in-depth analysis of the metal binding domain in a putative Zn(II) transporter of *Candida albicans*
Denise BELLOTTI, Cinzia TOCCHIO, Magdalena ROWIŃSKA-ŻYREK, Maurizio REMELLI
- 12:45-13:00 **OC 21:** Synthesis, characterization and DNA interaction of highly charged ruthenium complexes as photosensitizer agents in photodynamic therapy
Luca CONTI, Andrea BENCINI, Cristina GELLINI, Claudia GIORGI, Giangaetano PIETRAPERZIA, Barbara VALTANCOLI

13:00-14:30

Lunch

Chairperson: Demetrio Milea

- 14:30-15:15 **PL 3:** Bottom-up synthesis and physicochemical versatility of heterodimetallic complexes with 2,2'-oxydiacetate as bridging ligand
Carlos KREMER, Javier GONZÁLEZ-PLATAS, Julia TORRES
- 15:15-15:30 **OC 22:** Influence of ligand structure, central atom and water content on the properties of the lanthanide complex
Tsaqana SUMYANOVA, Natalya BORISOVA, Alexey IVANOV
- 15:30-15:45 **OC 23:** ⁶⁸Ga-Curcumin-based chelators: development of potential new PET radiotracers for colon carcinoma
Giulia ORTECA, Eleonora BETTALICO, Mattia ASTI, Federica PISANESCHI, Sara RUBAGOTTI, Frank RÖSCH, Markus PIEL, Monica SALADINI, Erika FERRARI
- 15:45-16:00 **OC 24:** Cu(II) and Pt(II) polynuclear clusters of novel oxime amide ligands
Elizabeth DIU, Igor NIKOLAYENKO, Matthew AKERMAN, Carla BAZZICALUPI

16:00-17:00

Coffee break and Poster Session

17:00-18:00

GTC Meeting

19:30-21:00

Aperitif on the terrace (Caffetteria delle Oblate, Via dell'Oriuolo, 26)

Wednesday, June 6th

Chairperson: Michel Meyer

- 8:30-9:15 **PL 4:** Therapeutic approaches targeting copper ions against Alzheimer's disease
Christelle HUREAU
- 9:15-9:30 **OC 25:** Enhancement of SOD activity in boehmite supported nanoreceptors
Álvaro MARTÍNEZ-CAMARENA, Estefanía DELGADO-PINAR, Concepción SORIANO, José M. LLINARES, Roberto TEJERO, Enrique GARCÍA-ESPAÑA
- 9:30-9:45 **OC 26:** Interaction of gold N-heterocyclic carbenes with nucleic acids
Federica GUARRA, Tarita BIVER, Chiara GABBIANI, Gennaro PESCIPELLI, Tiziano MARZO, Carla BAZZICALUPI, Paola GRATTERI, Luigi MESSORI
- 9:45-10:00 **OC 27:** Design and investigation of novel zinc finger–NCoE7-based artificial nucleases
Eszter NÉMETH, Zita FÁBIÁN, Bálint HAJDU, Enikő HERMANN, Ria K. Balogh, Chris OOSTENBRINK, Kyosuke NAGATA, Béla GYURCSIK
- 10:00-10:15 **OC 28:** Targeting G-quadruplexes with novel triphenylamine derivatives: recognition and biomedical applications
Isabel PONT, Jorge GONZALEZ-GARCÍA, Mario INCLAN, Estefanía DELGADO-PINAR, M. Teresa ALBELDA, Ramon VILAR, Enrique GARCÍA-ESPAÑA
- 10:15-10:30 **OC 29:** Hydroxyphenyl-benzimidazole based hybrids as metal chelating mimetics of the anti-Alzheimer's drug Donepezil
Federica RINALDO, Romane JOSSELIN, Daniel TOMÁS, Luca PIEMONTESE, Vito CAPRIATI, Sílvia CHAVES, M. Amélia SANTOS

10:30-11:00

Coffee break

Chairperson: Etelka Farkas

- 11:00-11:30 **KN 4:** Biomimetics of siderophores and their possible applications
Elżbieta GUMIENNA-KONTECKA
- 11:30-11:45 **OC 30:** Novel ratiometric fluorescence sensors for Fe(III) ion
Tiziana PIVETTA, Enzo CADONI, Maria Grazia CABIDDU, Sebastiano MASURI, Anna PINTUS, Claudia CALTAGIRONE, Francesco ISAIA
- 11:45-12:00 **OC 31:** A thermodynamic and chemometric study on tannic acid: protonation and interaction with iron(III)
Silvia BERTO, Giovanni GHIGO, Eugenio ALLADIO, Marco MINELLA, Davide VIONE, Valeria Marina NURCHI, Joanna LACHOWICZ, Pier Giuseppe DANIELE
- 12:00-12:15 **OC 32:** The his-containing peptide models of outer membrane proteins–binding sites responsible for copper redox balancing. Implication for fusobacterium–related carcinogenesis
Paulina K. WALENCIK, Urszula K. KOMARNICKA, A. KYZIOŁ
- 12:15-12:30 **OC 33:** Comparative solution equilibrium studies on various antitumor half-sandwich organometallic complexes of 2-picolinates and 8-quinolinols
Éva A. ENYEDY, Jelena M. POLJAREVIĆ, Orsolya DÖMÖTÖR, János P. MÉSZÁROS, Nóra V. MAY, István SZATMÁRI, Ferenc FÜLÖP, Gabriella SPENGLER
- 12:30-12:45 **OC 34:** Developingazole-based ambient condition Pd(II) catalysts for C-C coupling: trends and study of electronic/rigidity features of 2-(thiophen-2-yl)-1H-imidazoles on catalyst activity.
Abiodun OMOKEHINDE ESEOLA, Helmar GÖRLS, Joseph Anthony ORIGHOMISAN WOODS, Winfried PLASS
- 12:45-13:00 **Poster Awards**

13:00-14:30

Lunch

14:30-15:30 **Guided tours of the Italian Military Geographic Institute** (only for booked persons)

20:00 **Gala dinner** (Palazzo Borghese, Via Ghibellina, 110)

Thursday, June 7th

Chairperson: Maria Amelia Santos

8:30-9:00 **KN 5:** Fluorescent systems for metal cations and anions sensing
Vieri FUSI

9:00-9:15 **OC 35:** Sensor and microbiological activity of symmetrical tripods based of 1,8-naphthalimides
Ivo GRABCHEV, Desislava STANEVA, Evgenia VASILEVA-TONKOVA

9:15-9:30 **OC 36:** Insights on the metal ion coordination of carboxyphenyl porphyrins and chlorins
José ALMEIDA, Andreia LEITE, Luís CUNHA-SILVA, Maria RANGEL, André M. N. SILVA, Ana M. G. SILVA

9:30-9:45 **OC 37:** XAFS investigation of Cu coordination environment in complexes with bioactive Schiff base ligands
Diana KALINOWSKA, Marcin T. KLEPKA, Anna WOLSKA, Cristina A. BARBOZA, Elżbieta HEJCHMAN

9:45-10:00 **OC 38:** Engineering of copper(II) acetate structures with 2-phenylbenzimidazole and its derivative
Oleg SEMYONOV, Konstantin A. LYSSENKO, Damir A. SAFIN

10:00-10:15 **OC 39:** Interactions of square-planar metal complexes with lewis acids: principles of bonding
Zdeněk CHVAL

10:15-10:30 **OC 40:** Lead(II). A mimic of copper(II) ... and *vice versa*?
Astrid SIGEL, Helmut SIGEL

10:30-11:00 **Coffee break**

Chairperson: Raffaella Biesuz

11:00-11:30 **KN 6:** Model studies for the biotransformation reactions of half-sandwich type platinum metal complexes
Péter BUGLYÓ

11:30-11:45 **OC 41:** Complex formation of transition metal ions with the peptide fragments of rat amylin
Katalin VÁRNAGY, Ágnes DÁVID, Norbert LIHI, Imre SÓVÁGÓ

11:45-12:00 **OC 42:** Cu²⁺ recognition by C₂-symmetric pseudopeptides
Belen ALTAVA, Lingaraju GORLA, M. Isabel BURGUETE, Santiago V LUIS

12:00-12:15 **OC 43:** Thermal control nitrite linkage isomerism in *quasi*-aromatic Möbius chelates
Irina A. KONYAEVA, Ghodrat MAHMOUDI, Mariusz P. MITORAJ, Damir A. SAFIN

12:15-12:30 **OC 44:** A Contribution to European food safety. Indicating origin and process of European cured hams by using ⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr isotope ratio and multielemental signatures
Ekaterina N. EPOVA, Tea ZULIANI, Sylvain BÉRAIL, Julien MALHERBE, Laurence SARTHOU, Olivier X. DONARD, Montserrat López-Mesas, Manuel VALIENTE

12:30-13:00 **Presentation of ISMEC 2019 and Closing Ceremony**

13:00-14:30 **Lunch**

Plenary Lectures

Control and Crystallization in Supramolecular Gels

Jonathan W. STEED

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A vast and diverse array of organic compounds and coordination complexes form gels by hierarchical self-assembly either because of hydrophobic effects in water or by more directional interactions such as hydrogen bonding in less polar solvents. Of recent interest is the emergence of metal-, anion and salt-containing gelators based on small-molecule ‘low molecular weight gelators (LMWG)’. Particular attractions of LMWGs to the scientific community are the reversible nature of the interactions between the gelator molecules, the wide (essentially unlimited) range of solvents that can be gelled and the possibility of tuning the gels’ behaviour by introducing responsive or switching functionality. Gels derived from LMWGs have been proposed in a range of applications and include heavy metal sensing, templation of nanoparticles and nanostructures, drug delivery and as crystal growth media. This presentation focuses on the control and triggering of the materials properties of small molecule (supramolecular) gels. We show how concepts firmly rooted in supramolecular host-guest chemistry and supramolecular self-assembly can be married with the materials science of soft matter in order to utilise a molecular-level understanding of supramolecular chemistry to control and manipulate bulk materials properties.[1] The application of these kinds of switchable gels as novel media for pharmaceutical crystal growth is emerging [2] and they are also highly useful hydrophobic platforms to construct hybrid carbon dot nanomaterials for metal ion sensing, particularly silver(I) in the environment (see figure).[3]

Figure: A metal ion sensing system based on Fluorescent carbon dots suspended in a supramolecular hydrogel.[3]

Selected references:

- [1] C. D. Jones and J. W. Steed, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2016**, *45*, 6546.
- [2] D. K. Kumar, J. W. Steed *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2014**, *43*, 2080.
- [3] A. Cayuela, S. R. Kennedy, M. L. Soriano, C. D. Jones, M. Valcárcel and J. W. Steed, *Chem. Sci.*, **2015**, *6*, 6139.

Design and testing of Metal-based MRI reporters

Silvio AIME

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The possibility of carrying out Functional and Molecular Imaging protocols by means of MRI is very attractive for the superb anatomical resolution that is attainable by this technique. However, MRI suffers from an intrinsic insensitivity (with respect to the competing imaging modalities) that has to be overcome by designing suitable amplification procedures involving the use of properly designed chemicals. This approach relies first on the development of paramagnetic contrast agents endowed with an enhanced sensitivity and on the identification of efficient routes of accumulation of the imaging probes at the sites of interest. In this context much attention has been devoted to the design of systems endowed with enhanced relaxivity (i.e. able to generate high relaxation rates of the solvent water protons) and/or the use of self-assembled systems. Most often the imaging reporters are represented by highly stable paramagnetic Gd(III) complexes. Although Gd-bearing contrast agents (GBCAs) have been used in several hundred million of patients and are considered among the most well tolerated xenobiotics, recent reports show that tiny amounts of Gd are retained in the brain and other tissues of patients undergone MRI with GBCAs. These findings prompt for new research in the field aimed at getting a better understanding of the role of kinetic and thermodynamic stability of the GBCAs as well as to pursue an enhanced response (to decrease the administered dose) and an improved control of their biodistribution.

Besides relaxation agents much attention is currently devoted also to the use of CEST agents (CEST= Chemical Exchange Saturation Transfer). Upon applying a second rf field at the absorption frequency of an exchangeable protons pool, a net saturation effect is detected on the water signal. These are frequency encoding systems that allow multiple agents detection in the same anatomical region as well as they offer the possibility of designing innovative responsive probes that report on specific parameters of the microenvironment in which they distribute. Enhanced performances of CEST agents have been obtained by exploiting the perturbation induced by paramagnetic metal complexes acting on the chemical shift of water protons eventually through the exchange of mobile protons in the inner coordination sphere of the metal ion. To overcome sensitivity issues, also for this class of agents, the use of Liposomes (LipoCEST) and RBCs (ErythroCEST) appear to offer valuable solutions.

Bottom-up synthesis and physicochemical versatility of heterodimetallic complexes with 2,2'-oxydiacetate as bridging ligand

Carlos KREMER, ^{a)} **Javier GONZÁLEZ-PLATAS,** ^{b)} **Julia TORRES** ^{a)}

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Heterometallic coordination polymers containing lanthanide ions (Ln) present very interesting features. They allow the development of different architectures originated in the high coordination numbers of the Ln ions, as well as new luminescent porous materials. The magnetic interactions between the spin carriers through the chemical bridges can also be investigated if paramagnetic ions are included in the network.

2,2'-oxydiacetate (oda) has proved to be a suitable bridging ligand for this kind of polynuclear compounds. Several complexes with general formula $[\text{Ln}_2\text{M}_3(\text{oda})_6] \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (M = divalent metal ion) have been reported. They are detected in solution by potentiometric studies and can be isolated in the solid state. Under this formula, at least two groups of compounds exist [1,2]. If a distorted hexacoordinated cation as Cu(II) is used, hexagonal (space group P6/mcc) structures are obtained. The most interesting feature in the hexagonal structures, is the formation of a network containing large hexagonal channels. In the case of symmetric cations as Mn(II) or Ca(II), the complexes are better described as $[\{\text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6\} \{\text{MLn}(\text{oda})_3\}_2] \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with two nonequivalent M^{2+} ions in the cubic (space group Fd3c) structure.

Figure 1. Overview of the crystal structures (hexagonal, left and cubic, right) observed in the complexes $[\text{Ln}_2\text{M}_3(\text{oda})_6] \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

In this contribution, the recent advances on this interesting set of complexes will be presented. A critical discussion of the parameters that govern the obtaining of both structures will be developed.

The catalytic performance of the hexagonal framework $[\text{Cu}_3\text{Lu}_2(\text{oda})_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6] \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ towards the oxidation of alkenes and aromatic benzylic substrates show excellent conversions with O_2 under solvent free-conditions (95% for cyclohexane and 91% for cumene) [3].

The novel series $[\text{Ln}_2\text{Zn}_3(\text{oda})_6] \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ provides a subtle example on the control of the structure. For example, a phase change from hexagonal to cubic systems is observed as the lanthanide ion becomes smaller along the series. In the special case of Dy, both polymorphs were obtained by slight variations in the synthetic conditions. The configuration of Zn(II) allows to study the luminescent properties of these compounds.

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Therapeutic approaches targeting copper ions against Alzheimer's disease

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Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a neurodegenerative disorder characterized post-mortem by amyloid deposits made of aggregates of the amyloid- β ($A\beta$) peptide and containing high levels of d-block metal ions. Metal ions have also been involved in earlier processes linked to the development of the disease, namely, modulation of the aggregation of $A\beta$ and contribution to the oxidative stress. While the "metal hypothesis" of AD is disputed currently more than ever because of the failure of the first chelatotherapeutic approaches, one may also wonder whether the previously developed drug candidates fulfill all specifications required by a so complex disease [1-5]. We have recently developed several new therapeutic approaches that target the copper ion regarded as the most toxic one due to its redox ability involved in the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS).

After a brief introduction of the role of metal ions (copper and zinc) in the production of ROS and in the modulation of the aggregation properties of the $A\beta$ peptide, two key events linked to etiology of the disease [2, 3, 6], the evolution of the various approaches developed in our team will be described to illustrate the complexity of designing copper chelators in the context of AD [8-14].

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Keynote Lectures

From Simple to Complex: Supramolecular Anion Coordination

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Molecular structural intricacies both in the crystalline and solution states can frequently be unraveled with the help of X-ray crystallography and NMR, in particular, when the two tools are used together. This presentation will describe our exploration into both solution and solid state structures resulting from supramolecular associations. Examples will include the sequestration of the highly electronegative fluoride ion and its hydrated cluster (**1** and **2**) [1-4]; shape-accommodation for pseudo-linear dicarboxylates (**3**) [5]; the influence of a supramolecularly bound proton on solution chemistry of ditopic palladium(II) acetate complexes (**4**); and, finally, to potassium-bound *myo*-inositol-1,2,3,4,5,6-hexakisphosphate, phytate, (**5**), an important agricultural organophosphate.

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Development of non destructive analytical methodologies for the conservation diagnosis of urban built heritage based on spectroscopy and thermodynamic modeling

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Our built heritage is mainly made by stone and thus, it is prone to decay by natural and irreversible processes. Moreover, materials are also exposed to an anthropogenic environment, in which there are many factors that can accelerate its deterioration. Due to this fact, before proposing any solutions to its maintenance, preservation or revitalization, the study of building materials requires a wide knowledge of the factors that have an influence in their decay. Therefore, nowadays, the development of new diagnostic methodologies has gained importance in the field of material characterization. Moreover, given the intrinsic value of the samples, the usefulness of non-invasive methods that can be used in-situ preserving the integrity of materials is highlighted [1].

In this sense, this work is focused on developing non destructive analytical methodologies for the in-situ diagnosis of the urban built heritage, affected mainly by environmental factors. In this manner, the characterization, interpretation, classification and severity of damage suffered by building materials are assessed through real cases, paying special attention to establishing the origin and the chemical process involved in the pathologies by means of chemometric and thermodynamic models.

The proposed goals have been achieved thanks to the development and improvement of different combined methodologies, highlighting the usefulness presented by Raman spectroscopy in real conservation works. Moreover, the handicaps resulting from field analysis have been successfully reduced thanks to the implementation of DRIFT, providing a new path for the in-situ research of built heritage. Furthermore, micro destructive methods have been proposed to detect the penetration capacity of the weathering agents as well as to quantify the severity of salt damage, in accordance with existing legislation (Fig.1). Besides, the bases for reducing the sampling required for the quantification process have been established, thorough a non invasive method based on cellulose patch application. Finally, given the differences observed caused by seasonal changes, a study to describe the behavior of salts content under changing climate conditions, in a real intervention process, has been carried out in order to select the most suitable actions to prevent the progress of existing pathologies [2-3].

Figure 1: Work protocol proposed to diagnose study of built heritage.

The operational cases analyzed demonstrate the aggressive attack suffered by our built heritage, evidencing the suitability of the methodologies proposed as indispensable tool to perform a correct scientific study that allows us performing fast scientific diagnosis, helpful for the restoration or conservation procedures. Thanks to them, the need to take decisions only in terms of the expertise of the conservators could be avoided.

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Nanoparticles with biomedical applications

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Nanotechnology is an increasing field which incorporates the use of materials with submicron dimensions, usually between 1 and 100 nm in size [1]. This confers them a high surface area to mass ratio, adaptive sizes, shape and composition which make them valuable tools in biology and medicine [2]. Over the last years, there has been a progressively growing interest in using nanoparticles in different biomedical applications such as targeted drug delivery, hyperthermia, photoablation therapy, bioimaging and biosensors [3,4]. Therefore, nanomedicine has arisen as the application of nanoscale materials toward the benefit of human health.

Here, we will focus on two examples of how nanoparticles might have an impact on the medical field. One example is an imaging material for melanoma tumor cells based on the use of magnetic nanoparticles. The other is the development of liposome nanoparticles as diagnostic tools for myocardial infarction.

The growing incidence of malignant melanoma is an increasingly public health problem that concerns the worldwide scientific community. It is a type of highly-aggressive cancer and life-threatening disease due to its propensity to metastasize. Most melanomas may be detected at an early stage since they are predominantly found on the skin. Furthermore, the rising public knowledge and awareness about melanoma, together with the new advances in dermoscopy facilitate an early detection of this cancer, which is of crucial importance in saving lives. However, a percentage of melanomas are located in other areas different from skin, and also melanoma cells can spread to almost anywhere in the body. Early detection is very difficult in these cases and prognosis in advanced clinical stages is extremely unfavorable. Therefore, it is of paramount importance to develop new tools able to provide an objective means of evaluating and diagnosing this type of cancer from its

earliest stages indicating the location of melanoma tumors where they had been spread and to treat them.

The development of contrast agents based on magnetic nanoparticles and modified with specific biomarkers for melanoma, would allow the achievement of images indicating the location of tumors derived from melanoma. These nanoparticles have an increasing use as contrast agents and can allow exceptional real-time visualization and quantification of cancer cells.

Each year cardiovascular diseases (CVD) accounts for 17.3 million deaths worldwide and causes over 4 million deaths in Europe and over 1.9 million deaths in the European Union. Myocardial infarction (MI) is the biggest consequence of CVD with an estimated global mortality rate of 7.4 million per year. Based on data from the European Association for Cardiovascular Prevention & Rehabilitation, nearly 10000 people under 65 suffered a fatal heart attack in UK last year, the equivalent of 200 deaths every week. In addition, 1 in 5 people who survive a MI have a second cardiovascular event in the first year, even when receiving optimal treatment and care. These data make clear the strong human impact of CVD.

We have developed a non-invasive strategy to visualize the damaged heart using lipid-based liposomal nanoparticles that specifically target the injured myocardium after intravenous injection.

Figure 1. Left. Melanoma tumor imaged by MRI using magnetic nanoparticles. Right. Myocardial infarction region imaged by MRI (above) and with optical imaging (below) using multimodal liposomes.

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Biomimetics of siderophores and their possible applications

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The difficulties in synthesis of structurally complicated natural siderophores (low molecular weight molecules produced by microorganisms to acquire iron) has directed the siderophore research towards biomimetic chemistry, aiming at mimicking or reproducing the function of the natural product rather than its detailed structure. This approach allowed to diversify the arsenal of biologically active siderophore-type molecules, introduce additional desired chemical and/or physical properties, and provide means to identify general motifs governing an interplay between structure and function in biological activity.

Following these principles, we have been working on characterization of novel biomimetic compounds, artificial siderophores, in terms of iron complex formation and stability, for the construction of structural probes of microbial iron uptake processes and iron sensors [1-3].

Over the years, we were able to couple iron binding or its release with a signaling component in order to elicit spectrophotometric signals. Attaching fluorescent group to Fe(III) binding skeleton or fusing the binding site with a fluorescent probe into a single functionality provided tools to track the path of the iron from the environment to the cells of microbial species [1-3].

Here we will present the Fe(III) binding properties of novel artificial siderophores in the perspective of using the compounds as tools for investigating iron uptake by siderophore-utilizing organisms. We will also discuss abilities of these biomimetics to coordinate other metal ions in order to use them for imaging and detection purposes.

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Fluorescent systems for metal cations and anions sensing

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The development of chemical sensors (chemosensors) based on the fluorescence response and able to signal the presence of a species has always been of particular importance for biological and environmental interest. The chemosensor is the sensing unit of the fluorescent system; it directly interacts with the target and confers selectivity to the device, and the signal transduction unit. The target of a chemosensors are several, usually a single species as a metal cation or an anion but also an environment as a cell compartment. Effective fluorescent chemosensor commonly must transform the recognition of the species into an easily measurable and very sensitive light signal from the fluorophore. The fluorescent systems have found a great success because they are versatile and easy to use; they allow the obtainment of low cost instrumentation with respect to classic analytical one also permitting a real time analysis of the sample. For this reason, in the last few years, great attention has paid to them and many new fluorescent systems were developed.

In the last years, we are interested in fluorescent chemosensors able to signal metal cations and anions in solution, designing and achieving several fluorescent molecular frameworks. These systems must be able to interact with the target ion in solution signaling the presence by changing fluorescence properties, as well as the emission wavelength, and emission intensity, or by the appearance of a new fluorescence band different from those of the free sensor.

Chemosensors for metal ions generally contains one or more fluorophores linked to a coordinating active moiety through a spacer. The coordinating active part shows functions able to coordinate a metal ion as a polyamine or other binding functions and can be open-chain structure or closed macrocyclic structure, the choice of the donor-functions and of the molecular framework is determined by the metal ion which has to be detected.[1]

On the other hand, systems able to give a response to the presence of an anion usually exploit weaker binding forces as, charge-charge, H-bonding or charge-dipole interactions [2] but, also metal complex showing an unsaturated coordination environment of the metal ion, can behave as chemosensor for anions.[3]

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Model Studies for the Biotransformation Reactions of Half-sandwich Type Platinum Metal Complexes

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Administration of $[(\eta^6\text{-arene})\text{M}(\text{XY})\text{Z}]$ (M = Ru, Os) or $[(\eta^5\text{-Cp}^x)\text{M}(\text{XY})\text{Z}]$ (M = Rh, Ir, Cp^x = cyclopentadienyl, pentamethylcyclopentadienyl) complexes with potential antiproliferative activity may result in ligand exchange reactions and formation of complexes with high and low molecular mass components of the various biofluids.

For several years we have been working on exploring these interactions by studying the complexation reactions of the above metal ions with various small bioligands in aqueous solution with the aid of the combined use of pH-potentiometry, NMR and MS in order to estimate the stability constants and stoichiometry of the metal-ligand species present in these systems and to obtain information on the most likely solution structure of the complexes formed. Furthermore, to support the solution speciation studies these interactions are also studied in the solid state by isolation of the major complexes and by characterization of them using various analytical techniques and by DFT calculations [1-10].

This contribution will focus on some of our results obtained lately in this field.

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Fernando Pulidori Prize 2018

Equilibrium and thorough spectroscopic characterization of the complex formation processes of NiSOD enzyme fragments

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Superoxide dismutase enzymes are a dedicate class of enzymes which are able to keep the superoxide anion radical at a controlled low concentration level via the disproportion of these radicals to molecular oxygen and hydrogen peroxide.[1,2] Four different classes of SOD enzymes can be distinguished by considering the metal ion in the active center.[3] A recently discovered SOD enzyme contains nickel ion in the active site [4] and the disproportion reaction occurs through a proton coupled electron-transfer mechanism parallel with the rearrangement of coordination sphere of nickel from square-planar (nickel(II), spin state = 0) to square-pyramidal (nickel(III), spin state = 1/2).[5] With respect to nickel binding, the N-terminal region has a crucial role in metal binding, however, in-depth characterization of the complex formation processes of the nickel binding hook have not been reported yet.

We have launched systematic studies on the complex formation processes of peptides mimicking the N-terminal binding hook of the NiSOD. These were the HCDL-NH₂, HCDLPCGVY-NH₂ and the N-terminally protected Ac-HCDLPCGVY-NH₂. Their nickel(II) and zinc(II) complexes were studied by potentiometric, UV-vis, CD, NMR, ESI-TOF MS and MS-MS experimental techniques. Our results indicated, that the terminal amino group of HCDLPCGVY-NH₂ is the primary metal binding site for nickel(II) resulting in the high nickel(II) binding affinity *via* the formation of (NH₂,N⁻,S⁻,S⁻) coordination environment. In addition to the traditional spectroscopic methods, the preference of this binding mode has been proved by MS-MS experiments, too. Moreover, this donor set is able to compete with the albumin-like (NH₂,N⁻,N⁻,N_{im}) donors in nickel(II) binding.

The acylation of the amino terminus significantly reduces the nickel(II) binding affinity of the nonapeptide (Figure 1.). There is, however, no significant difference in the zinc(II) binding affinity of the N-terminally free and protected peptides, both ligands form zinc(II) complexes with outstanding high stability. In the case of acetylated peptide, only 10% of the total amount of nickel(II) is in complex while the zinc(II) complexes with macrochelate structures are the major species in the whole pH range as it is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Theoretical distribution curve calculated in the Ni(II):Ac-HCDLPCGVY-NH₂:HCDL-NH₂:HCDLPCGVY-NH₂ 1:1:1:1 system at $c_L = 1.5$ mM.

Figure 2. Predominance distribution curves as a function of pH calculated in the Ni(II):Zn(II):Ac-HCDLPCGVY-NH₂ 1:1:1 system. $c_L = 1.5$ mM

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Oral Communications

Non-covalent interactions in the coordination sphere of the uranyl ion: an experimental and theoretical study

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An understanding of the plethora of non-covalent interactions is of importance, not just in structural chemistry but also materials and biological chemistry. While the hydrogen bond is the most well studied, over the past few years other non-conventional noncovalent interactions have garnered significant amount of attention, such as halogen bonding [1], pnictogen bonding [2] and chalcogenide bonding [3]. The latter is a relatively recent addition to the toolbox of crystal engineering. All of these non-classical interactions can be described via a σ -hole mechanism, that is visualized as a region of positive electrostatic potential found on an empty σ^* orbital [4]. The strength of the interactions depend on the polarizability of the chalcogenide atom, so as the group is descended the strength increases. However few examples of chalcogenide interactions exist where a metal ion is included [5]. We have noted that simple uranyl coordination compounds $[R_4N]_3[UO_2(NCE)_5]$ (R = Me, Et, ⁿPr, ⁿBu, Me₃Bz, Et₃Bz; E = S, Se) can be used as a convenient tecton to study non-covalent S...S or Se...Se interactions in the solid state and solution, using a combination of X-ray crystallography, spectroscopic measurements and theory [6]. In the solid state, S...S interactions are dependent upon the nature of the alkyl ammonium cation, whilst Se...Se interactions are more common. Moreover, the solid state structures allows us to interrogate U=O...H-C and E...H-C weak hydrogen bonding. Spectroscopic measurements indicate that these interactions do not perturb the uranyl bonding as shown by vibrational and photoluminescence spectroscopy, although the latter shows an unusual coupling of the NCE vibrational mode to the U=O MLCT based emission. A theoretical examination of these and model compounds $[UO_2X_2(H_2O)_3]$ (X = Cl, Br, NCSe) gives more detailed insight into the weak interactions and the Se...Se interaction can be described as a charge transfer from the lone pair coordinated NCSe to the σ^* orbital of the acceptor NCSe ion.

Figure. **Top left:** solid state packing diagram of [Et₃NBz]₃[UO₂(NCSe)₅] with dotted black lines indicating Se...Se interactions; **top right:** Molecular electrostatic potential projected onto the 0.001 au isodensity surface for [UO₂(NCSe)₅]³⁻ showing a σ-hole; **bottom:** NBO orbitals involved in the Se...Se interactions.

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Robson-Type Metallomacrocycles Acting in Second-Sphere: Selective Complexation of Cuprate Ions

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Second-sphere coordination plays an important role in supramolecular chemistry and coordination chemistry [1-4]. Several macrocycles such as crown ethers, cyclodextrins, and cyclophanes have been employed to generate second-sphere adducts with transition metal complexes. For the most part, the components interact via non-covalent bonding interactions, such as hydrogen bonding, π - π stacking, and hydrophobic interactions.

The hexaaza-dithiophenolate macrocycle H_2L is known to support mixed-ligand complexes of the type $[M_2L(\mu-X)]^+$ featuring a face-sharing bioctahedral core structure (Figure 1) [5]. The structures of some cobalt and nickel complexes co-ligated by small halide (F^- , Cl^- , Br^-) and pseudo-halide anions (N_3^- , NCS^- , OCN^-) have been reported [5-7]. The macrocycle invariably adopts a specific conformation, in which the co-ligand is surrounded by two propylene chains (marked in red). The size- and form-selective binding is attributed to a high degree of pre-organization and to repulsive interactions between the guest ion X and the propylene groups of the macrocycle.

Figure 1. Left: Dinuclear $[M_2L(\mu-X)]^+$ complexes supported by the macrocycle $(L^2)^{2-}$. Right: 3D representation of the structure of the $[M_2L(\mu-X)]^+$ complexes highlighting the anion binding site and the cuprate binding site.

In the course of our studies, it was found that the $[M_2L(\mu-X)]^+$ complexes readily form adducts with halogeno cuprate anions ($[Cu^IHal_2]^-$, Hal = Cl, Br, I). The cuprate ions are bound to one of the two thiophenolato-S atoms of the Robson macrocycle and interact also via a second-sphere (cation- π) interaction with an aromatic ring ($d(Cu \cdots center^{aromatic\ ring}) = 3.2 \text{ \AA}$). So far, three such complexes

were obtained, namely $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{L}(\mu\text{-F9CuBr}_2)]\text{ClO}_4$, $[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}_2\text{L}(\mu\text{-F})\text{CuI}_2]$ and $[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}_2\text{L}(\mu\text{-OH})\text{CuI}_2]$. The synthetic procedures and results from IR spectroscopy, X-ray crystallography, and temperature dependent magnetic susceptibility measurements are reported herein. Spectrophotometric titration and accompanying DFT calculations were also performed to shed light on the bonding interactions in the second sphere.

Figure 2. Molecular structure of the $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}\text{Co}^{\text{III}}(\mu\text{-F})\text{CuBr}_2]^+$ cation in crystals of $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}\text{Co}^{\text{III}}(\mu\text{-F})\text{CuBr}_2]\text{ClO}_4 \cdot 2\text{MeCN}$.

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Intramolecular Interactions in Transition Metal Bis(Dicarbollide) Complexes and Their Role in Design of Molecular Switches

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Molecular switches are molecules or supramolecular complexes having bistability, i.e., the ability to exist in two or more stable forms, among which may be reversible transitions under external influence. The design and the study of molecules capable of performing mechanical movement is an important problem of modern chemistry. The bis(dicarbollide) complexes of transition metals $[3,3'-M(1,2-C_2B_9H_{11})_2]^{n-}$ were proposed as suitable stable organometallic units for design of molecular switches [1]. The control over the ligand rotation in these complexes can be reached by introducing substituents which could provide stabilization of certain rotamers due to weak interactions between the ligands, on the one hand, and which can participate as Lewis bases in complex formation with external metals resulting in a change in the rotation angle of the ligands, on the other hand. A series of isomeric iron and cobalt bis(dicarbollide) complexes $[X,Y-(MeS)_2-3,3'-Co(1,2-C_2B_9H_{10})_2]^-$ were prepared using the corresponding methylsulfanyl or dimethylsulfonium derivatives of *nido*-carborane (Schemes 1 and 2) [2,3].

Scheme 1

For the 8,8'- and 4,4'-isomers *transoid* and *gauche* conformations are stabilized by two pairs of intramolecular $\text{CH}_{\text{carb}} \cdots \text{S}$ hydrogen bonds, whereas for the 4,7'-isomers *gauche* conformation is stabilized by one pair of the $\text{CH}_{\text{carb}} \cdots \text{S}$ bonds (Fig. 1). Complexation of the methylsulfanyl derivatives with various labile transition metal complexes will be discussed.

Figure 1

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Gastrointestinal speciation and mineral bioavailability: dietary management of vegetable-based meals

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myo-inositol phosphates are essential biomolecules in all eukaryotic cells. Among them, phytate (Scheme 1, L¹²⁻) is largely abundant in vegetable-based products and it possesses various beneficial effects in health, such as being a broad spectrum anti-neoplastic and lipid-lowering agent. Conversely, it has been categorized as an antinutrient, a precipitating agent that reduces the absorption of Fe, Zn and Ca, causing a global nutritional problem. This contradiction has raised a debate [1], and chemical quantitative data are still not available to give an answer to this problem. In this work we tackle this dichotomy, building an *in silico* gastrointestinal model to estimate the phytate's chemical speciation at the duodenum and the mineral bioaccessibility during the digestion of different vegetable-based meals.

Scheme 1. Structure of phytate anion (L¹²⁻).

Some missing thermodynamic data on the interaction of phytate with metal ions were necessary as an input and were determined by potentiometry (0.15 M Me₄NCl, 37.0 °C). Soluble mononuclear ([Mⁿ⁺(H_xL)]^{(12-n-x)-}) and polynuclear ([M_x(H_yL)]^{(12-n-x)-}) metal complexes were detected. Besides, the solid metal phytates were synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, infrared spectra and solubility measurements (for example: Zn₅(H₂L)·14H₂O and Fe₄L·22H₂O; K_{s0} = -42.8(9) and -74.7(2), respectively, 0.15 M Me₄NCl, 37.0 °C). This information, the chemical composition of each food product and the physiological parameters of the gastrointestinal tract [2-3] were included in a mathematical model, which contains 6483 chemical species and more than 45000 thermodynamic data. This model was handled with the program JESS [4], allowing the calculation of the gastrointestinal speciation and mineral bioaccessibility for each tested intake.

For instance, for an intake of one glass of soy formula, our nutritional model showed that as both the soy protein and phytate are less concentrated, the bioaccessibility (solubility) of iron increases (Figure 1). This is in line with the reported experimental data, giving evidence of the satisfactory performance of the computational model [5]. The model also allowed, for the first time, to unveil the chemical basis behind these trends. When the concentration of soy protein is small, as the phytate is depleted from the intake the calcium ion is released to the solution and interacts with the phosphate anion. In this process, the iron ion, which was precipitated with the phosphate anion,

is set free and complexed by glucosamine, raising its bioaccessibility. On the other hand, if there is a low phytate concentration, a depletion of the protein content leads to an increase in the concentration of non-adsorbed calcium ion. This triggers the precipitation of the phosphate anion (as calcium salt), releasing the iron ion initially bound to it, which in turn is complexed by glucosamine.

Figure 1. Calculated iron solubility (bioaccessibility) at duodenum as a function of phytate and soy protein concentration (intake: 250 mL soy formula; experimental data in reference [5]).

The nutritional model also permitted us to understand the general chemical speciation of phytate during the digestion of the most common meals. Phytate is expected in the duodenum to be mostly precipitated with magnesium and calcium, and it only reduces zinc and iron bioaccessibility by disturbing their adsorption and solution equilibria. The citrate and glucosamine are the most important solubilizing agents at gastrointestinal level. The application of the gastrointestinal model allows us to understand nutritional tendencies by predicting the bioaccessibility of essential metal ions. As an example, we have found that although the cocoa negatively affects the level of milk's available calcium, this effect can be counteracted by adding orange juice to the meal.

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Anion Encapsulation Drives the Formation of Dimeric Ln^{III}[15-metallacrown-5]³⁺ Complexes in Neutral Aqueous Solution

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Molecular capsules have gained considerable interest over the past decades as vehicles capable of selective molecular recognition and catalysis [1]. While there are different categories of such species including purely covalent organic structures or organic fragments that associate through hydrogen bonding interactions, the most heavily studied are self-assembled architectures that use metal atoms to template the desired molecular environment [2]. There are several examples of soluble self-assembling compartments capable of recognizing guests [3].

One class of metallamacrocycles that has seen applications in guest recognition, molecular magnetism and luminescent spectroscopy is metallacrowns [4], which can be prepared with varying sizes but also can change the composition of metal and ligand and total charge. An important subgroup of metallacrowns, 15-MC-5, can be prepared as 3D structures or planar materials with transition metals such as Cu(II) in the metallacrown ring position and lanthanides in the captured central position. Most interesting are those complexes prepared with chiral ligands, such as phenylalanine hydroxamic acid (pheHA) [5], which lead to the formation of face differentiated metallacrowns that place five ligand side chains on the same face (see figure below).

These systems associate in the solid state forming chiral compartments that exhibit non-linear optical properties when the proper guest is captured in these cavities [6]. While crystallographic studies clearly demonstrate that hydrophobic compartments of different volume can be prepared by varying the hydroxamic acid ligand side chain [7], there is limited information on whether such dimeric structures exist in solution [8] and are able to sequester guests into the generated molecular capsule. To this end we have examined the binding features of some Ln(III)[15-MC_{Cu(II)NpheHA-5}]³⁺ (MC) hosts with different dicarboxylate guest molecules having variable length, size and different degrees of unsaturation. We have explored to what extent MC is still capable to form dimeric complexes in aqueous solution through nano-ITC experiments in neutral aqueous solution. The splitting of the Gibbs free energy into the enthalpic and entropic contributions allowed us to unveil the forces driving the molecular recognition process in solution.

We demonstrated that chiral, amphipathic MCs may form dimeric complexes with both aromatic and aliphatic dicarboxylates in aqueous solution at neutral pH and that the chain length of the guest is a more important criterion for recognition than is the degree of molecular unsaturation [9]. These data resolve the long-standing question as to whether these MC-based complexes exist in solution and show for the first time that their formation is a consequence of the host/guest interaction.

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Porous metallacrown frameworks: crystal engineering through a mindful ligand design

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Metallacrowns are metallamacrocycles, inorganic analogs of crown ethers, that originate by self-assembly of bischelating ligands (e.g. hydroxamic acids) and metal ions. The metallacrown scaffold is characterized by the (M-N-O)_n connectivity. The interest in these systems arise from their molecular architecture, where a relatively large amount of metal ions are confined in a small molecular volume. As a result, metallacrowns show peculiar chemical physical features, such as luminescence or single-molecule magnets behavior. [1] Moreover, properties and structure of this class of compound are tunable through a mindful choice of the building blocks set. [2] In fact, several metallacrowns known in literature were isolated starting from a pre-synthetic design. [3]

We present here three new metallacrowns-based materials, that were prepared using salicylhydroxamate derivatives and Mn(II/III) as selected building blocks. The crystal engineering allowed us to turn a non-porous 3D architecture into porous ones, through the introduction of one single functionality on the aromatic ring of the Shi³⁻ ligand (Figure 1-Left).

Figure 1–Left: H₃Shi, H₃pAShi and H₃pPyShi derivatives structures; **–Right:** View along the 3-fold axis of the molecular unit resulting from a) H₃Shi, b) H₃pAShi and c) H₃pPyShi ligands respectively. From this perspective the 3 blasé propeller motif is highlighted.

The salicylhydroxamic acid ligand (H₃Shi) react with manganese acetate to originate a Mn₁₁(μ₃-O)₄(Shi³⁻)₆ metalacryptate, which resembles a 3-blade propeller. (Figure 1-Right, a) Neighboring propellers interact through sodium ions, leading to a tightly packed and not porous coordination polymer (Figure 2-a).

The introduction of an amino function onto the H₃pAShi ligand leads the propellers to interact not only through sodium ions, but also via supramolecular interactions. Infact, -NH₂ crosslink facing endeca-manganese clusters. The overall arrangement result in the formation of hexagonal channels, which correspond to 39 % of the unit cell volume (Figure 2-b).

The pyridyl function of H₃pPyShi, leads the system to form a metallacrown-based metal organic framework, whose nodes are rapresented by the endeca-manganese units. The H₃pPyShi propellers are connected thanks to the coordinative bonds formed by the 6 ligands, which coordinate a Mn ion through the hydroxamic function on one side and another Mn ion through the pyridinic N atom on the other side. The resulting 3D network shows channels in all the three dimensions. Those channels are hexagonal when viewed along the c axis (Figure 2-c), whereas along both the a and b axis they are smaller and trapezoidal. The overall voids correspond to 55% of the unit cell volume.

Figure 2: packing of: **a)** Mn₁₁(μ₃-O)₄(Shi³⁻)₆; **b)** Mn₁₁(μ₃-O)₄(pAShi³⁻)₆; **c)** Mn₁₁(μ₃-O)₄(pPyShi³⁻)₆.

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NMR and structural characterization of paramagnetic metallacrown architectures containing lanthanides

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There is a growing interest in the development of molecular architectures containing lanthanides. These ions are actually attractive for their peculiar chemico-physical properties. The intrinsic luminescence of lanthanides that spans from the visible to the near infrared, or their magnetic anisotropies at the basis of the single-molecule magnetic behavior of Ln-containing materials, are just examples of these features.[1]

In the field of self-assembled supramolecular architectures, metallacrowns (MC) have received attention as metallamacrocycles capable to encapsulate lanthanide ions and give rise to stable molecular entities.[2] Among the peculiar structural features of metallacrowns is the possibility to tune the ligand field operated by the oxygen donor atoms of the cavity from prolate to oblate. This ultimately offers a window into the design of supramolecular architectures that lead in a predictable way to a highly anisotropic ground state for a given f-element. Currently, in our laboratory we are exploring the possibility to isolate porous 3D architectures using metallacrowns as building blocks.[3] We expect that the inclusion of guests into the pores of these materials will produce an overall change of the 3D structure that, although smooth, may impact the magnetic properties of the solid materials to allow a magnetic-based detection of the guest molecules.

Figure 1 Left and center: Structural representation of $\text{LnNa}(\text{OAc})_4[12\text{-MC}_{\text{GaIII}(\text{N})\text{shi-4}}$; right: stacked ^1H NMR spectra of Er(III) and Y(III) MCs.

For the rational development of these magnetic-responsive materials, it is desirable to have access to a fast and reliable method to determine the ligand field parameters of the molecules used as the building blocks. For this purpose, we have recently reported the ¹H NMR study of paramagnetic LnNa(OAc)₄[12-MC_{MnIII(N)shi}-4] complexes (H₃shi = salicylhydroxamic acid, Figure 1).[4] Actually, the pseudocontact (or dipolar) contribution of the Ln(III) to the overall NMR chemical shift contains both the information on the structure in solution and that on the ligand field. Therefore, treating the ¹H NMR data on these Ln-metallacrowns using the structural parameters obtained by X ray crystallography we were able to obtain information on chemico-physical parameters that affect the overall paramagnetism of these molecules.

Moving one step forward in the study of these molecules, in this contribution we report the ¹H NMR characterization in solution of self-assembled heterotrimetallic Ln(III)/Ga(III)/Na(I) MCs. Compared to the spectra of the parent Ln(III)/Mn(III) complexes, the gallium analogues present a higher level of complexity. The results obtained on these complexes will be compared, and explained on the basis of the X ray structural data and of their integrity in solution.

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Monitoring chicken meat spoilage: from pH indicators to on-package labels

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The meat spoilage is a very complex combination of processes, related to bacterial activities which, depending on external conditions, are responsible of oxidation of glucose, lactic acid and fatty acid and, eventually, of degradation of proteins.

The methods commonly employed to evaluate meat quality require instrumental or microbiological analysis and sensory evaluation. They are all expensive methods, that require specialized people and have long time response.

Numerous efforts are under way to develop automated techniques and/or methods that allow a continuous and simple monitoring, for in-field application, like home setting, supermarket, store. In this way, through simple, low-cost and highly efficient and effective methods, also consumers could directly detect the meat freshness. [1] We can include in this category biosensors, electronic devices (e-nose and e-tongue) [2] and colorimetric sensors.

Colorimetric sensors based on colorimetric indicators are capable of changing color due to a reaction with volatile compounds produced on packaged meat samples. Either included directly on packaging, or attached with on-package sticker, they offer the simplest, practical, instrumentless way for monitoring meat freshness, directly detected using naked eye.

Actually, many examples can be found that follow this idea. Immobilized bromocresol green was used for fish spoilage indicator, or mixed pH dye based indicator as been proposed as a “chemical barcode” (bromothymol blue and methyl red or bromothymol blue, bromocresol green and phenol red were used as single indicator). [1] The disadvantage with a single sensor is like to that encountered in classical acid base titration technique using a pH dye. It is difficult to determine the onset of detection related to the spoilage threshold, where it could be too early or too late when it correlated with microbial growth.

Moreover, in literature the attention was almost always focused identification of biological amines, BA. As demonstrated, [3] in the early spoilage other events take place, and the chemical spoilage index, CSI, is associated with production of EtOH, 3 methyl 1-butanol and free fatty acid, particularly acetic acid, which are definitively the major VOCs. Any meat at this stage is still a safety product. Amines production begins after, when the estimated shelf lives are beyond the expiry date, and meat spoilage is manifested as off-odors and discoloration. Consumption of meat at this stage could be a serious hazard.

With this in our mind, we selected different dyes that change their color in a wider pH range and focused our attention on chicken meat, firstly following the spoilage aerobically at ambient temperature.

We selected a panel of pH indicator dyes with different pK_a values. [4] Ligands were embedded into an anion exchange cellulose sheets, to obtain colored spots, see Figure 1a. Color image analysis was chosen for the colorimetric analysis.

An array of 6 spots were placed over the tray containing a sample of the skinless chicken breast, but under the PVC package, avoiding direct contact with meat. Photos of the array were acquired for each sample as function of time, RGB index were used for monitoring the spoilage, Principal Component Analysis to model the data set: three clusters of three different degradation step, the early spoilage (green cluster), intermediate spoilage (yellow cluster) and the final spoilage (red cluster) were identified, see Figure 1b.

Figure 1: a) evolution with time of sensing spots in contact with around 3 hg of poultry meat, as described above. From left to right the embedded spots are: *m*-cresol purple-CC@, *o*-cresol red-CC@, bromothymol blue-CC@, thymol blue-CC@, chlorophenol red-CC@, Ellman's reagent-CC@. b) Scores plot of the 2 first component of PCA on RGB evolution on 6 different poultry samples, where the safety area, green, the warning area, orange, the hazard area, red are discriminated.

As validation the spoilage steps of the spots are simultaneously analyzed by SPE analysis in mass spectroscopy of VOS's, on head space of meat samples. We will complete the spoilage model of chicken breast in a domestic refrigerator, which has a slightly different evolution, due to different bacteria involved in the spoilage.

This is the preliminary study for developing sensing packages for food industry. We will ultimately select not more than three dyes, to be included not simply on cellulose spots, but directly in PVC or PE sheets, in a forthcoming project in collaboration with colleagues of Organic Chemistry and the R&D laboratory - technical support special films department of ITP (Industria Termoplastica Pavese), extremely interested in developing new tailored materials.

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Extraction of toxic metals: from fundamental advances in macrocyclic chemistry to soft materials incorporated in ultra-sensitive detectors

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Exposure to lead-contaminated tap water is a persistent issue in most western countries, which primarily concerns children and the economically less-favored population. Once ingested through the gastrointestinal track, lead accumulates in vital organs and bones, and finally causes a number of diseases ranging from anemia to nervous system degeneration. In order to avoid all risks of increasing blood lead level in infants and protect them against the adverse neurotoxic effects, the World Health Organization recommends a maximum uptake of 25 µg per week and kilogram of corporal mass in conjunction with a maximum acceptable concentration in drinking water of 10 µg/L.

In that context, we got involved in the design of a cartridge-based purification system that could be mounted directly on a kitchen faucet. Solid-phase extraction by covalent attachment of a lead-selective sequestering agent to the surface of silica gel was thought as an efficient method to reduce the lead level below the new parametric value, as shown by pipe-loop tests [1]. High binding affinity, selectivity, and fast uptake kinetics are of crucial importance. This fine-tuning was most conveniently achieved by taking advantage of the outstanding coordination properties of *N*-functionalized tetraazamacrocycles bearing amidic side chains [2]. Their structural, thermodynamic, and kinetic characterization will be discussed, together with solid/liquid extraction data [3, 4].

The outstanding recognition properties of some mesoporous hybrid materials were further exploited for the selective and sensitive detection of lead(II) in water by electrochemical methods [5]. The solid adsorbents were incorporated into carbon paste electrodes, which were used for lead accumulation at open-circuit followed by an anodic stripping square-wave voltammetric detection. Under optimal conditions, a linear calibration curve was obtained between 10^{-8} and 10^{-7} M, while the detection limit of 2.7×10^{-9} M was found well below the European regulatory limit of lead in consumption water.

This project found further interesting outreaches in the field of chemosensing [6]. The most efficient system developed was a reusable surface plasmon resonance chip which allows the quantitative and selective detection of mercury(II) ions in water at the 10^{-11} M level [7]. The surface-modified gold sensor consists of a rarefied self-assembled monolayer of octanethiol topped by a Langmuir-Blodgett monolayer of an amphiphilic and highly-specific chelator. The interdigitated architecture confers to the bilayer a high packing density, surface coverage, and binding-group accessibility.

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A new approach for arsenic speciation in natural waters through complexation with a dithiophosphinic acid derivative incorporated in a polymer inclusion membrane

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Arsenic is a toxic element found in water mainly from natural sources. Ground water contains inorganic arsenite (As(III)) and/or arsenate (As(V)), being the first the most toxic form. Thus, it is necessary to develop reliable methodologies for the selective detection of As in natural waters.

In literature, studies on As(V) extraction are reported [1]. However, to the best of our knowledge, only few works concerning As(III) extraction are available, but not in natural matrices but in synthetic samples [2]. Accordingly, in this study we present the possibility of using the extractant Bis(2,4,4-trimethylpentyl)dithiophosphinic acid, Cyanex 301, to complex arsenic species and to investigate whether it is possible to discriminate between the two chemical forms, As(III) and As(V). Moreover, a simple and novel analytical methodology is also proposed incorporating this complexing agent in a polymeric matrix to determine arsenite content in natural water samples.

Preliminary solvent extraction experiments (using a 0.1 M Cyanex 301 solution in toluene) were performed in 0.1 M HCl solutions containing 10 mg L⁻¹ of As(III) or As(V). It was found that As(III) was completely extracted after 30 minutes whereas 24 hours were required for the complete extraction of As(V). This different kinetic behaviour can be exploited for speciation purposes.

These results encouraged us to attempt the extraction by using polymer inclusion membranes (PIMs), which need a very small amount of organic components, and thus, are an eco-friendly option of the solvent extraction process. PIMs consist of a polymer, which provides mechanical strength, the carrier, which is the responsible of the extraction process, and sometimes also a plasticizer can be used to provide elasticity. These membranes are easy to prepare and thanks to their versatility can be used in many analytical applications, especially in the removal of pollutants from waters [3]. PIMs were prepared by incorporating the extractant in a cellulose triacetate (CTA) polymeric matrix with a final composition of 50% CTA-50% Cyanex 301 (% in mass). Results demonstrated that when Cyanex 301 is entrapped in a polymer the quantitative extraction of As(III) requires 3 hours while As(V) was not extracted, even after 24 hours. Therefore, we extended the use of PIMs to natural waters, in particular well water and tap water samples acidified with HCl. Despite the complexity of the matrix, As(III) extraction was complete, showing the good performance of these membranes containing Cyanex 301.

Taking advantage of the characteristics of the PIMs, we investigated the possibility of determining arsenite preconcentrated in PIMs by Energy Dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (EDXRF). Loaded PIMs were directly analyzed by EDXRF using the experimental conditions described in [4]. Resulting EDXRF spectra are displayed in Fig. 1(a), where it can be seen that As

signal increases when increasing the metal concentration initially present in the aqueous solution. The representation of the peak area obtained for each membrane vs. the initial As content in the water sample shows a very good linearity (see Fig.1(b)).

Figure 1. (a) EDXRF spectra for PIMs contacted with spiked water at pH 1 at different As(III) concentration levels and (b) the corresponding calibration curve using Ka line intensity.

This result indicates that there is a strong relationship that can be used as a calibration curve for future determination of As(III) when contained in water samples.

Thus, this methodology combining As extraction by PIM and EDXRF determination can be viewed as a promising approach to perform not only As(III) quantification in natural waters but also speciation studies.

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Biospeciation and anti-diabetic effects of oxidovanadium(IV) complexes

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The reaction of the vanadyl ion (VO^{2+}) with imidazole-4-carboxylic acid (Im4COOH), imidazole-2-carboxylic acid (Im2COOH) and methylimidazole-2-carboxylic acid (MeIm2COOH), respectively, in the presence of small bioligands (bL) [oxalate (Ox), lactate (Lact), and phosphate (Phos)] and high molecular weight (HMM) human serum proteins [albumin (HSA) and transferrin (hTf)] were studied in aqueous solution using potentiometric acid base titrations under oxygen- and carbon dioxide-free conditions. The data obtained from these titrations was used to calculate the binary and ternary stability constants using the program HYPERQUAD. The overall stability constants for VO^{2+} -L-Ox system ($\log \beta_{1111} = 18.9, 18.79$ and 19.86), VO^{2+} -L-Lact system ($\log \beta_{1111} = 21.83, 20.98$ and 22.86), and VO^{2+} -L-Phos system ($\log \beta_{1111} = 27.35, 24.16$ and 27.42) (for L = Im4COOH , Im2COOH and MeIm2COOH , respectively) were obtained. The species distribution diagrams showed that under physiological pH the following ternary and quaternary species; $[(\text{VO})\text{L}(\text{bL})]$, and $[\text{VO}(\text{L})(\text{bL})(\text{OH})]$, would dominate provided that the competition with serum proteins is not too strong. These species were also confirmed by HPLC, LC-MS and EPR. The overall stability constants for the VO^{2+} -L-HSA system ($\log \beta_{2,1,1,0} = 24.3, 23.7$ and 24.7), and for the VO^{2+} -L-hTf system ($\log \beta_{2,2,1,0} = 31.1, 30.8, 36.4$ for L = Im4COOH , Im2COOH and MeIm2COOH , respectively), suggesting stronger binding of transferrin. The formation constants for the formation of binary ($\text{VO}(\text{IV})$ and the proteins) were 9.1 and 13 for $\log \beta_{11}$, and 20.9 and 25.2 for β_{12} , for human serum albumin and human serum transferrin respectively. The species distribution diagrams for the proteins (HMM) with oxidovanadium(IV) under physiological pH was dominated by $\text{VO}(\text{HMM})_2$, $\text{VOL}(\text{HMM})$ for unsubstituted Im4COOH and Im2COOH , however, for the N-substituted MeIm2COOH , the species distribution diagrams under physiological pH, were dominated by VOL_2 , $\text{VO}(\text{HMM})_2$ and $\text{VO}_2\text{L}_2(\text{HMM})$. These species were further confirmed by HPLC, MALDI-TOF-MS and EPR.

The glucose stimulated insulin secretion (GSIS) action of the complexes was investigated using INS-1E cells at $1\mu\text{M}$ concentration which was established through cytotoxicity studies *via* the MTT assay. The vanadium salt (VOSO_4), cationic vanadium(IV) complex ($[\text{VO}(\text{MeImCH}_2\text{OH})_2]^{2+}$) were also included in the GSIS study in addition to the three neutral complexes $[\text{VO}(\text{Im4COO})_2]$, $[\text{VO}(\text{Im2COO})_2]$ and $[\text{VO}(\text{MeIm2COO})_2]$ for comparison. The neutral complexes, especially $[\text{VO}(\text{MeIm2COO})_2]$, showed promising results in the stimulation of insulin secretion than the cationic complex and the vanadium salt.

¹H NMR relaxometric study of Eu(II)-containing cryptates in aqueous solution

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Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is a noninvasive technique used to visualize the interior of objects with high spatial resolution. The contrast observed in most MR images can be enhanced with contrast agents that modulate the longitudinal (T_1) relaxation times, of protons on proximal water molecules. Contrast agents for MRI are often paramagnetic Gd^{III}-based complexes. Recently, Eu(II)-containing complexes have been also studied as redox-active alternatives to Gd(III)-based complexes [1]. Indeed, Eu(II) is isoelectronic with Gd(III) and shortens the T_1 relaxation times of nearby water protons to a similar extent as Gd(III), leading to enhanced contrast in T_1 -weighted images. The ability to shorten T_1 relaxation times is measured in terms of relaxivity (r_1).

In this project, three different Eu(II)-containing cryptates (Fig. 1) were synthesized and fully characterized by the relaxometric point of view in order to evaluate the molecular parameters (water-exchange rate, electronic relaxation time, and rotational correlation time) that influence the relaxivity. The results reported here demonstrate for the first time that it is possible to achieve a high relaxivity enhancement through non-covalent interactions between suitably functionalized Eu(II)-containing complexes and slowly tumbling substrates like β -CD, poly- β -CD, and human serum albumin. Similarly to the case of well-known Gd^{III}-based complexes, the relaxivities of rapidly rotating Eu^{II} chelates are essentially limited by the value of the rotational correlation time. A lengthening of τ_R causes a considerable increase in the longitudinal relaxation rate of water protons. However, unlike what is often observed in the case of Gd^{III}-based complexes, the slow exchange process of the bound water molecules does not hamper the increase in relaxivity at the imaging fields of the supramolecular adducts. This is because the Eu^{II} complexes investigated to date have solvent exchange rates values in the range necessary to achieve high relaxivity. This property, in the case of macromolecular systems, largely compensates for the negative effect on relaxivity of a greater distance between the water protons and the paramagnetic ion, thus enabling relaxivity values comparable to those of the analogous Gd^{III}-based systems.

These preliminary results clearly indicate that in the case of Eu^{II}-containing complexes, it is possible to design and develop highly sensitive macromolecular or nano-sized probes for advanced MRI applications and we expect that our results will be instrumental in the design of future Eu^{II}-based contrast agents [2].

Figure 1: Eu^{II}-containing cryptates used in this study. Complexes are drawn with two coordinated molecules of water, and counter anions are not shown for clarity.

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Towards high relaxivity in MRI: design and synthesis of new gadolinium complexes based on HP-DO3A

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Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is a powerful diagnostic technique widely applied in current medicine [1]. This non-invasive procedure is based on the relaxation rate of *in vivo* water protons and provides highly resolved images of the internal organs and structures of human body. Nowadays, more than 30% of the worldwide MRI scans are performed by administration to the patient of a contrast agent (CA) which is a gadolinium complex [2]. This choice is based on the favorable relaxometric properties of Gd(III) ion such as seven unpaired electrons and long electronic relaxation time [3]. The efficacy of a CA is expressed by its relaxivity (r_1), the enhancement of the longitudinal proton relaxation rate induced by the paramagnetic agent at 1 mM concentration. The relaxivity of CAs on the market is in the range of 3.6 - 6.3 mM s⁻¹ at 37°C in human plasma (HP) and with a magnetic field of 1.5 Tesla [4].

In the last years there has been a growing concern regarding the safety of gadolinium based contrast agents (GBCAs), mainly related to the *in vivo* release of gadolinium ion [5]. GBCAs derived from macrocyclic ligands (e.g. DOTA, HP-DO3A) show a greater thermodynamic and kinetic stability than those obtained from linear ligands (e.g. DTPA) and for this reason they should be considered safer [6].

Prohance (Bracco Imaging), the gadolinium complex of HP-DO3A, is a neutral GBCA very well tolerated but with a relaxivity of only 4.1 mM s⁻¹ (37°C, HP, 1.5T). The goal of this research was to seek a new GBCA based on HP-DO3A structure, which offers the desired stability, but with an increased relaxivity in order to significantly reduce the dose to the patient. The synthetic strategy pursued was through simple modifications of the HP-DO3A side chain.

In this communication the design, the synthesis and the results of a series of new gadolinium complexes showing high relaxivity will be presented.

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AAZTA: An Ideal Chelating Agent for the Development of ⁴⁴Sc PET Imaging Agents

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The enduring development of targeted imaging agents for Positron Emission Tomography (PET), relying on biomolecules and nanoparticles, stimulates research on radionuclides with half-life matching their biological properties. Recently ⁴⁴Sc has raised a significant interest as a potential radionuclide for PET imaging.^[1] ⁴⁴Sc combines a relatively long half-life (3.97 hours, E_{mean} (β⁺) = 632 keV) with a high positron branching of 94.27%,^[1,2] opening the way to targeted radiotracers with relatively slow pharmacokinetic profiles. ⁴⁴Sc can be conveniently produced by the ⁴⁴Ti/⁴⁴Sc generator^[1,3] overcoming the dependence on expensive accelerators. The relatively long half-life of ⁴⁴Sc isotope requires very robust ⁴⁴Sc^{III}-complexes characterized by high thermodynamic and kinetic stability for *in vivo* application. **DOTA** (Scheme 1) and its derivatives still represent the workhorse for the preparation of stable chelates, but their slow formation kinetics require long reaction times at 70-95°C, hardly compatible with the labelling of antibodies and other biomolecules.^[4] **AAZTA** is a readily available mesocyclic chelating agent (Scheme 1), with a remarkable affinity to *d* and *f* transition-metal ions.^[5]

Scheme 1. The chelating agents **AAZTA**, **CNAAZTA** and **DOTA**.

Herein we report a comprehensive account of the thermodynamics, transmetallation kinetics and structural properties of the Sc(AAZTA)⁻ complex. Additionally, ⁴⁴Sc-labeling of AAZTA and DOTA were carefully executed to find the best conditions for chelate formation and to compare their labelling efficiency. Finally, PET images of healthy and tumour animal models were obtained using ⁴⁴Sc-labeled CNAAZTA-conjugates (⁴⁴Sc(CNAAZTA-c(RGDfK)), c(RGDfK): Cyclo(-Arg-Gly-Asp-D-Phe-Lys)).

The thermodynamic stability constant ($\log K_{\text{Sc(AAZTA)}^-} = 27.69(4)$) is lower than that of Sc(DOTA)⁻ ($\log K_{\text{Sc(DOTA)}^-} = 30.79$).^[6] However, the conditional stability constants shows that $p\text{Sc}=24.72$ of Sc(AAZTA)⁻ is higher than $p\text{Sc}=23.92$ of Sc(DOTA)⁻ with almost one unit ($p\text{Sc}=-\log[\text{Sc}^{3+}]_{\text{free}}$, $[\text{Sc}^{3+}]_{\text{tot}}=1\times 10^{-8}$ M, $[\text{L}]_{\text{tot}}=1\times 10^{-7}$ M, $\text{pH}=7.4$). The transmetallation reactions occur between Sc(AAZTA)⁻ and Cu²⁺ ions through the spontaneous (k_0) and the proton assisted (k_1) dissociation of Sc(AAZTA)⁻, followed by the fast reaction between the released AAZTA ligand and the free Cu²⁺ ions. The k_1 rate constant characterizing the proton-assisted dissociation of Sc(AAZTA)⁻ ($k_1=0.1\pm 0.01$ M⁻¹s⁻¹) is $2\cdot 10^4$ times faster than that of Sc(DOTA)⁻ ($k_1=1.8\cdot 10^{-6}$ M⁻¹s⁻¹).^[6] X-ray diffraction studies of the single crystals with the formula $\{(\text{NH}_4,\text{K})[\text{Sc}(\text{AAZTA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]\}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ indicate that the coordination polyhedron around the Sc^{III} ion can be described by an irregular dodecahedron defined by a 1:4:3 stack of the water molecule and of two nearly parallel pseudo-planes formed by the oxygen and nitrogen atoms of the AAZTA ligand. Near complete (>95%) incorporation of ⁴⁴Sc was achieved almost instantaneously at $[\text{AAZTA}] \geq 1$ μM and $T \geq 55^\circ\text{C}$ over the broad pH range 2 – 8. On the other hand, the labelling efficiency of DOTA with ⁴⁴Sc was only $\geq 80\%$ at 95°C in narrow pH range ($\text{pH}=2 - 4$) and in the presence of a large DOTA excess ($[\text{DOTA}] \geq 3$ μM). To get more insight into the *in vivo* properties, the biodistribution of ⁴⁴Sc³⁺, ⁴⁴Sc(AAZTA)⁻ and ⁴⁴Sc(CNAAZTA-c(RGDfK)) has been investigated in healthy control and 4T1 tumour-bearing BALB/c mice. The accumulation of ⁴⁴Sc(CNAAZTA-c(RGDfK)) in 4T1 tumour is 25-fold higher than in muscle (as background) as expected in the case of the overexpression of $\alpha_v\beta_3$ integrin receptors that are the specific targets for ⁴⁴Sc(CNAAZTA-c(RGDfK)).

In conclusion, this work demonstrated the suitability of the chelating agent AAZTA for the preparation of Sc-based radiopharmaceuticals.

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Pyclen-based ligands with pendant picolinate arms as attractive rare earth chelators for diagnostic and therapy

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Rare earth(III) complexes are widely used as diagnostic and therapeutic probes. The most well-known are probably the paramagnetic Gd(III) chelates employed as MRI relaxation agents whereas the complexes of luminescent lanthanides, such as Eu(III) or Tb(III), are explored as optical probes. On the therapeutic side, complexes formed with the β^- -emitter ^{90}Y ($t_{1/2} = 64.2$ h, $E_{\beta^-} = 2.28$ MeV) are very attractive for radio-therapy. However, for evident toxicity issues and to preserve their properties, all these chelates must be thermodynamically and kinetically very stable in order to avoid any release of the metal in biological media. In addition, each application has its own specification. For example, a fast chelation is preferred for radionuclides, a coordinated water molecule is needed for MRI, while a complete coordination sphere is required for optical probes. Then, the conception of chelators requires to address significant synthetic challenges to offer to the metal complex the desired properties/behavior.

Aiming to find a family of theranostic ligands able to form Ln(III) and Y(III) complexes that fulfill both biological and the specific application requirements, we synthesized and studied different regio-isomers of pyclen-based ligands bearing one or two pyridine-2-carboxylic acid pendant arms (Figure 1) [1].

Figure 1: *N*-functionalized pyclen regio-isomers and potential applications of their chelates.

The physico-chemical properties of the Y(III) and Ln(III) complexes were deeply investigated, as well as the ⁹⁰Y(III) radiolabeling [2,3], the relaxivity measurements of the Gd(III) complexes and the photo-physical properties of the Eu(III) and Tb(III) complexes. These studies allow to assess the potential use of each chelate rather for therapy or for diagnosis and highlight the importance of the regiospecific *N*-functionalization, which affects both kinetic and thermodynamic stabilities and physical properties [4].

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Cobalt(III) ternary complexes of hydroxamate-based compounds

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Hydroxamic acid(s), containing the characteristic function $-\text{CONR}_N\text{OH}$ ($R_N = \text{H}$ in primary derivatives, alkyl or aryl in secondary ones), are very effective metal binding agents forming, most commonly, 5-membered hydroxamate type (O,O)-chelate via the deprotonated form of the function [1]. The close correlation between their metal-binding ability and the wide array of different applications, *e.g.* in nature and medicine is well-known [2,3]. For example, trihydroxamate-based siderophores play crucial role in iron-uptake of microbes, or due to their metalloenzyme-inhibitory effect, several monohydroxamate-based drug candidates, such as batimastat and its orally bioavailable analogue, marimastat [4], have been developed. Vorinostat (suberoylanilide hydroxamic acid) was the first histone deacetylase inhibitor approved by the U.S. FDA for the treatment of cutaneous T cell lymphoma [5].

However, in the cancer therapy, selective targeting of the used anticancer agent is extremely crucial. It is a common situation that the realized selectivity and efficiency problems can be associated with some interaction of the drugs during their transportation to the target. To solve the problem, chaperoning of the drug molecule to the site of action in an inactive form and activation of it at the site is one of the known approaches [6,7]. If the drug molecules are potential chelating ligands, like hydroxamic acids, their inactivation may be achieved via their chelation to the metal centre of kinetically inert pro-drug complexes. The very significant difference in lability between the complexes of cobalt(III) and cobalt(II) makes this metal preferred to construct hypoxia selective pro-drug complexes [6]. By using simply monohydroxamic acids, preparation of stable cobalt(III) complexes is not possible, even with trihydroxamate-based siderophores it can only be done under basic conditions [8]. Usually some tripodal 4N-donor ligand is selected to synthesize chaperons with stabilized 3+ oxidation state of the central cobalt, while the coordination sphere is completed via the inhibitor chelator, like a monohydroxamate. Reduction of the central cobalt(III) ion to the labile cobalt(II) by bioreductants under hypoxic condition (hypoxia is one of the intrinsic features of a tumor-environment) and subsequent dissociation of the drug molecule will lead to the activation at the site. However, this can only be expected, if the redox potential of the complex falls into the potential range of biological reductants.

To collect information about the possibility of tuning the redox potential of above-mentioned type ternary complexes, numerous new representatives have been prepared and characterized in our recent work [9] by making some changes either in the structure of 4N-donor ligand or in the substituent of the monohydroxamate-based inhibitor molecule. The formula of the investigated 4N-donor ligands are shown below:

Various benzohydroxamic acid derivatives were used to complete the coordination sphere of the cobalt(III)-4N complexes and cyclic voltammetry was used to investigate their redox behavior. Although, irreversibility of the reduction of the complexes was found in all cases, but, relating the 4N-donor ligands, significant effect of both the character of the N (aliphatic or aromatic) and the sizes of the chelating rings on the redox potential was detected. For the monohydroxamic acids, however, the only significant difference was found between the values for the complexes containing either the mono-deprotonated (hydroxamate) or the doubly-deprotonated (hydroximate) forms of the bioactive molecules. The details of the results are planned to be discussed at the ISMEC 2018.

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Ciprofloxacin-metal complexes –stability and toxicity tests in the presence of humic substances

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The co-contamination of ciprofloxacin (CIP) with metal ions results in alteration of CIP mobility [1], antimicrobial activity [2] and distribution/development of the antibiotic-resistance genes [3]. Hence, we decided to investigate the stability of CIP-Me complexes (Me = Co(II), Cu(II), Mg, Al(III), Fe(III)) via fluorescence spectroscopy for seven days at two temperatures (4°C and 18°C) in ultrapure water, at pH 6.5±0.1 to simulate the pH of wastewater. The influence of humic substances (HS) on formed complexes was also tested due to HS prevalence in the environment. The complexation sites of CIP-Me+HS systems were established by Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy. However, another question arose: how do the HS affect the antimicrobial activity of CIP-Me complexes? Thus, we determined the minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) of CIP-Me complexes and CIP-Me complexes in the presence of HS against two bacterial strains – Gram-positive, *Bacillus subtilis* and Gram-negative, *Enterobacter aerogenes*.

The most stable complexes were CIP-Al, CIP-Cu, and CIP-Co. At lower temperature (4°C), their stability constants decreased: 1-fold for CIP-Al, 14-fold for CIP-Co and 2-fold for CIP-Cu. The presence of humic substances decreased the stability of complexes. The chemical reactions of Fe³⁺ in water at circumneutral pH resulted in stability alteration. The formation of CIP-Mg complexes at lower temperatures and in the presence of HS was limited.

In ultrapure water, CIP-Me complexes exhibit higher toxicity towards Gram-negative *E. aeruginosa*. MIC values ranged between 0.125-0.5 µg/ml. However, the presence of HS reduced the antimicrobial activity of CIP-Me complexes by at least 2-fold as presented in figure 1. Gram-positive representative, *B. subtilis* was not affected by the presence of metal ions and/or HS. The toxicity toward *B. subtilis* for the complexes was equal to toxicity of CIP alone (MIC=0.25 µg/ml). This suggested the different susceptibility to CIP and its complexes.

Figure 1. The susceptibility of Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria towards ciprofloxacin and its complexes

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pH-Dependent Modulation of Reactivity in Ruthenium(II) Organometallics

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The anticancer activity of ruthenium(II)-based organometallic compounds continues to be intensively investigated [1-5], building on early work that revealed promising antiangiogenic, antimetastatic and antitumoural activity with the $[\text{Ru}(\eta^6\text{-arene})\text{Cl}_2(\text{PTA})]$ (RAPTA) [6, 7] and $[\text{Ru}(\eta^6\text{-arene})(\text{en})\text{Cl}]^+$ [8] series of compounds. The anticancer activity of many of these prospective metallodrugs is exerted via metalation of protein and/or DNA targets [9, 10], where a coordinated H_2O ligand is displaced by a donor atom within the biomacromolecule. A major limitation of this mode of action is that metalation is not selective and can occur in healthy and cancerous tissue alike – ultimately resulting in undesired side-effects.

The known differences [11] between the extracellular pH of healthy tissue (7.2-7.4) and cancerous tissue (6.5-6.9) may be exploited in the development of more selective metallodrugs via the incorporation of ligands which regulate metal-centered reactivity in a pH-dependent manner. For example, the $\text{p}K_a$ values of the aqua ligand in $[\text{Ru}(\eta^6\text{-fluoroarene})\text{Cl}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{PTA})]^+$ complexes were shown to be dependent on the fluoroarene ligand (5.5, 8.3 and 8.9 for $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CF}_3$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{F}$ and 1,4- $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3\text{F}$ respectively), although a degree of arene lability was reported with these complexes [12]. The $\eta^6:\kappa^1\text{-arene}/N$ chelate formed within $[\text{Ru}\{\eta^6:\kappa^1\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)\text{NH}_2\}(\text{XY})]^{n+}$ complexes was shown to ring open under acidic conditions; the ring-opened form of the complex was able to bind to guanosine 5'-monophosphate (5'-GMP) whilst the chelate form rendered the complex inactive toward 5'-GMP [13]. However, the $\text{p}K_a$ value of the ligand (ca. 2.5) results in these complexes remaining inactive under physiologically relevant conditions.

In this work we present a series of ruthenium(II) arene complexes bearing a tethered sulfonamide ligand [14].

The pH-dependent intramolecular ligation of the sulfonamide group is demonstrated and we show the basicity of the sulfonamide nitrogen may be modulated by variation of the sulfonamide R substituent. With an appropriate R substituent the formation of the intramolecular chelate is shown to regulate binding of the metal to 5'-GMP across the physiologically relevant pH region. Our results indicate intramolecular sulfonamide chelation may enable pH-dependent control of metal-centered reactivity in known cytotoxic metallodrugs and may also be employed in the development of new metal-based anticancer compounds.

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Phosphine-peptide(SarGlyOH) conjugate attached to Cu^I complex contra breast cancer – physicochemical and biological characteristics

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Approximately 7 million people die from tumor-related cases per year, and it is estimated that there will be more than 16 million new cancer patients every year by 2020. Chemotherapy is still one of the major approaches to fight against cancer diseases by delivering cytotoxic agents to unhealthy cells. However, the main disadvantage of conventional chemotherapy lies in its inability to deliver the correct amount of drug to the target cells without harming healthy ones. This shows the importance of development of the systems that will selectively destroy cancer cells.

We synthesized (**Figure 1**) new phosphine-peptide conjugate (Ph₂PCH₂-Sar-Gly-OH, **PSG**) derived from H-Sar-Gly-OH. This short template dipeptide can be easily exchanged to other peptide carriers in future. We also obtained the first copper(I) complex ([CuI(dmp)(P(Ph)₂CH₂-Sar-Gly-OH)] (**1-PSG**) with a peptide motif, where dmp: 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline).

Figure 1 Schematic view of the compounds and synthetic routes.

The synthesized compounds were characterized by NMR (1D, 2D), UV-Vis spectroscopy and DFT methods. **PSG** phosphine and **1-PSG** complex are stable in biological medium (in the presence of atmospheric O₂ for several days).

Figure 2 Synthesis, characteristics and insight into cytotoxic action.

The cytotoxic activity of all compounds and cisplatin was tested against three cancer cell lines: mouse colon carcinoma (CT26; $1\text{-PSGIC}_{50}=3.12\pm 0.1$), human lung adenocarcinoma (A549; $1\text{-PSGIC}_{50}=2.01\pm 0.2$) and human breast adenocarcinoma (MCF7; $1\text{-PSGIC}_{50}=0.98\pm 0.2$) as well as against one primary line of human pulmonary fibroblasts (MRC-5; $1\text{-PSGIC}_{50}=78.56\pm 1.1$) (**Figure 2**). Calculated therapeutic index for **1-PSG** (MCF7) is very high and equals 80. Cytotoxicity of **1-PSG** greatly depends on copper uptake. The accumulation of this complex inside cancer cells MCF7 increased with time and was much higher (96%) than inside normal MRC5 cells (20%). The attachment of simple H-Sar-Gly-OH peptide to cytotoxic copper(I) complex *via* phosphine motif helped make **1-PSG** complex highly selective towards breast cancer cells. Studies of the **1-PSG** activity against MCF7 revealed that this inorganic compound causes apoptotic cell death with simultaneous decrease of mitochondrial membrane potential level and increase of caspase-9 and -3 activities. Additionally, **1-PSG** generated high concentration of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the MCF7 which was the reason for oxidative damages of the sugar–phosphate backbone of plasmid DNA (**Figure 2**).

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An in-depth analysis of the metal binding domain in a putative Zn(II) transporter of *Candida albicans*

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It is well established that, in the last decades, invasive mycoses have developed alarming drug resistance attitudes, making fungal pathogens extremely dangerous for the patients' subsistence. *Candida albicans* is one of the most diffused opportunistic pathogenic yeasts, known to be a commensal organism of the human body, but also an extremely dangerous threat in immunocompromised individuals, which can develop severe, life-threatening candidemia [1].

Several lines of evidence confirm that the ability of pathogenic microorganisms, such as *C. albicans*, to assimilate metal nutrients from the host environment is a fundamental aspect of infection. As a consequence, studies concerning the characterization of the host/pathogen interface and the mechanism of metal uptake and transport in fungal species can provide crucial information and a base to identify new pharmacological targets for the treatment and diagnosis of mycoses [2-4].

Zinc and copper are crucial for the virulence and survival of fungal pathogens in humans, since they are indispensable in the expression of several metalloproteins and enzymes. The acquisition processes of these metals by pathogens is extremely challenging: the concentration of free Zn(II) is normally as low as subnanomolar [5], and Cu(II), that is an endogenous metal, can widely compete with Zn(II) for the same binding sites. As a consequence, both the uptake and safe storage of these metals must be strictly controlled [6].

We recently focused our attention on Zn(II) and Cu(II) binding behaviour towards C4YJH2 (UniProt Knowledgebase [7]), a protein sequence of 199 amino acid residues, found in the genome of *C. albicans* (Fig. 1). C4YJH2 is suggested to be involved in metal transport processes, since it shares high percentage of identity with several putative Zn(II) transporters and proteins involved in metal homeostasis. This sequence is of remarkable interest, since it has a significant high number of histidine and serine residues, especially in its C-terminal domain, which was confirmed to have a role as metal binding site [8].

The present work represents an in-depth analysis of the metal binding domain of C4YJH2: the protected peptide Ac-GSDHSGDSK-NH₂, encompassing residues 148-156 of the protein, is considered, along with its following analogues: Ac-GSDHSGASK-NH₂, Ac-GADHAGDAK-NH₂, Ac-GSDH-NH₂, Ac-HSGD-NH₂.

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      10          20          30          40          50
MNSKEIRIVA LLILDTVFFL LEAIIGYTVH SLALIADSFH MLNDIISLII
      60          70          80          90         100
ALWAVRVKNT KPADGKYTYG WQRAEILGAL INAVFLLALC FTIIMDSIQR
      110         120         130         140         150
FFEPQEISNP KLILIVGIAG LVSNGVGLVL FHEHGHSHSH GSGGGGGGSD
      160         170         180         190
HSGDSKSHSH SHSHSHGEAT TFSQGDEEDI LAPKMNIIH YYIILLIRL
```

Figure 1. C4YJH2 protein sequence, corresponding to the gene CAWG_03987 found in the strain WO-1 of *Candida albicans*. The evolutionarily conserved sequence among zinc-binding proteins from fungal species is highlighted in red.

The preliminary results presented here concern the stoichiometry and thermodynamics of complex-formation of the above reported ligands with Zn(II) and Cu(II), investigated by means of potentiometric titrations; the hypothesized geometry of the formed species is also discussed, on the basis of UV-Vis spectrophotometric data at variable pH. The comparison between the behaviour of the different analogues helps to shed light on the role of some residues of the sequence (such as Ser and Asp), not directly involved in complexation but influencing the complex geometry and contributing to its stability. The study on the two short peptides, Ac-GSDH-NH₂ and Ac-HSGD-NH₂, gives information about the attitude of Cu(II) to form complexes which involve amide nitrogens in the amine-terminus or carboxylic-terminus direction.

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Synthesis, characterization and DNA interaction of highly charged ruthenium complexes as photosensitizer agents in photodynamic therapy

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Photodynamic therapy (PDT) is attracting increasing interest for its successful application in the treatment of a wide variety of skin diseases, bacterial infections and cancers.[1] It consists of optimally designed molecules (photosensitizers) which can be activated by low energy light, to produce cytotoxic species such as singlet oxygen $^1\text{O}_2$ or reactive oxygen species (ROS), causing severe damages to selected biological targets.

Among the main advantages concerning the use of PDT in medicine, the possibility to achieve a temporal and spatial control of the drug-activation, allows to ensure a better discrimination between malignant and surrounding healthy tissues. This permits to strongly reduce the common dose-limiting side effects incurred with standard chemotherapies.

In this context, many ruthenium (II) polypyridyl complexes have been exploited in PDT thanks to their great ability to generate singlet oxygen upon exposure to visible light. On the other hand, tissue oxygenation might represent a critical requirement for the application of PDT in case of hypoxic tumors. Therefore, much interest has been focused on the development of a new class of ruthenium (II) polypyridyl systems, whose employment in PDT requests a lower reliance on molecular oxygen. These compounds are in fact, characterized by a ‘distortion feature’ in their octahedral coordination geometry.

Figure: Schematic representation of the Ru(II) polypyridyl complexes herein presented.

The enhanced strain lowers the triplet metal-centered state (^3MC), allowing for thermal population from the triplet metal to ligand charge transfer state ($^3\text{MLCT}$), bringing to the loss of one or more ligands upon light activation. The resulting active species are then able to form covalent adducts with DNA, in a ‘cis-platin like’ fashion.[2]

In the present work, we report a series of novel ruthenium (II) polypyridyl complexes featuring different ancillary ligands, and containing a peculiar polyaminomacrocyclic unit which can easily undergo protonation in physiological media.[3,4] Ligands were synthesized and characterized by means of NMR spectroscopy, CHN analysis, Mass and Uv-visible spectrometry. Their interaction with calf-thymus DNA was investigated by means of spectroscopic and fluorescence experiments, while, based on absorption titration studies, the corresponding binding constants were determined. Finally, gel electrophoresis experiments on plasmid DNA were carried out in order to evaluate their capacity to damage the biopolymer by photoactivation. Thanks to their tunable absorption properties and to the strong ability to produce both oxygen singlet and ligand photo-ejection processes upon light activation, the above mentioned compounds appear to be optimal candidates for a further development as light-activated drugs in PDT.

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Influence of ligand structure, central atom and water content on the properties of the lanthanide complex

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Polydentate ligands are interesting as promising extractants for the separation of f-element ions [1]. In addition, their complexes have specific photophysical properties and can be used as luminescent materials [2]. The purpose of our work was to determine the influence of substituents in the ligand on the stability constants of complexes of substituted bipyridine-dicarboxamides (Figure 1) with lanthanides series.

Figure 1: Structure N⁶,N^{6'}-diethyl-N⁶,N^{6'}-R-[2,2'-bipyridine]-6,6'-dicarboxamide, where R: Ph – H [1], (2,5-diMe)Ph – 2,5-diMe, (2,4-diMe)Ph – 2,4-diMe, (3,5-diMe)Ph – 3,5-diMe, (3,4-diMe)Ph – 3,4-diMe, (2-F)Ph – 2-F, (3-F)Ph – 3-F, (4-F)Ph – 4-F.

Since previous study of donor and acceptor effects is less focused on the position of the deputy himself [3], our task was therefore to study the influence of the position of the substituent on the stability of complex. For this purpose, complexes of lanthanides (except for Pm) with a series of ligands were studied and their stability constants were determined by spectrophotometric titration. The evolving factors analysis point to the presence of two absorbing species corresponding to free ligand and the complex. The stoichiometries of the complexes were determined by Job's method and they are in coincidence with X-ray and analysis data for the prepared individual complexes.

The stability constants of the lanthanide complexes were calculated by nonlinear least-squares regression analysis using the HypSpec program [4], based on equation (1) and (2) for the complexes:

To verify the results, the titration were repeated twice and found that the results are in the confidence interval.

$$\beta_1 = \frac{[Ln_x^{+3}L_y^0]}{[Ln_x^{+3}] \cdot [L_y^0]}, \quad \text{where } x = 1 \text{ and } y = 1 \quad (2)$$

As follows from Figure 2a, the introducing of two donor methyl groups into the phenyl ring of diamide H increases the stability of complexes ($\lg \beta_1$), but this effect is different in its value for various metal ions. This increase is due to electron-donating nature of the methyl-groups. The degree of enhancing of stability of the complexes depends on the position of substituents in amidic aromatic

ring and this effect differs for light and heavy lanthanides. For ions from La³⁺ to Gd³⁺ the lowest stability show 2,5-*diMe* ligand and the highest – 2,4- and 3,4- ones. This can be connected with more contribution of the electronic factors (2- and 4- positions of the aromatic ring are more sensitive to +*I* groups) than the steric factors. Heavy lanthanides show less effect of steric hindrance with 2-substituted diamides probably owing to lanthanide contraction: the stability of complexes with 2,5-*diMe* are higher than with 3,4-*diMe*. As shown on Figure 2b, after the introducing acceptor group into the phenyl moiety of diamide *H* a similar increase is observed as for methyl-groups. The increase in stability occurs almost linearly for the 2-*F* with light lanthanides, contrary the 3-*F* show constant stability. So, for fluoride-group there was a similar contribution of electronic factors as in the case of methyl-groups.

Figure 2: Influence of the ligand structure on the values of the $lg\beta_1$ from 4f-element, where: a) filled circles with a line – *diMe*-substituted ligands with water content in CH₃CN 30 ppm, unfilled circles – *diMe*-substituted ligands with water content in CH₃CN 400 ppm, unfilled circles with dotted line – *H* ligand; b) filled triangles with a line – *F*-substituted ligands with water content in CH₃CN 30 ppm, unfilled triangles – *F*-substituted ligands with water content in CH₃CN 400 ppm.

The influence of water content on the stability of complexes is shown on Figure 2 by open circles and dotted lines. Increase of water content in the solvent from 30 to 400 ppm reduces the $lg\beta_1$ from 5.8–7.6 to 4.5–5.1 and diminish the difference in stability of complexes within the lanthanide series for ligands 2,4-*diMe*, 2,5-*diMe* and 2-*F*. The 3-*F* and 4-*F* follows same trend as illustrated by several examples. The most interesting feature consists in the significant diminishing of the variation of stability constants within the metal ion series upon the increase the water content. This can be explained by metal hydration energy contribution.

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⁶⁸Ga-Curcumin-based chelators: development of potential new PET radiotracers for colon carcinoma.

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Curcumin, the yellow pigment extracted from the dried rizomes of *Curcuma longa* L., is by far known for its therapeutic properties; moreover, its efficacy against several diseases has been tested both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Among these, colorectal cancer represents one of the best target of curcumin, as reported for *in vitro* assays on cell cultures [1,2] PET (Positron Emission Tomography) is a radioisotopes-based diagnostic technique to investigate diseases where a biological molecule, selective for a specific pathological target and chemically linked to a positron emitting metal isotope, is injected in patients for imaging purpose. In particular, gallium-68 exhibits advantageous features, being a generator produced positron emitter radionuclide with characteristics suitable for diagnostic nuclear medicine and direct labelling of biomolecules (89% β^+ , E = 1.92 MeV; $T_{1/2}$ = 67.7 min). Hence, radiolabeled curcuminoids could be potential biomarkers for colorectal cancer by means of nuclear medicine imaging techniques.

In this study, a new class of curcuminoid derivatives linked to bifunctional chelators were synthesized and radiolabeled. The first group of compounds were prepared starting from the curcumin backbone and connecting different chelators (DOTA, NODAGA, AAZTA, DATA) to the hydroxyl group of the phenyl ring. The second group was synthesized by keeping AAZTA as fixed chelator and changing the targeting molecule backbone. Curcuminoid-chelators were labelled with gallium-68 by reacting precursors with cation exchange pre-purified generator eluate fractions containing ca. 80 MBq of $^{68}\text{Ga}^{3+}$ in 0.05 M HCl. Amount of precursor was optimized and kinetics of the reactions were assessed at different times. The pH was fixed to 4 (0.2 M Ammonium Acetate) and the temperature ranged from RT to 95°C depending on the chelator. Stability and lipophilicity of the ^{68}Ga -labelled compounds were also assessed. An incorporation of gallium-68 higher than 95% was generally achieved in less than 5 min of reaction. Stability of the compound ranged from 60-85% (HS and PBS, 2h) and lipophilicity ranged from 1.0-2.5.

For ^{68}Ga -DOTA-C21 (**Figure 1**), the uptake was assessed *in vitro* in HT29 colorectal cancer cell line and *in vivo* in immune-compromised mice where HT29 cells were injected to growth the tumor. ^{68}Ga -DOTA-C21 exhibits interesting biodistribution and pharmacokinetics. The results will give insight into the possibility to employ these compounds as PET radiotracers for clinical applications.

Figure 1.

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Cu(II) and Pt(II) Polynuclear Clusters of Novel Oxime-Amide Ligands

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In the course of our systematic studies of 2-substituted oxime-amide chelates, we have synthesised and characterised a series of 2-methyl oxime-amide-amine ligands (**L1-L4**), as well as ligands **L0** and **L8**, Scheme 1. We have also explored the protonation behaviour of new ligands and determined their protonation constants in aqueous medium by the glass-electrode potentiometric titrations.

Scheme 1. Ligands synthesized.

In view of a well-known propensity of the oximato group to form bridged dinuclear structures, Scheme 2, we have set out to prepare polynuclear coordination clusters using our new tridentate and tetradentate ligands.

Scheme 2. Some of the known oximato-bridged Cu(II)-dinuclear complexes.

We have succeeded in isolating six polynuclear complexes, CC1-CC6, that fall into four structural types, and determined their molecular and crystal structures by X-ray diffraction. All coordination clusters are new, and if the structural types of polynuclear core have been reported before, our compounds employ different ligands and are distinguished by numerous structural features. In particular, the coordination cluster CC6 is entirely without precedent. Representative structures for each type are shown below.

Type 1: $\{[Cu^{2+}(mhieoaH_{-1.5})_2] \cdot Na^+ \cdot 2(H_2O)\}$ (**CC1**), the “staircase” Cu(II)-cluster, Figure 1, left.

Type 2: $\{[Cu^{2+}(mhieapnH_2)]_4 \cdot 4 \cdot H_2O\}$ (**CC2**), the pseudo-cubane tetranuclear Cu(II)-cluster, Figure 1.

$\{[Cu^{2+}(mhieapohnH_2)]_4 \cdot (CH_3OH)\}$ (**CC3**), the pseudo-cubane Cu(II)-cluster, not shown.

Fig 1. **Left:** A fragment of the “staircase” structure CC1 with Cu(II) centres labelled. **Centre:** A view of the pseudo-cubane cluster CC2. **Right:** The tetra-copper core in CC2.

Type 3: $[\{Cu^{2+}_3(\mu_3-OH)\}_2\{\mu-Cl\}(mhiea_2es_2H_2)_3(Cl)(H_2O)] \cdot 2Cl^-$ (**CC4**), the hexanuclear Cu(II)-cage, Figure 2.

$[\{Cu^{2+}_3(\mu_3-OH)\}_2\{\mu-Br\}(mhiea_2es_2H_2)_3(Br^-)_3]$ (**CC5**), the hexanuclear Cu(II)-cage, not shown.

Fig 2. **Left:** A view of the hexa-copper cage in CC4 from above. **Right:** The same cage viewed from the side.

Type 4: $[4(\mu-S)-(Pt^{2+}mhieaesH_2)_2(Pt^{2+}mhieaesO_2H_2)_2]$ (**CC6**), the tetranuclear Pt(II)-cluster, Figure 3.

Fig 3. **Left:** A view of the tetra-platinum cluster CC6 with Pt and S centres labelled. **Centre:** A view of the macrocyclic eight-membered Pt_4S_4 core in CC6 from two directions. **Right:** A view of the coordination environment around platinum atoms in CC6 with the numbering scheme.

Preparation, properties, and structural features of new metal clusters will be discussed in this presentation.

All Cu(II)-species have shown cooperative molecular magnetism, and may possess catalytic activity reminiscent to that of enzymes. The CC6 complex is expected to show nuclease activity on DNA, and presents interest as potential chemotherapy agent.

Enhancement of SOD activity in boehmite supported nanoreceptors

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The imbalance between the generation and clearance of reactive oxygen species (ROS) causes oxidative stress, which is related to a variety of health issues that include neurodegenerative disorders such as Parkinson's and Alzheimer's disease (AD).[1] In order to remove ROS, living organisms have developed a battery of protective enzymes, such as superoxide dismutases (SODs), which are not useful for a therapeutic treatment due to the drawbacks that they present -such as the absence of oral activity-. In this respect, it has been reported that several copper complexes of aza-macrocyclic ligands have SOD activities in vitro which rank among the highest ones so far reported for synthetic systems.[2,3] A step forward to improve the activity, the likely-cell uptake and bio-distribution of these low molecular weight mimetics might be their incorporation in non-toxic nanoparticles (NPs). The grafting of the molecules to the surface of the nanoparticles may yield pre-concentration and amplification of the signal.

As a proof of concept, here we report the synthesis of a new Cu²⁺ binucleating aza-macrocyclic ligand (**L1**) functionalized with a hydroxo group rightly disposed to permit its covalent anchorage to boehmite (g-AlO(OH)) nanoparticles (**L1-BNP**) without loss of SOD activity.[4]

Figure 1. Ligands drawing

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Interaction of gold N-heterocyclic carbenes with nucleic acids

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Metal complexes with N-heterocyclic carbenic ligands (NHCs) have found applications not only in catalysis but also as anticancer agents [1]. In particular, gold-NHCs turned out to be particularly promising. First of all, they are stable complexes whose synthesis is relatively simple. Moreover, their biological and targeting properties can be tuned by modifying substituents on the carbenic ligand. Preclinical studies showed antiproliferative properties both *in vitro* and *in vivo* and encouraging results on selectivity [2,3]. These compounds target mitochondria and proteins, among which of paramount importance is the selenoenzyme Thioredoxin reductase. However, more recent studies also consider their interaction with dsDNA or G-quadruplexes [4,5]. Indeed, some of the latest approaches on anticancer metallodrug design include the synthesis of multitargeting platforms [6], cancer being such a complex series of genetic diseases that a single target therapy may not be effective enough.

Within this frame, we synthesized and chemically characterized a gold monocarbene with a planar aromatic moiety (Scheme 1) able to interact with dsDNA.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 1-(9-anthracenylmethyl)3-(1-trimethylsilyl-3-propynyl)-benzimidazol-2-ylidene gold chloride

Binding with natural DNA has been characterized by means of different spectroscopic methods such as spectrofluorimetric titrations and thermal denaturation spectrophotometric studies. Moreover, inhibition of purified Thioredoxin reductase has been measured. Preliminary *in vitro* cytotoxicity experiments show moderate antiproliferative activity.

In addition, single crystals of bis-(1-butyl-3-methyl)imidazol-2-ylidene-gold hexafluorophosphate ([BMIm₂Au][PF₆]) with the human telomere Tel-23 have been obtained. The adduct has been also characterized in solution by means of ESI-MS, circular dichroism and melting experiments.

As for dsDNA binding, the results show that the synthesized gold-NHC does indeed bind the nucleic acid in a complex manner that includes both intercalation and interaction with the groove. Great stabilization of the helix is observed at compound/DNA molar ratio of 1. As for TrxR inhibition, IC₅₀ values in the micromolar range comparable with the *in vitro* cytotoxicity suggest that the enzyme may play an important role for the biological action.

As for the telomere, solution studies on the [BMIm₂Au][PF₆]/Tel 23 adduct confirm the features already pointed out by the crystal structure. The gold compound binds the G-quadruplex externally with a 1:1 stoichiometry. CD spectra and melting studies show that the interaction exists but is rather weak.

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Design and investigation of novel zinc finger–NColE7-based artificial nucleases

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Application of artificial nucleases (ANs) for genome editing is still hindered by their cytotoxicity, related to off-target cleavages. Such side-effects could be obviated, similarly to the natural systems, by the regulation of the nuclease domain. Seeking for a suitable catalytic unit we found that the nuclease domain of colicin E7 requires the concerted action of its C- and N-termini to cleave the DNA. This property can be exploited for allosteric control of the enzymatic process.

First we carried out a computational design of novel integrated zinc finger nucleases, constructed by linking the inactivated catalytic centre and the allosteric activator sequence of the colicin E7 nuclease domain to the two opposite termini of a zinc finger array.[1]

Fig. 1 The concept of the NColE7-based artificial metallonuclease design.

The synthesis and purification of the new proteins was performed, followed by characterization of DNA-binding specificity and metal-ion binding ability by electrophoretic mobility shift assays, synchrotron radiation circular dichroism spectroscopy and nano-electrospray ionization mass spectrometry. In situ intramolecular activation of the nuclease domain resulted in specific DNA cleavage with moderate activity.[2]

Furthermore, besides the Nx-ZF-Cy type of the new ANs, we have established a number of Cx-ZF-Ny-type enzymes, as well. The latest results proved the cooperative effect of the two termini of the ANs in DNA cleavage.

Our study represents a new approach to AN design through integrated nucleases consisting of three (regulator – DNA-binding – nuclease) units rather than simple chimera. The fine tuning of such ANs may lead us to safe gene editing enzymes.

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Targeting G-Quadruplexes with novel triphenylamine derivatives: recognition and biomedical applications.

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Nowadays is well known that DNA can fold into various inter- and intramolecular secondary structures such as G-quadruplexes.[1]

This type of DNA can be found at the end of chromosomes, the telomeres. Each time a normal cell divides, the ends don't get completely copied and they become just a bit shorter.[2] However, there is an enzyme who can deal with the shortening of telomeres, the telomerase. High telomerase activity has been detected in approximately 90% of tumor cells.[3] Consequently, the inhibition of the telomerase activity is considered an attractive target for antitumor drugs.

This work comprises the study of novel triphenylamine derivatives which are selective fluorescence probes towards G-quadruplex. To get insight into the interaction between the molecules and DNA, we have performed several studies by means of fluorescence spectroscopy, FRET-melting assays and circular dichroism. The best candidate was encapsulated in liposome nanoparticles combining diagnostic and therapeutic effects in one platform. Finally, the cytotoxicity was evaluated in different tumoral cell lines.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the liposome nanoparticles.

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Hydroxyphenyl-benzimidazole based hybrids as metal chelating mimetics of the anti-Alzheimer's drug Donepezil

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Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a severe age-dependent neurodegenerative disorder, affecting about 47 million people worldwide [1]. So far there is no curative medication to prevent or slow down the progression of the disease but only with palliative effects and temporary symptomatic reliefs [2]. Since the unmet AD cure is believed to be mainly due to its complex multifactorial nature, recent worldwide research has been focused on developing compounds with multi-target profiles, namely to hit some of the main pathophysiological hallmarks of the patient brains as the deficit in cholinergic neurons, deposits of amyloid peptide (A β), as well as dyshomeostasis of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and redox-active metal ions [3,4].

As part of our continuing effort towards innovative anti-AD drugs, we have been using a polypharmacological strategy based on the repositioning of already approved palliative drugs with acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitory capacity which are extra-functionalized to endow the compounds with other targeting capacities [4,5]. Thus, following recently reported studies on tacrine-hydroxyphenyl-benzimidazole (TAC-BIM) hybrids with multi-targeting capacity [6], we decided to explore the use of the same extra-functional group (BIM) to develop multifunctional derivatives of another AChE inhibitor drug (donepezil). In particular, multi-targeting donepezil mimetics, based on the conjugation of a piperidine/piperazine active moiety with BIM (see Fig 1), have been designed and studied in terms of their potential multiple properties, such as inhibition of AChE and A β aggregation as well as modulation of metal ions and ROS. A set of compounds were tested and showed good AChE inhibitory activity (low micromolar range) and moderate inhibition of A β ₁₋₄₂ self-mediated aggregation, which generally improved for Cu-induced aggregation.

Taking into account the recognized role of the metal ions as age triggers of AD, namely responsible for A β aggregation and oxidative stress [7,8], the copper and zinc chelating capacity of the developed compounds is herein evaluated for representative examples of this set of chelating hybrids. The compounds showed good chelating capacity towards Cu(II) (pCu ~ 11-12) and moderate towards Zn(II) (pZn ~ 6) in a 50% w/w DMSO/water medium, mostly involving complex species with metal coordination through the phenolic oxygen and the imidazole nitrogen N(3) of the BIM moiety.

The set of obtained results is discussed in terms of substituent effects and positional isomerization, and structure-activity analyses allow the identification of some promising compounds.

Figure 1. Donepezil and metal-chelating donepezil mimetics

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Novel ratiometric fluorescence sensors for Fe(III) ion

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The development of sensors for metal ions is of considerable importance especially for metals with biological or environmental interest [1]. In recent years, great attention has been devoted to the development of coumarin-based fluorescent chemosensors due to their low toxicity and facile synthesis [2].

We prepared seven derivatives (**L2-L8**) of the 3-(pyridin-2-yl)coumarin (**L1**) (Figure 1), with different substituents in 6th and 7th positions.

L1: R = R' = H,

L5: R = OH, R' = H,

L2: R = Cl, R' = H,

L6: R = H, R' = F,

L3: R = OCH₃, R' = H,

L7: R = H, R' = OCH₃,

L4: R = F, R' = H,

L8: R = H, R' = OH.

Figure 1. Ligands used in this work.

The complex formation equilibria of **L1-L8** ligands with Fe(III) were studied by Uv-vis spectrophotometric titrations. Fluorescence properties of ligands and Fe(III) complexes have also been studied. All the ligands are able to discriminate between Fe(III) and Fe(II).

As an example, selected spectra collected during the spectrophotometric and spectrofluorimetric titrations are reported in Figure 2 for the system **L2-Fe(III)**.

We observed different fluorimetric response for iron(III) complexes in dependence of the position and the nature of the substituents. The differences observed in the emission intensity of ligands and related complexes are discussed also in terms of molecular orbitals.

Figure 2. Selected spectra collected during (A) the spectrophotometric titration of Fe(III) with **L2** (Fe(III) $4.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mmoles, **L2** $4.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M, NaClO₄ 0.05 M ionic strength buffer, 1 cm optical path length, 25 °C, CH₃CN solution) and (B) spectrofluorimetric titration of **L2** with Fe(III) (**L2** $6.75 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mmol, Fe(III) $2.49 \cdot 10^{-3}$ M, CH₃CN solution, 25 °C, λ_{exc} :301 nm).

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A thermodynamic and chemometric study on tannic acid: protonation and interaction with iron(III)

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The Tannic acid (TA) is a polyphenolic compound that belongs to the class of hydrolysable tannins, which are natural polymers derived from the vegetable kingdom [1,2]. Recently, the attention of the scientific community towards these molecules has increased due to their biological activity as antioxidants and antibacterial agents [3–5]. Moreover, TA is used in environmental studies as a surrogate of Natural Organic Matter (NOM), [6,7] and in technological processes to prepare coated nanomaterials. Polyphenols have been employed to prepare metal-phenolic networks (MPNs), in which context TA is a suitable coating agent for biointerfaces because of its high biocompatibility and strong interaction with metal ions, which provide MPNs with additional functionalities [8,1].

The TA molecule is based on a α/β -D-glucopyranose skeleton where the hydroxyl groups are partially esterified by gallic acid. Commercial TA has 1701.20 g mol⁻¹ molecular weight and a declared structure where the central core of glucose is esterified with five digallic units. However, it is actually a mixture of gallic acid, methyl gallate, n-galloyl glucose and compounds with higher molecular weight, having several gallic units linked together by ester bonds around the glucose core [9]. Given the different and interesting aspects concerning polyphenolic compounds, it is interesting to identify chemical models to explain properly the TA protogenic capacity and its coordination capability towards metal cations.

In this work [11], potentiometry, UV-vis, fluorescence spectroscopy and *ab initio* calculations were used to identify the protonation properties and the spectroscopic features of TA. A preliminary chromatographic investigation revealed the presence of gallic acid (GA) in the commercial TA mixture. This mainly affects both the pH of TA solutions and the fluorescence signals, but its impact on the total acidity equivalents is low. The pH-metric data, elaborated with the BSTAC software [10], showed the presence of three main types of protogenic groups, with pK_a values included in the range of 6–8.5. They can be ascribed to phenolic functions and are in quite good agreement with the values obtained by *ab initio* calculations on the basis of model structures. The least acidic site shows the highest concentration, and the dissociation of half of the TA phenolic groups takes place at pH ~ 7.8.

The UV-vis spectra of the protonated and deprotonated species were obtained through data elaboration by the conventional stoichiometric approach (HypSpec®), by spectra decomposition (Gaussian functions) and by chemometric techniques. The results are in quite good agreement and show main absorption maxima at 277 and 323 nm, similar to those obtained using *ab initio* calculations. The fluorescence excitation–emission matrices (EEM) were recorded on solutions of GA and TA with excitation wavelengths in the range of 200–500 nm (10 nm intervals), emission

wavelengths from 250 to 500 nm and a 10 nm bandpass. In order to resolve the contribution of GA to the EEM spectra of TA, a MCR-ALS (Multivariate Curve Resolution-Alternating Least Squares) approach was employed.

A preliminary study on TA - iron(III) system was conducted by UV-vis spectrophotometry. The spectra were recorded in the pH range 3–9, on solutions with concentration ranging between $2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and $6 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol L⁻¹ and metal to ligand ratios of 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3. The solutions were maintained at low ionic strength because of the low solubility of the complexes. The binary solutions show a characteristic LM-CT (ligand to metal – charge transfer) band with an absorption maximum comprised between 500 – 600 nm, which shows a blue-shift after pH ~ 7. The spectra were elaborated by both HypSpec® software and MCR-ALS. Both elaborations showed the presence of two main species.

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The His-containing Peptide Models of Outer Membrane Proteins – Binding Sites Responsible for Copper Redox Balancing. Implication for *Fusobacterium* – related Carcinogenesis.

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Colorectal cancer (CRC) is the third commonly diagnosed form of cancer worldwide. Recent studies have indicated a relationship between CRC and microbial dysbiosis [1]. Increased colonization of *Fusobacterium nucleatum* (*Fn*), anaerobic Gram-negative bacteria, within intestinal tracts has been considered as a biomarker of CRC progression [1-3]. Furthermore, significantly higher concentration of transition metals ions such as copper and iron were also observed in mentioned carcinoma tissues. It has been proposed, that binding of redox active metal ions to bacterial outer membrane proteins may promote ROS (Reactive Oxygen Species) generation what in turn induced carcinogenesis [4-6](Fig.1).

Figure 1: Scheme of the proposed mechanism of *Fusobacterium nucleatum*-induced carcinogenesis via ROS generation.

Herein, we present recent results concerning the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ interaction with His-containing peptide models of bacterial outer membrane proteins – FomA and Aim1. The impact of this interaction on intracellular ROS generation was investigated using model cell line CT26 (mouse colon carcinoma). The Cu^{II} and Cu^{I} binding to peptides were carefully studied using a variety of complementary techniques (potentiometry, UV-Vis, CD, fluorescence, EPR and NMR). Structural motifs regulating $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ affinities and redox cycling were identified. The values of apparent dissociation constants indicated that presence of at least two His residues is crucial for efficient Cu^{I} binding. It is worth emphasizing that peptide cyclisation improved Cu^{I} affinity. The difference between coordination of Cu^{II} to linear and cyclic ligands revealed that peptide cyclisation precisely

imitated loop-binding behavior. The quasi-reversibility of CV waves indicated that Cu^{II}/Cu^I conversion required major reorganization within coordination sphere including: changes of geometry and donor rearrangements. The redox activity was highly dependent on coordination mode. Presence of amide nitrogens among copper binding sites stabilized its higher oxidation state. Due to their higher redox potential, all studied systems were capable of oxidizing various cellular reductants. In the presence of HAsc (ascorbic acid) all Cu^{II} complexes were immediately reduced to Cu^I, however reappearance of Cu^{II} was kinetically sluggish. HAsc-linked redox cycling induced ROS generation and oxidative damages among all peptides. Such metal-catalyzed process caused changes in coordination of reappeared Cu^{II} (Fig.2).

Figure 2: Proposed mechanism for redox cycling of the Cu^{II}/Cu^I complexes with two-His-containing peptide models at pH 7.4.

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Comparative solution equilibrium studies on various antitumor half-sandwich organometallic complexes of 2-picolinates and 8-quinolinols

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Ruthenium complexes have been the subject of extensive drug discovery efforts yielding NKP1339/IT-139 as the most promising Ru(III) compounds being currently under clinical development against numerous human tumor types [1]. Half-sandwich Ru(II)(η^6 -arene) complexes have tunable reactivity and numerous of them show remarkable anticancer activity such as the RAPTA or RAED compounds [2,3]. Rh(III)(η^5 -arenyl) complexes are isoelectric with Ru(II)(η^6 -arene) complexes and have some further (chemically) attractive properties such as the faster ligand exchange processes. Despite the large number of half-sandwich organoruthenium and organorhodium compounds still limited information is available about their solution speciation. However, the knowledge on the solution stability and predominant forms at various concentrations and pH values, ratio of the active aqua and the chlorido species strongly contributes to the understanding and controlling of the pharmacokinetic properties and mechanism of action. Careful tuning on the physico-chemical properties including lipophilicity of the complexes may improve the pharmacokinetic behavior and ultimately the anticancer activity.

Figure 1. The studied half-sandwich organometallic cations and the core structures of the ligands

Here, we report the results on the comparative solution equilibrium studies, X-ray crystal structures and *in vitro* cytotoxicity of Rh(III)(η^5 -C₅Me₅), Ru(II)(η^6 -*p*-cymene) and Ru(II)(η^6 -toluene) complexes formed with various derivatives of 2-picolinic acid and 8-quinolinol bearing (N,O) donor set (Fig.1). Solution stability, chloride ion affinity (Fig. 2) and lipophilicity of the complexes were characterized by the combined use of pH-potentiometry, UV-Vis spectrophotometry and ¹H NMR spectroscopy. The *in vitro* cytotoxic activity was studied in cancer cell lines being sensitive and resistant to classic chemotherapy and in normal cells as well. In addition interaction of selected complexes with the blood transport protein, human serum albumin, was investigated by ultrafiltration and fluorometry. The novel results are compared to our previously published data [4-7].

Figure 2. Complex formation and co-ligand exchange equilibrium processes for the half-sandwich complexes of the organometallic cations

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Developing azole-based ambient condition Pd(II) catalysts for C-C coupling: trends and study of electronic / rigidity features of 2-(thiophen-2-yl)-1H- imidazoles on catalyst activity

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Palladium catalysed carbon- coupling reactions have provided seamless solutions and invaluable to otherwise difficult or impossible organic synthetic challenges [1–4]. Furthermore, it is also a common practice to add a palladium salt and a prescribed ligand into reaction mixtures during application of C-C catalytic coupling strategies [5,6]. However, studies of catalytic behaviours for varying possible catalyst or pre-catalyst species self-assembled during *in-situ* generation of catalyst are scarce. In particular, comparative study of effects of pre-catalyst molecular variations such as cis- or trans-coordination disposition, donor systems variation, etc. on catalytic outcomes is generally scarce [7].

A series of monodentate 2-(thiophen-2-yl)-1H-imidazole ligands (**L1** – **L8**), 2,4,5-triphenyloxazole (**L9**) and 2-(1H-imidazol-2-yl)pyridines **L10** – **L11** were prepared in search for improved azole-based palladium coupling catalysts as well as for systematic study of molecular variation effects on catalytic efficiencies of their palladium complexes. These phosphine-free ligands formed diverse dichloropalladium complexes in three coordination forms, which are chloro-bridged dimers (**PdL**)₂, mono-ligand species with *trans*-solvent coordination **PdL**-solvent and *trans*-bis-ligand complexes **PdL**₂. The triphenylphosphine complex PdI₂(PPh₃)₂ was also studied for comparative purposes. Ligand pK_a estimations and palladium complex single crystal data were analysed and correlations were observed between ligand donor strengths, x-ray structural properties and catalytic efficiencies.

The synthetic design paid off by affording very attractive ambient condition Suzuki-Miyaura coupling efficiencies with catalytic activities at as low as 40 °C, 0.2 mol % catalyst loading, high yields within minutes and tolerance for substrate variation. These catalytic results represent a very significant advancement relative to known imidazole-based precatalysts [8,9], which are often dependent on high temperature and / or requiring very long durations.

Furthermore, complexes bearing the weakly-donating and more rigid phenanthrenyl-substituted ligands **L1** – **L5** displayed superior catalyst activities over complexes of the strongly-donating and more flexible 4,5-diphenyl-substituted ligands **L6** – **L11**. Very poor catalyst activities were observed for *trans*-bis-ligand precatalyst analogues **Pd8₂**, **Pd11₂** and PdI₂(PPh₃)₂ at ambient temperatures, which is ascribed to lack of sufficient ligand-ligand repulsion resulting from non-rigidity coupled with stronger ligand donor strengths. To the best of our knowledge, results obtained in this study represent the best performance for palladium catalyst precursors bearing only simple phosphine-free imidazole ligands.

Fig. 1: (Above) Structures of studied precatalysts; (Below) Overlay of crystal structures, overlay of spectra for protonation-deprotonation experiments and a graph of catalysis progress as a function of time or temperature.

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Sensor and microbiological activity of symmetrical tripods based of 1,8-naphthalimides

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In the recent years, the fluorescent 1,8-naphthalimide and its 4-substituted derivatives capable of changing their photophysical characteristics have been investigated intensively due to their usage in high technology. 1,8-naphthalimide derivatives with amino groups at C-4 position are of yellow colour enhanced by the fluorescence emission, while those with alkoxy groups are colorless and emit blue fluorescence. These spectral characteristics make them suitable for the design of fluorescent chemosensors. The photoinduced electron transfer occurring in the compounds allow to detect metal cations and protons in the environment or in living cells. Therefore, dendritic and branched symmetrical molecules are of great interest. In this case, the presence of more chromophoric moieties in a single molecule leads to signal amplification of its activity. On the other hand, as heterocyclic systems 1,8-naphthalimides are an important class of organic compounds with good biomedical and pharmacological activity and many of them have been used as antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral anti-inflammatory or anticancer therapeutic agents.

In this study, we report on the synthesis of fluorescent tripods comprising three 1,8-naphthalimide fluorescent units, bonded to the central aromatic nucleus (Scheme 1). A very important part in the design and synthesis of the tripods is the receptor fragment, which reacts with the analytes. For the purpose as receptor fragments we used:

- A = *N,N*-dimethylethylamine,
- N,N*-dimethylaminoethoxy
- N*-methylpiperazine

Scheme 1

The influence that the chemical structure of the receptor fragments and the polarity of the organic solvents have on the photophysical characteristics has been investigated and discussed. The effect of different metal cations (Ag^+ , Cd^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and Al^{3+}) on the fluorescence intensity has been studied. The microbiological activity against gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria and the yeast *Candida* has been investigated. Our findings indicate that the tripods possess very high sensitivity to Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} , depending on the sensor receptors. They also exhibit good antimicrobial activity, particularly against Gram-positive bacteria and yeast *Candida* strain.

Materials based on the studied compounds could be effective antiseptics and disinfectants.

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Insights on the metal ion coordination of carboxyphenyl porphyrins and chlorins

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Recent developments in supramolecular assemblies through non-covalent intermolecular interactions have allowed the construction of new molecular architectures with important electrochemical and photophysical properties [1]. Porphyrins are building blocks particularly attractive to incorporate into ordered arrays by self-assembly via (a) metal coordination to peripheral ligands such as carboxyphenyl and pyridyl groups, (b) hydrogen-bonding molecular recognition and (c) central metal coordination. Most of these strategies have been used to obtain materials with superior photoactivities for photonic and medicinal applications [2, 3].

Herein, we are pleased to present our latest results involving the microwave-mediated metallation of synthetic 5-(4'-carboxyphenyl)-10,15,20-tris(pentafluorophenyl)porphyrin **1** and its pyrrolidine-fused chlorin derivative **2** (Figure 1) with Fe(III), Cu(II), Zn(II), Pt(II) and Hf(IV) salts [4]. We intended to achieve a new series of photoactive multiporphyrinic arrays with high absorption in the visible region and strong emission sensing properties, in order to apply them in a wide range of applications, including the development of optical sensors that respond to environmental stimulus [5], and also as promising photosensitizers for photodynamic therapy (PDT) and diagnosis of cancer [6].

The absorption and emission properties of free-base and metal complexes of carboxyphenyl porphyrins and chlorins will be presented as well as the study of the different Cu(II) complexes by EPR spectroscopy. Structural elucidation of possible dimers or trimers was also studied by MALDI-TOF and ESI mass spectrometry.

Figure 1: Structure and spectroscopic characterization of porphyrin **1** and its pyrrolidine fused-chlorin **2**: (a) absorption and emission spectra of macrocycles **1** and **2**; (b) ESI mass spectra region of porphyrin's **1** copper(II) complex; UV-Vis and fluorescence spectra of porphyrin's **1** zinc(II) complex and EPR spectra of porphyrin's **1** copper(II) complex.

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XAFS investigation of Cu coordination environment in complexes with bioactive Schiff base ligands

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A great number of metal-organic ligand complexes are known for having biological activities. Moreover, an increase in the activity of the complexes with the respect to the initial ligand is often observed. As an example Schiff base complexes can be mentioned, which are often used in the design of therapeutic compounds with extensive pharmacological activity. Especially their complexes with transition metals are the subject of interest due to anticancer as well as antimicrobial activity. Not only the presence of metal ion but also its oxidation state, type and number of coordinating ligand next to complexes' coordination geometry define the biological activity of a complex. [1,2]

The aim of presented research is the structural characterization of metal environment in three Schiff base complexes with copper ions. For the ligands (Scheme 1) as well as their complexes, cytotoxic activity (against tumor cell lines of human cervical cancer HeLa and pancreatic cancer CFPAC-1) has been found.

Scheme 1. Initial Schiff base ligands used in complexation reaction.

Since obtaining presented metal–organic ligand complexes in a crystalline form was unsuccessful, therefore structural information about examined compounds were obtained using the XAS (X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy) technique. This technique is ideal to study compounds regardless of their form or state. XAS analysis was supported with a number of different spectroscopic and laboratory techniques.

With FTIR spectroscopy it is possible to confirm that complexes were synthesized and to identify a functional groups that are involved in coordination process. With the elemental analysis metal to ligand ratio has been obtained. In order to get information about local atomic order around Cu ions extended X-ray absorption fine structure (EXAFS) is analyzed, thus giving initial structural information for the model construction. With X-ray absorption near edge structure (XANES) analysis the oxidation state of Cu ions can be determined. Moreover, XANES technique is sensitive to the geometric arrangement of atoms around absorbing center and together with theoretical calculations at DFT level, it is a tool for model refinement. The proposed structural research methodology has been already successfully applied for non-crystalline metal-organic ligand compounds. [3,4]

X-ray absorption results has been obtained in the frame of the Project No. 20175011 at Elettra synchrotron (XAFS beamline).

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Engineering of copper(II) acetate structures with 2-phenylbenzimidazole and its derivative

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Copper is an essential trace element for many biological processes. It is found in a variety of enzymes, including the copper centers of cytochrome C oxidase, the Cu–Zn-containing enzyme superoxide dismutase, and it is the central metal in the oxygen carrying pigment hemocyanin[1]. For example, the trans bis(acetate)bis(imidazole)copper(II) complex, which exhibits the strongest antitumor activity against the mouse melanoma cancer cell line B16[2]. Copper(II) acetate complexes with imidazole derived ligands have been studied as models for copper proteins [3]. Some of these copper(II) complexes were found to have a variety of pharmacological effects such as antitumor [4] and superoxide dismutase activities [5]. The nature of the products that result from the reaction of copper(II) acetate with basic ligands are partially due to the electronic properties of the added bases, though the correlation between these properties and resulting structures are not straightforward. We report herein for the first time about the synthesis of copper(II) acetate complexes with 2-phenylbenzimidazole (L^I) and 2-(2-iodophenyl)-5-chlorobenzimidazole (L^{II}) ligands, namely $[Cu(OAc)_2L^I_2]$ (**1**) and $[Cu(OAc)_2L^{II}_2] \cdot 2AcOH$ (**2**·2AcOH). Complexes were obtained in good yields and were fully characterized by elemental analysis, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, single-crystal X-ray diffraction, topological analysis and Hirshfeld surface analysis.

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Interactions of Square-Planar Metal Complexes with Lewis Acids: Principles of Bonding

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Metal coordination compounds are textbook examples of donor-acceptor bonds in which the central metal ion acts as a Lewis acid and the ligands as Lewis acids. But there is an increasing evidence of complexes where at least one of the bonds is opposite in nature: a central metal ion as a Lewis base donates electron density to the acidic ligand. Currently the main interest is focused on M(0) neutral complexes acting as the Lewis bases on boron ambiphilic (bridged) ligands [1]. Interactions of M(0) complexes with free un-bridged Lewis acids such as GaCl₃ and AlCl₃, BF₃ were studied experimentally and theoretically, respectively, by the groups of Braunschweig [2] and Sakaki [3].

The basicity of the metal centers in the positive oxidation state is still not well recognized phenomena although the first example of this kind of bonding was published already in 1955 by Wilkinson and Birmingham who observed the protonation of di- π -cyclopentadienylrhodium hydride in acidic medium. [4] Recently we have shown that cisplatin acts as a weak Lewis base even in pure water solution [5].

In this contribution the stabilities of donor-acceptor adducts of neutral square planar Pt(II) and Ir(I) complexes with trihydrides and trihalides of group 13 elements of general formula YZ₃ (Y = B, Al, Ga; Z = H, F, Cl, Br) were studied theoretically using DFT methodology in the gas phase. Metal complexes act as the Lewis bases donating electron density from occupied 5dz² natural atomic orbital (NAO) of the metal M atom to the empty pz NAO of Y forming pentacoordinated square pyramidal adducts with M•Y dative bonds. The transferred charge Δq correlated with the energy difference between these two NAO's. Bonding energies reached up to 55.1 kcal/mol and 84.4 kcal/mol for interaction of GaF₃ as the strongest acid with Pt(II) and Ir(I) complexes, respectively. Except Δq , bonding energies depended also on other parameters including Pauli repulsion energy.

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Lead(II). A Mimic of Copper(II) ... and *vice versa*?

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Mankind knows the metal lead already for thousands of years; e.g., there is a figure in the British Museum made of lead that is by now nearly 6000 years old [1]. Hence, it is not surprising that already Greek and Arab scholars were aware of the toxicity of lead [1]. For example, lead affects the central and nervous systems [2], as well as the genetic and reproductive machinery [1, 3]; indeed, it interferes with the metabolism of other metal ions, like Ca(II), Fe(II/III), Cu(II) or Zn(II) [1, 4]. It is thus surprising that the information available for the interaction of Pb(II) with bio-ligands and the stability of the resulting complexes in aqueous solution is rather scarce. Therefore, estimation procedures are desirable.

The indicated lack of information is probably connected with the ambivalent properties of Pb(II) which originate in its 6s² lone pair [5]. If this lone pair is stereochemically active, it screens one side of Pb(II) and leads to low coordination numbers (CNs) [6, 7]. One distinguishes therefore in a first approximation [8] holodirected (symmetric, with a spherical 6s² lone pair) and hemidirected (distorted, with a non-spherical 6s² lone pair) coordination spheres [7, 9]. For example, S-donor atoms are expected to have a minimal Pb(II) 6s-orbital interaction, leading thus to holodirected structures [10]; such sulfhydryl-Pb(II) complexes can be very stable [4, 11], but this is also true for Pb(II) complexes of negatively charged O sites [4, 11]. Indeed, electronegative donor atoms [9], like O sites, favor hemidirected structures [10], whereas "weak" N sites and a high CN favor holodirected arrangements [12].

Evidently Pearson's hard–soft classification fails [4] under these circumstances and this has led Martin to propose his *Stability Ruler* [4, 11] which predicts very similar stabilities for Cu(II) and Pb(II) complexes formed with O-donor sites. One may note that there is a structural similarity between the Jahn-Teller-distorted Cu(II) coordination sphere and the hemidirected one of Pb(II); both like CNs close to four. Indeed, an example for the similarity of the stabilities of complexes formed with O-donor ligands is given in the Table, where

Table. Comparison of the log stability constants of M²⁺ complexes formed with mono-(R-MP²⁻) and diphosphate (R-DP³⁻) monoesters (aq. sol.; 25°C; I = 0.1 M, NaNO₃)^{a)}

L	log K _{M(L)} ^M for M ²⁺ =			
	Cu ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Cd ²⁺	Pb ²⁺
R-MP ²⁻	2.87 ± 0.06	2.12 ± 0.06	2.44 ± 0.05	2.93 ± 0.08
R-DP ³⁻	5.27 ± 0.04	4.12 ± 0.03	4.27 ± 0.03	5.30 ± 0.15

^{a)} Abstracted from Table 6 in [13]. The errors given are three times the standard error of the mean value (σ). R represents in all instances a residue which does not affect metal ion coordination at the phosphate group(s), i.e., neither in a positive nor negative sense.

phosphate monoesters are considered. From the Table it follows that the stabilities of the Cu(II) and Pb(II) complexes are identical within the error limits, whereas the corresponding complexes of Zn(II) and Cd(II) are less stable. There are more such results available which show the analogous pictures [13]. Therefore, one may conclude that Cu(II)-O-donor complexes and their stabilities mimic well the stabilities of the corresponding Pb(II) complexes. Hence, insights into Pb(II) systems for which no experimental data (yet) exist, may thus indirectly be gained. This is of relevance, e.g., for the interaction of Pb(II) with hydroxyl groups [14] and sugar residues [13], where information is obtained in this way.

The affinity of Pb(II) towards N sites is much smaller than towards O sites. In fact, from Martin's *Stability Ruler* it follows [11] that the affinity of ammonia (and imidazole as well) is similar towards Fe(II) and Pb(II) (see also Table 1 in [13]). This helps to rationalize the coordinating properties of Pb(II) towards bio-ligands like adenosine 5'-monophosphate (AMP²⁻) or guanosine 5'-monophosphate (GMP²⁻). In Pb(AMP) no macrochelate formation of the phosphate-coordinated Pb(II) with N7 of the purine residue takes place, whereas in Pb(GMP) an interaction with the N7/(C6)O site occurs [13, 15].

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Complex formation of transition metal ions with the peptide fragments of rat amylin

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Amylin is a 37-residue peptide hormone cosecreted with insulin by pancreatic β -cells. It is the principal constituent of the amyloid deposits that form in the islets of Langerhans in patients with type-2 diabetes mellitus. However rat amylin does not form amyloid-like fibrils and is not toxic to cultured pancreatic islet β -cells. The main difference is in the two sequences that histidine is not present in rat amylin.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37
Human amylin	K	C	N	T	A	T	C	A	T	Q	R	L	A	N	F	L	A	H	S	S	N	N	L	G	P	V	L	P	P	T	N	V	G	S	N	T	Y
Rat amylin	K	C	N	T	A	T	C	A	T	Q	R	L	A	N	F	L	V	R	S	S	N	N	F	G	A	I	L	S	S	T	N	V	G	S	N	T	Y

Figure 1. The sequence of human and rat amylin

Despite the lack of any common strongly coordinating donor functions the tridecapeptide fragment of rat amylin (rIAPP(17-29)) are able to bind copper(II) ion. According to our earlier results the hexapeptide domain –VRSSNN– can be the main metal binding sequence. [1]

Figure 2. The schematic structure of 17-29 peptide region of rat amylin

The sequence of this peptide fragment does not contain any strongly coordinating side chain but is able to keep copper(II) ions in solution in the whole pH range with extra base consuming processes between pH 6-8. Further studies on the shortened fragments revealed that a tetrapeptide segment –SSNN– is responsible for copper(II) binding and the side chain amide group of asparagine is the primary binding site. For getting more information about metal binding of rat amylin, the fragments and its mutants (VRSS-NH₂, SSNN-NH₂, SSNA-NH₂, AANN-NH₂, VRSSNN-NH₂, VRAANN-NH₂, VRSSAA-NH₂ and GGH-SSNN-NH₂) have been synthesized and their metal (Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II)) complexes studied by pH-potentiometric, UV-Vis, CD and EPR spectroscopic methods. [2,3]

These studies unambiguously proved the outstanding role of asparagine in the copper(II) binding of those peptides, in which the asparagine and other polar side chains are present in a specific sequence; these peptides can be effective copper(II) binding ligands even in the absence of a strongly coordinating side chain like histidine. For nickel(II) containing systems an increased stability of the corresponding complexes was measured.

NMR measurements on the N-terminally free peptide SSNA-NH₂ clearly demonstrated that an equilibrium between the common (NH₂,3N⁻(peptide)) and (NH₂,2N⁻(peptide),N⁻(asparagine)) coordination modes can exist in basic solutions. These observations support that a single asparaginyl residue cannot be an anchor for nickel(II) binding but with an amino group in chelating position can contribute to the nickel(II) binding of peptide molecules. Studies on the corresponding zinc(II) complexes ruled out the anchoring and even the stabilizing role of the internal asparagine moieties and only low stability complexes were detected with the exclusive binding of the amino terminus.

From the comparison of the results obtained for the three metal ions, it can be unambiguously stated that although the -SSNN- sequence binds nickel ion more effectively than the simple oligopeptides, the 19-22 peptide fragments of rat amylin have an outstanding affinity for copper(II) binding. This metal binding site, however, is different from that of the human amylin which may also play a role in their different aggregation behaviour.

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Cu²⁺ recognition by C₂-symmetric pseudopeptides

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The design, preparation and study of organic ligands able to interact with specific transition metals are of great current interest for the relevant role of these metals in different areas of chemistry and biology [1]. Among various ligands explored in co-ordination chemistry, the inclusion of amino acid residues in the ligands structure is one of the most common strategies, not only due to their strong coordinating ability to a variety of metal ions, but also because they provide coordination environments of the metal ions similar to those found in metalloproteins with multiple binding sites [2].

Recent contributions from our group have revealed that C₂-symmetrical bis (amino amides) derived from amino acids form stable complexes with Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Ni²⁺ ions [3]. These results have highlighted the importance of different structural factors for this interaction and suggested that the presence of aromatic rings at different positions can be a key structural element.

Fig. 1 – General structure of the C₂-symmetric pseudopeptidic ligands

Herein, we present the synthesis of two new open-chain N,N'-benzylated bis(amino amide) ligands derived from *L*-phenylalanine and *L*-valine (Fig. 1) and the study of their acid–base properties as well as their metal complexation capacity, in particular for Cu²⁺ using a variety of techniques including UV-Vis and CD spectroscopy or ESI-MS [4].

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Thermal Control Nitrite Linkage Isomerism in *Quasi*-aromatic Möbius Chelates

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Coordination compounds, bearing the NO₂⁻ anion, have extensively been studied from the earliest days of coordination chemistry because of the key feature of NO₂⁻ to coordinate a metal center in a rich variety of coordination modes with the formation of nitrito derivatives, where the metal atom is linked by the oxygen atom, and nitro compounds, where the coordination centre is bound by the nitrogen atom. Notably, different coordination modes of the NO₂⁻ anion leads to different physico-chemical properties of the final product.

Helical metallocomplexes fabricated from polydentate Schiff base ligands, comprising two symmetrically related pyridyl coordination sites derived from benzylidenehydrazones, are monohelical due to the constraint rotation around the C–C bond. Upon coordination, the rotating freedom of the two N–N bonds is also reduced, and the ligand can be locked in a twist conformation (Scheme 1). Helical nature of a system renders additionally the question on a possible role of the aromaticity (or resonance effects). Among various types of aromatic species one of the most fascinating are the so-called Möbius objects. Aromatic stabilization in the metallacyclic units is not inextricably linked with a full π -conjugated pattern. In such metallacycles the metal center itself is not stabilized by the conjugation effects and its nature might be a powerful tool to design the *quasi*-aromatic structures with the targeted topology and properties.

Scheme 1

Accordingly, using the Cd^{II} atom for this purpose is particularly attractive since being a soft metal and exhibiting a variety of coordination numbers it can promote the formation of non-predictable final structures with possible interesting properties [1].

We describe the structural investigations of the mononuclear helical complexes synthesised from Cd(NO_x)₂-based (x = 2 or 3) and tetradentate ligand **L**, derived from benzildihydrazone and 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde, in methanol, namely [Cd(NO₂)₂(**L**)]·2MeOH (**1**·2MeOH) and [Cd(NO₃)₂(**L**)]·MeOH (**2**·MeOH) (Scheme 1). The crystal structure of the Cd(NO₂)₂-based complex was studied at 100(2) and 298(2) K to probe the coordination behavior of the NO₂⁻ ligands. For the first time, we observed η²-*N,O*-coordination of the NO₂⁻ anion towards Cd^{II} [2].

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A Contribution to European Food Safety. Indicating Origin and Process of European Cured Hams by using $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ Isotope Ratio and Multielemental Signatures

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Nowadays the production of dry-cured ham is a traditional meat product originating from southern European countries, mainly carried out in Spain, France and Italy with minor contribution of Hungary, Rumania and Greece. Different types of dry-cured ham can be found depending on the origin and environment of raw material and process curing techniques.

Some agricultural practices, such as controlled feeding and intensive rearing, can minimize the chemical variation and will then interfere with geographic origin determination based on multi-discriminant statistics [1]. The use of a precise and accurate specification of the isotopic composition can reinforce discrimination potential. Stable isotope ratio (SIR) determination is one of the robust and performant methods with traditional approach based on ratios of light bio elements such as hydrogen, nitrogen, oxygen, carbon and sulfur, determined often by methods isotope ratio mass spectrometry (IRMS) and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR). The ratios of $^2\text{H}/^1\text{H}$, and $^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O}$ are strongly latitude dependent, while local agricultural practices and animal diet will rather affect the ratios $^{15}\text{N}/^{14}\text{N}$, and $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$, respectively. The recent instrumental development – multicollector (MC)-ICP-MS have expanded the potential of isotope analysis by adding the so-called “non-traditional” elements – strontium, lead [2]. This innovation has improved the information related with the provenance studies due to the outstanding precision and accuracy of simultaneous multi-isotopes detection. The ratio $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ is a long-term stable parameter, which does not significantly depend on human activity, climate or season of production, but is regulated by local geological environment. The ratio $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ is an encouraging provenance tracer and has already demonstrated its great discriminating potential for geographical origin differentiation of various types of food matrices [3]. For processed food, the potential effect on the ratio $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ from food additives could be altered by different preparation steps. Raw meat used in dry-cured ham production varies largely by the mode of farming. While black Iberian pigs are free-range-reared race, the white genotypes used for Parma, San Daniele, and Bayonne hams are intensively reared. The main ingredient generally added during

production is salt [4]. This addition will modify the taste of cured ham and will add the presence of trace elements associated in the salt matrix.

In this study, world famous brands of dry-cured ham – Iberian (Spain and Portugal), Bayonne (France), San Daniele and Parma (Italy) - were investigated with aims to evaluate the feasibility of applying multi-elemental and Sr isotopic compositions to identify their geographic origin. The original analytical data for thirty-four trace and ultra-trace elements determined by high performant quadrupole inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (Q-ICP-MS) is presented. The variation of elemental composition considers as promising constituents to be used for distinguishing of Bayonne ham from hams other origin. Strontium isotope ratio $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ of dry-cured hams determined by multicollector inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (MC-ICP-MS), consider an additional distinctive parameter which presents remarkable improvement for Bayonne ham discrimination. The authors bring attention to the important fact that food processing features can be also traced by isotope analysis and became an important signature in proving of food authenticity and safety.

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PTFE (“TEFLON”) Sealing Ring for hermetic greaseless Glass Joints

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There is a prejudice that PTFE (often called “Teflon”) is too inelastic to be a hermetic sealant for greaseless conical joints. Therefore, teaching books [1,2] recommend threaded or flanged “O-ring joints” for hermetic manipulation of air- and moisture sensitive chemicals if joint grease is no option.

Here we show [3] (Figure 1) that the common ground conical glass joint can be sealed relatively hermetic and at low cost with a narrow flat PTFE sealing ring (less than 1 mm wide and 0.1 mm thick, weight only 5 mg PTFE). The sealing ring is high-vacuum tight (air leakage rate 10^{-8} ... 10^{-6} mBar*Liter/sec), solvent tight (loss of ethyl acetate out of containers < 0.1 mg/day) and resistant to fluctuation of temperature (freezing-thawing-heating cycles). The reusable PTFE sealing ring prevents stuck joints, is thin enough to be used with all joint clamps and is fixed elastically (without groove) on the glass joint. We demonstrate also a new all-glass-syringe ((Figure 1, 1 - 100 mL) that is gastight at fluctuating temperatures (freezing-thawing-cycles) by a similar exchangeable sealing ring (PTFE) in a groove of the glass piston [4].

Figure 1. Left: PTFE-sealing ring fixed elastic (no groove necessary). Middle: Sealing ring intransparent without pressure. Right: Sealing ring transparent under sealing pressure. Far right: A similar PTFE ring and a piston groove make an all-glass-syringe gastight.

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Poster Contributions

Synthesis and DNA binding tests of a fluorescent pyrene bearing a Pt(II) pyridineimino complex

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Despite the long time gone respect to the discovery of cis-platinum anticancer activity, still a huge amount of research is devoted to the design of new Pt(II) complexes with enhanced biological activity [1-3].

The here presented work concerns the synthesis of a fluorescent pyridinimino platinum(II) complex (Figure 1), where the presence of a cis-platinum moiety linked to an extended aromatic residue could provide interesting properties as for binding to biosubstrates. In fact, covalent Pt(II) binding can occur, which would be strengthened by the anchoring offered by possible intercalation in nucleic acids of the pyrene fragment. Antiproliferative properties have been described for some pyridinimino [4] and pyridinamino [5] platinum(II) complexes. Moreover, similar bifunctional systems have already been tested with interesting performances [7,8].

Figure 1. The metal complex synthesized and analysed in this study: [dichloro{N-[7'-(pyren-2''-yl)-3',6'-dioxahsept-1-yl]-pyridyl-2-methanimine}platinum(II)]

The chelating iminopyridine ligand was prepared by a condensation reaction between pyridine-2-carboxyaldehyde and the suitably O-alkylated aminoalcohol. The platinum complex was then synthesized starting from *cis*-[PtCl₂(DMSO)₂], and purified by crystallization. The pure complex (elemental analysis) was spectroscopically (IR, ¹H-, ¹³C and ¹⁹⁵Pt NMR) characterized. It is well soluble in DMSO and in DMSO/H₂O mixtures, where its stability was checked by ¹H- and ¹⁹⁵Pt NMR. The absorbance and fluorescence optical features of the dye were also checked.

Afterwards, the target Pt(II) complex was let interact with natural double stranded DNA to check its reactivity towards this biosubstrate. Spectrophotometric and spectrofluorometric titrations show that the binding does indeed occur. As for absorbance data, hypochromic and bathochromic effects suggest intercalative binding. However, the absence of a defined isobestic point indicates

multiple equilibria. Interestingly and in agreement with this observation, the light emission behavior of the dye/DNA system is complex. Opposite fluorescence change trends are observed at different temperatures, likely related to a different contribution of DNA-templated dye aggregation. Under the (until now) explored conditions, the binding is so strong to turn to be quantitative. Further experiments are ongoing to better enlighten the binding mechanism.

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Tetranuclear Co(II)-Complexes with a Macrocyclic Tetraaza(tetrakis(thiophenolato))-Ligand System: Syntheses, Characterisation and Magnetic Properties

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In the last decade much effort has been invested in synthesis and characterisation of polynuclear transition-metal thiolate complexes, due to their intriguing magnetic and electronic properties [1]. In 2014 SCHLEIFE developed a synthesis for a novel amino-thiophenolatoligand, which is able to form tetranuclear complexes with selected 3d-transition metals [2]. In this case polynuclear Cobalt-complexes are of special interest because of their magnetic behaviour [3, 4].

Figure 1. Tetraaza-tetrakis(thiophenolato)-ligand H_4L^{MeN4S4} (left), Molecular structure of Cobalt-benzoate-complex $[Co_4L^{MeN4S4}(\mu-Cl)(\mu-OBz)_2]^+$ (right) (Co: purple, S: yellow, N: blue, Cl: green).

The syntheses and characterisation of tetranuclear Cobalt(II)-complexes are presented. The magnetic exchange interactions of some complexes are investigated by temperature depending magnetic susceptibility measurements.

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A new Kojic Acid-peptides: solid-phase synthesis, complexation and biological activity

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Peptides are known for being highly selective, efficacious, relatively safe and well tolerated. Their roles are crucial in human physiology, including actions as hormones, neurotransmitters, growth factors, ion channel ligands, or anti-infectives being able to bind to specific cell surface receptors where they start up intracellular effects. Consequently, there is an increased interest in peptides in pharmaceutical research. Nevertheless, naturally occurring peptides are often not directly proper for use as convenient therapeutics for their intrinsic weaknesses, such as poor chemical and physical stability, and a short circulating plasma half-life [1,2]. Therefore our idea is to create a new series of Kojic Acid (KA) derivatives combining peptide properties in order to promote the transport of chelating agents in biological fluids and test toxicity and inhibitory capacity [3]. KA has been studied for its antifungal and antibacterial properties and as a food additive to prevent enzymatic browning since it acts as a potent metal chelator and consequently because of its inhibitory effects on melanin synthesis in which tyrosinase plays an important role in the biosynthesis from tyrosine amino acid [4]. In the past several KA peptides and amino acid derivatives have been synthesized showing high tyrosinase inhibitory activity, higher storage stability and lower toxicity than KA [5,6]. Instead of classic solution strategy, solid-phase synthesis (SPPS) has been performed. Keeping the peptide elongation via a coupling reaction between amino acids according to Fmoc strategy [7,8,9], the key of SPPS is to add a covalent attachment step that links the nascent peptide chain to an insoluble polymeric support such as resin. KA derivatives has been synthesized with a single amino acid or a very short peptide sequences, to prevent a weakening of the metal ion coordination.

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Transition Metal Complexes as Driers for High-solid Alkyd Binders

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High-solid alkyd resins are polyesters mainly based on renewable sources (e.g. linoleic acid contained in natural triglycerides). Drying process usually involves physical (solvent evaporation) and chemical drying, which is ensured by oxo-polymerization process called autoxidation. High-solid resins contain a few solvents, so evaporation has insignificant effect [1]. Fatty acid esters determine low volatile content due to tendering a sufficient number of functional groups for cross-linking reactions. High-solid alkyd resins have specific behavior during autoxidation process. Common features include long drying times, tendency to create defects and soft cured films [2]. Alkyd resin, used for this work, is based on tall oil fatty acids (TOFA) and pentaerythritol, as four functional component, provides many ways to modifications (see Figure 1). In our case, pentaerythritol allows to increase the concentration of reactive centers in alkyd resin (isolated double bonds). This binder is solventless, low yellowing and suitable for decorative coatings uses. Autoxidation process is accelerated by redox reactions generated with drier addition. Driers are generally transition metal compounds capable of reversible change in oxidation state.

Figure 1: Simplified structure of high-solid alkyd resin.

These redox-active complexes are primary responsible for hydroperoxides decomposition but they can also catalyze their initial formation (see Figure 2). Kinetic parameters of autoxidation process were already studied on model compounds (e.g. ethyl linoleate, methyl ricinate, 3,6-nonadien,...) by many techniques including infrared spectroscopy in transmission mode [3]. However, kinetic parameters obtained from model systems are not suitable for application in real systems like alkyd resins, where autoxidation process does not proceed uniformly over the entire

volume of the layer. Kinetic parameters are affected by many factors (polarity, oxygen diffusion, chemical composition) in these systems.

Figure 2: Abridged autoxidation process of alkyd resin.

This work is focused on study the behavior of driers based on different transition metals widely used in industry (cobalt, vanadium, iron and manganese) and their catalytic effect to autoxidation process. Tested coatings (drier/TI870) were characterized by film drying time, relative film hardness, cross-cut test and IR spectroscopy. This study provides a new insight onto autoxidation process in different layers of polymeric film due to FTIR-ATR measurements.

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Competition of transition metal ions between the trihistidyl and N-terminal histamine binding sites in HAVAHHH peptide

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It is well-known that essential metal ions play an important role in the synthesis and transport of organic molecules and in the catalysis of acid-base and redox processes in biological systems. Such interactions are present in the metalloenzymes, too. The histidine imidazole nitrogens are frequent side chain donor groups in these metalloenzymes and imidazole nitrogen is one of the most important binding sites of transition metal ions. Such metal ion / protein interaction plays role for example in the function of Cu,Zn superoxide-dismutase enzyme or neurodegenerative diseases. So it is momentous to investigate the interaction between the transition metal ions and the peptides and proteins.[1-5]

Aims of our present metalloprotein chemistry research work were the synthesis, equilibrium, and structural studies of complexes of N-terminally free HAVAHHH-NH₂ multihistidine peptide. The measurement involved Cu(II), Ni(II) and Zn(II) ions. The formation of copper(II), nickel(II) and zinc(II) complexes of the mentioned ligand were studied using pH-potentiometric, UV-vis, CD spectroscopy and ESI-MS and MS/MS techniques.

The HAVAHHH-NH₂ heptapeptide contains two types of binding site including terminal amino group and histidine imidazole ring. Due to the biological relevance the simultaneous presence of these metal ions are also important to investigate if mixed metal complexes are possible to be formed.

In the presence of all three metal ions the studied peptide form ML complexes in the physiological pH range with the coordination of N-terminal part of the molecule and the distant histidyl sites can also contribute to the metal binding. At higher pH coordination isomer copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes are formed simultaneously with deprotonation and coordination of amide nitrogen.

The novel technique, the complex MS/MS served as a good method to determine the favourable binding site of metal complexes. For the CuH₂L complex the metal ion binding on the N-termini is preferred, in contrast the primary binding site of the Ni(II) ion is His5 imidazole ring.

On the other hand this oligopeptide is able to bind more than one Cu(II) or Ni(II) ion. At excess of metal ion M₂H₄L and M₂H₅L complexes are formed at high pH range. Moreover the presence of both metal ions results in the formation of mixed Cu(II)/Ni(II) complexes. The existence of CuNiH₅L was supported by mass spectrometry.

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Interaction of organometallic half sandwich Ru(II) and Rh(III) complexes with human serum albumin

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Interest in the medicinal properties of ruthenium(II)-arene compounds has grown rapidly over the last decade. Research has been devoted principally to the study of complexes with a bidentate ligand and one chloride co-ligand (see figure); the prototype compounds of this class are RAED complexes, *i.e.* [Ru(η^6 -arene)(ethylenediamine)Cl]. It is generally accepted that cytotoxicity of Ru(II)-arene compounds is related to their ability to bind DNA nucleobases, although catalytic activity of the complexes and existence of possible protein targets may have importance in the mechanism of cancer cell death as well [1,2]. Related [Ru(η^6 -arene)(1,3,5-triaza-7-phosphaadamantane)Cl₂] (RAPTA-type) complexes were found to exhibit relevant antimetastatic properties *in vivo*, that probably can be due to interactions with extra cellular matrix proteins and cell surface molecules [3]. Rh(III)-cyclopentadienyl complexes are isoelectric with Ru(II)-arene complexes and have some chemically attractive properties such as increased aqueous solubility and faster ligand exchange kinetics [4]. Promising antiproliferative activity of half-sandwich organometallic Rh(III) complexes based on (N,N) donating polypyridyl ligands, with IC₅₀ values in the low micromolar concentration range, have been reported [4]. Molecular targets of Rh(III)-cyclopentadienyl complexes are not clarified yet.

Interaction of these Ru(II) and Rh(III) compounds with proteins may proceed not only at the site of action but it starts probably long before as they enter into the human body. In this account the interaction with serum proteins, such as human serum albumin (HSA) comes into focus. Various binding sites are provided on HSA, since this protein possesses several nonspecific hydrophobic pockets and direct coordination of amino acid side chains to the metal center is feasible as well. At the same time reaction partners can be found among the low molecular mass (LMM) components of the blood serum as well. The available information about the blood serum speciation of this type of organometallic half-sandwich complexes using ‘real-world’ samples is fairly limited in the literature. The coordination of the accessible surface imidazole nitrogen donors (His) of HSA to the Ru(II) centre was reported by Sadler *et al.* in the case of [Ru(η^6 -biphenyl)(ethylenediamine)Cl]⁺ complex

[5]. The interaction of $[\text{Ru}(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cymene})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]^{2+}$ with amino acids Met and S-methyl cysteine was reported to be fairly fast by Buglyó *et al.* and high stability complexes formed [6]; while coordination of Ser resulted in a low stability mono complex [7].

HSA is a blood transport protein, although it is also a good model to study metal complex–protein interactions in general. Our aim was to investigate the binding of some Ru(II) and Rh(III) complexes towards HSA in detail to reveal their distribution in blood serum. Studied complexes possess various bidentate ligands with (O,O), (O,N) and (N,N) donor atom sets such as hydroxypyridinones, picolinate derivatives, ethylenediamine and 2,2'-bipyridine. Aqueous stability of these complexes were reported (mainly by us) in the literature, which was helpful in the interpretation of results on their protein binding [8,9]. Global and site specific binding of the complexes will be presented here; kinetic aspects, binding strength and the mode of interaction (dissociative, non-dissociative) are in scope of our interest. Effect of LMM components on the protein binding of these compounds is investigated as well. These studies are performed using UV-Vis spectrophotometry, ¹H-NMR spectroscopy, spectrofluorometry, ultrafiltration, and capillary zone electrophoresis.

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Affinity protein purification resulting in protein sequence without remaining amino acid residues

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Artificial nucleases are commonly applied for DNA engineering. The well-known zinc-finger nucleases and transcription activator-like effector fusions with FokI nuclease domain (ZFN and TALEN, respectively), as well as the most recent CRISPR/Cas RNA-guided endonucleases [1] have the disadvantage of performing off-target cleavages. Although this side effect is minor, it prevents these nucleases from using them in human gene therapy.

The aim of our research is to develop specific artificial ZFNs with safe control mechanism in which the nuclease domain of Colicin E7 (NColE7) from *E. coli* forms the catalytic domain. In these proteins an array of three ZF motifs was joined to the selected N- and the C-terminal sequences of NColE7 by designed linkers [2]. We envisaged that these nucleases can be allosterically regulated: the catalytic reaction can occur only when the recognition domain binds to the specific DNA sequence and the conformational changes are forwarded to the cleavage domain. The solution structure of three such nucleases and their interaction with Zn²⁺ and DNA were examined by circular dichroism spectroscopy, mass spectrometry and electrophoretic assays [3].

Fig. 1 A) Schematic drawing of the designed NColE7-based artificial metallonucleases.

B) Scheme of the developed purification process.

The purification of the computationally designed NColE7-based ZFN proteins requires a complicated procedure and is time consuming. It is important to obtain the proteins with the precise amino acid sequences, without any additional residues. Therefore, most of the traditional affinity chromatography methods are not applicable, since the protease cleavage can not be performed at an

arbitrarily chosen sequence. To avoid this, no sequences encoding for affinity tags were fused before during the expression and purification of the new ZFNs.

In order to make the purification more effective and simple, our research group developed a new purification process. The genes of the new constructed ZFNs (Cx-ZF-Ny and Cx-ZF, where x and y are the number of the amino acid residues of the C- and N-terminal NCoIE7 fragments fused to the two termini of a zinc finger domain) were inserted into a modified pET-21a vector by means of which a His₆-tag and an SRHX motif were fused to the C-terminal part of the proteins during expression (**Fig. 1**). The fused part can be cleaved by Ni(II) ions owing to the SRHX motif [4, 5]. The purification of the His₆-tagged proteins were successful by Ni-affinity chromatography, and the optimization of the Ni(II)-induced cleavage is currently carried out. The most recent results will be presented in the poster.

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Green Synthesis of cobalt nanoparticles by using plant extracts

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Green synthesis of metal nanoparticles has been recently recognized to be a simple, environmentally friendly, pollutant-free and low cost approach versus conventional synthesis techniques. In this context, some researchers have been studied the use of plant extracts for the fabrication of nanoparticles [1]. Plant extracts contain bioactive compounds such as tannins, phenolic acids, flavonoids and reducing sugars that have redox activities and are good chelation agents. In fact, it has been reported that green synthesis of nanoparticles by using plant extracts produces NPs of smaller size with good stability as the bioagent acts as reducing and capping agent [2].

In this work, the use of different plant extracts for the synthesis of cobalt nanoparticles has been studied. Extracts of grape stalks, rooibos, coffee beans and pomegranate peel have been prepared, characterized and used as bioagent for cobalt-NPs synthesis. A conventional cobalt-NPs synthesis by using chemical reagents (NaBH₄/citric acid) [3] was conducted to compare the obtained cobalt-NP.

For the synthesis of cobalt-NPs, the reducing/capping reagent was added to a cobalt chloride solution in a stoppered tube placed in a controlled temperature bath and under N₂ atmosphere. After the reaction, the solution was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 min. The pellet was washed with ultrapure water and resuspended in absolute ethanol. Cobalt-NPs size present in the supernatant and in the resuspended pellet was measured by dynamic light scattering (DLS).

DLS results indicate that the smaller particle size cobalt-NPs were obtained when rooibos and grape stalks were used as bioagents. Then, a deeply study of the optimal conditions for the synthesis of cobalt-NPs by using the bests bioagents was conducted. To do this, a factorial experimental design [4] was used to investigate the effect of three independent variables on cobalt-NPs size: ratio extract/metal solution, reaction temperature and reaction time. The synthesis experiments were conducted randomly at different levels of independent variables coded as $-\alpha$, -1 , 0 , 1 , $+\alpha$ for high and low values, respectively with 6 central points to give a total of 21 synthesis runs. The low and high levels of the variables values were selected according to the results obtained in a preliminary test.

The obtained cobalt-NPs were characterized by XRD diffraction. The structural morphology was examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM).

Figure 1. Graphical representation of green synthesis of Co-NPs

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Studies on arsenic and fluoride adsorption and removal from natural waters using a titanium dioxide sorbent

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The quality of drinking water is an issue of paramount importance to ensure the health of the population around the world. The presence of fluoride can be either beneficial or harmful for human health depending on the fluoride concentration in drinking water. Lower concentration of fluoride in drinking water is determined as an essential micronutrient to prevent dental caries and facilitate the mineralization of hard tissues, while at higher levels, fluoride can have adverse impact on human health, causing dental or skeletal fluorosis. The standard level of fluoride in drinking water is 1.5 mg L⁻¹ according to the WHO. However, arsenic is a potent human carcinogen, and its presence in water, especially groundwater, is a major problem in different areas of the world. The maximum As content in natural waters is recommended to not exceed 10 µg L⁻¹.

Among the different technologies developed for inorganic species removal, the adsorption process is a well-established technology that can be used for either fluoride and arsenic removal from groundwater, especially for small communities, because of the ease of handling, sludge-free operation, and possibility of regeneration.

In this study we have studied the adsorption of inorganic arsenic species and fluoride anions present in water samples using Adsorbisia As600, a commercial grade TiO₂.

Inorganic arsenic species in aqueous solution are neutral or anionic, according to the corresponding pK_a values and the pH of the sample. At the pH range of natural waters H₂AsO₄⁻, HAsO₄²⁻ and H₃AsO₃ are the predominant species while the primary titanium dioxide nanoparticles include the neutral species TiOH⁰ and the negatively charged TiO⁻. A formation of bidentate complexes such as [(TiO)₂...AsO₄]⁻, [(TiO)₂...AsO₄]⁻ and [(TiO)₂...AsO₃]⁻ has been postulated [1]. In a previous work, Adsorbisia As600 was used for analytical purposes to preconcentrate As(III) and As(V) from natural waters [2].

In the case of fluoride, it is well known that it is adsorbed by ferric and aluminum (hydr)oxides through the formation of inner-sphere surface complexes with the surface hydroxyl sites [3]. When the surface complexes are formed, the surface hydroxyl groups, which are considered as the most abundant and active adsorption sites for adsorption of anions, will be replaced by the adsorbed anions. In the present study this titanium dioxide sorbent has been explored for the first time as a fluoride adsorbent, and all parameters affecting the system have been evaluated such as adsorption isotherms, possible interferences, and effect of pH, among others. It was observed that the adsorption was not affected by the pH but the presence of high amounts of hydrogen carbonate interfered in the removal of fluoride. This issue was solved increasing the amount of adsorbent used. Moreover, we took benefit of this interference, and hydrogen carbonate was investigated as a possible eluent of the adsorbed fluoride, obtaining a quantitative recovery. Thus, it was possible to regenerate the sorbent without losing its efficiency.

The good performance of this adsorbent for the treatment of ground water samples with both arsenic and fluoride was demonstrated by achieving high removal efficiency values using polluted waters. Then, water treatment with this sorbent allowed the fulfillment of the limits established by the WHO, as it can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Effect of water composition on fluoride and arsenic removal. Water sample: 25 mL; amount of sorbent: 1g; contact time: 24h. (*added)

Ground water sample	HCO ₃ ⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	F ⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	As (µg L ⁻¹)	Cl ⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	F ⁻ removal efficiency (%)	As removal efficiency (%)
Initial concentration	340.92	10*	99.73*	17.2	22.55	89	>90
Final concentration	59.29	0.55	<10	24.26	87.6		

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A highly-unsaturated macrocycle for Zn(II) detection and antitumoral activity

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Zinc is the most ubiquitous of the trace elements involved in the metabolism of human beings, and its physiological importance has long been recognized. It is needed by more than one hundred specific enzymes for their catalytic functioning, it plays a part in many biochemical pathways and has multiple roles in the perpetuation of genetic material. Zinc also affects both non-specific and specific immune factors, such as the integrity of the epithelial barrier and the function of neutrophils, monocytes, macrophages and lymphocytes. Due to its primary biological importance, and because several diseases can be ascribed to its deficiency or over-exposure, many health organizations have convened expert committees to develop estimates of human zinc requirements.[1,2]

In this context, developing fluorescent chemosensors with a high selectivity for Zn(II) in an aqueous solution is an urgent and important goal in analytical chemistry. Herein we describe the PeT-mediated Zn(II) sensor 13,16,19-trimethyl-1,3,4,13,16,19,28,29-octaaza-36,37-dioxapentacyclo[29.3.1.1(2,5).0(6,11).0(21,26).1(27,30)]eptatriconta-2,4,6,8,10,21,23,25,27,29,31,33,1(35)-tridecaene containing five aromatic ring as photoactive unit and a tertiary polyamine, able to detect Zn(II) in aqueous and organic media (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Structure of L and fluorescence titration in water/ethanol 50/50 v/v at pH=7.4 (TRIS, λ_{ex} =315 nm)

Biological studies on neoplastic models demonstrated that exposure to **L** led to a dose-dependent reduction in cell survival in all the cellular lines considered. Sublethal concentrations of **L** induce profound cell cycle changes, whereas exposure to lethal doses causes the induction of programmed cell death. Molecular biology studies indicated that **L** interacts with DNA. Taken together, these results show that **L** may exert its antiproliferative activity through the induction of DNA perturbation. This evidence, together with the high synthetic versatility of polyamine compounds, makes **L** an interesting molecular scaffold for the future design of new potential anticancer agents.

The X-ray structure of free **L** is reported (Figure 2.)

Figure 2. X-ray structure of free **L**.

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Iron coordination properties of Gramibactin, a novel bacterial siderophore

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Iron plays a crucial role in life, being involved in numerous biochemical reactions. However, in spite of being one of the most abundant transition metals present in the biosphere, under aqueous-aerobic conditions and neutral pH, iron is present as insoluble Fe(III) oxide, which is not a readily available nutrient form. Therefore, to overcome this difficulty, living organisms have developed a large variety of highly regulated mechanisms to acquire ferric and ferrous iron. One of these strategies is the secretion of ferric iron-chelating molecules – *siderophores* – that promote iron uptake from the environment (or strip it from other iron chelants).

In this communication, we will report the results of the solution thermodynamics study of a new siderophore, gramibactin (GBT) produced by *Burkholderia graminis*, a cereal-associated bacteria.[1] Using potentiometric and spectrophotometric titration techniques, the acid-base behavior of GBT was studied, as well as its complexation ability towards Fe³⁺ in aqueous solution and over a wide range of pH values (2 ≤ pH ≤ 11), at $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ in KCl_(aq) and $T = 298.15 \text{ K}$. Due to the high stability of the formed GBT/Fe(III) species, the ligand-competition method was applied, using EDTA as competing ligand.[2]

The sequestering ability of GBT and its dependence on pH will be also discussed, in terms of pM and pL_{0.5}. [3]

Speciation diagram of Fe³⁺/EDTA/GBT system: fraction of Fe vs. pH, in $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ KCl_(aq) and $T = 298.15 \text{ K}$. $c_{\text{GBT}} = c_{\text{EDTA}} = c_{\text{Fe}} = 1 \text{ mmol dm}^{-3}$.

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Simple Cu(I) complexes as potential low-cost antenna for dye-sensitized solar cells

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The technology of converting sunlight into electricity has recently emerged as an important strategy aimed at achieving a sustainable diversification of the energy matrix in Uruguay and other South American countries. In this regard, photovoltaic devices appear quite attractive because they are noiseless, present no carbon dioxide emission, and require rather simple operation and maintenance, those of solid-state junction—usually made of silicon—being the most important ones. This technology, which is associated with important costs, has been challenged in the last few years by the development of a third-generation solar cells based on conducting polymers films and nanocrystalline oxide. The so-called dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSC) appear as a representative prototype of this family of photovoltaic devices. They combine the optical absorption and the charge separation processes by association of a sensitizer—as the light-absorbing material—with a wide band-gap semiconductor of nanocrystalline morphology.

In this contribution, simple Cu(I) complexes with potential application as low-cost antenna for DSSC are presented. In order to get a clear picture of their behaviour in solar-cell conditions, microwave-afforded nanoparticles of anatase and hydrogen-titanate nanotubes of composition $H_3Ti_2O_7$ were sensitized with the antenna-complexes. The sensitization process was conducted by means of the so-called *surface-as-ligand* approach (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Schematic description of the *surface-as-ligand* synthetic strategy employed in the sensitization process.

First, the anchoring ligand (L^{anc} : 2,2'-biquinoline-4,4'-dicarboxylic acid, $H_2\text{biqdc}$) was bonded to the surface of the semiconductor. Then, the modified surface was treated with a solution of a homoleptic $[\text{CuL}_2]^+$ complex ($L = H_2\text{biqdc}$, neocuproine (neo), bathocuproine (batho)). A ligand-exchange reaction gives the surface-bound (surface- L^{anc}) $\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}\text{L}$ species (hereafter referred to as $[\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}(L^{\text{anc}})\text{L}]@\text{surface}$).

All $[\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}(L^{\text{anc}})\text{L}]@\text{surface}$ species were characterized by UV-vis (reflectance) spectroscopy, vibrational microRaman spectroscopy, and photophysical studies (emission, excitation, and life-time measurements). The reflectance studies did not account for significant changes of the absorptive features of dyes in the VIS-region with sensitization. An example of microRaman results of $[\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}(L^{\text{anc}})\text{L}]@\text{TiO}_2$ systems is showed in Figure 1 ($L = L^{\text{anc}}$, $[\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}(L^{\text{anc}})_2] = \text{CuL1}$). The characteristic A_{1g} , B_{2g} , and E_g modes of anatase at the low-energy region appears to be modulated in the presence of the sensitizer. The sensitization process also resulted in slight changes in a weak band assigned to the symmetrical stretch of the linker groups ($-\text{COO}^-$) at about 1400 cm^{-1} , which could be associated with chemisorption between the dye and TiO_2 . At the same time, a very weak band—assigned to $\square(\text{C}=\text{O})$ stretching of COOH groups—was observed at 1761 cm^{-1} , which appears 22 cm^{-1} shifted to higher energy after sensitization. This observation could indicate that some $\text{C}=\text{O}$ from $-\text{COOH}$ groups are not bound.

Photoluminescence studies of $[\text{Cu}(L^{\text{anc}})\text{L}]^+@\text{TiO}_2$ and of $[\text{Cu}(L^{\text{anc}})\text{L}]^+@\text{H}_3\text{Ti}_2\text{O}_7$ (preliminary life-time decay measurements, in particular) were in line with a very fast decay process with relaxation times below 2 ns.

For the further understanding of the electronic properties of all systems, theoretical studies were also conducted. In this regard, DFT and TD-DFT calculations at the B3LYP/6-31G* level of theory of systems $[\text{Cu}(L^{\text{anc}})\text{L}]$ and $[\text{Cu}(L^{\text{anc}})\text{L}]@(\text{TiO}_2)_n$ ($n = 1-6$) were performed.

Figure 1. MicroRaman results of TiO_2 , of CuL_1 , and of $\text{CuL}_1@\text{TiO}_2$ ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 532\text{ nm}$).

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Nuclear uptake and cytotoxicity of two new Zn(II) mono- and bis-terpyridine derivatives. Interaction with non-canonical DNA structures.

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One of the biggest challenges when developing small molecules as G4 binders, is to turn them into selective compounds for a given G4 DNA structure over others as well as over duplex DNA. G-quadruplexes are four-stranded nucleic acid secondary structures that are formed in guanine-rich sequences tetrads stabilized by K⁺ ions. They exhibit high structural diversity caused by the strand orientation, base composition, nature of pentose ring, conformation of glycosidic bonds of guanine bases in the G-quartets, length and sequence composition of loops/grooves formed. G-quadruplexes are widely distributed in functional regions of the human genome [1] such as human telomeres, oncogene promoter regions, replication initiation sites, and untranslated regions.[2] Many G-quadruplex-forming sequences have been found to be associated with cancer [3] and, thus, these non-canonical nucleic acid structures are regarded as attractive molecular targets for cancer therapeutics with novel mechanisms of action.

Therefore, the search of molecules able to interact and stabilize these structures with therapeutic purposes has attracted growing attention in recent years. [4-5] Among them, terpyridine derivatives constitute an important family of potential G4 ligands.[6] In this work, we show two newly synthesized Zn(II) complexes with terpyridine derivatives, Zn(II) mono and bis- terpyridine, able to target G-quadruplexes. FRET melting assays have revealed that both Zn(II) complexes thermally stabilize G-quadruplex structures even though with different selectivity.

These Zn(II) complexes are fluorescent molecules, hence their cellular uptake can be monitored by fluorescence microscopy. Both terpyridine derivatives are successfully internalized in the cells, being localized mainly in the nucleus. In addition, their cytotoxicity towards SW480 (colon tumor cells) was also evaluated, the Zn(II) bis-terpyridine derivative being more cytotoxic than the Zn(II) mono-terpyridine derivative.

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Structure-Activity Relationship for Benzimidazole-Iridium Complexes

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Chiral half-sandwich complexes of d⁶ transition metals have aroused particular interest due to their wide applications in catalysis and organic transformations. However, compared to the wealthy chemistry of ruthenium and rhodium, endowed with chiral half-sandwich scaffolds, the iridium counterparts have been investigated to a much lesser degree. The last efforts in chemotherapy have been dedicated to develop iridium metallodrugs[1], which exhibit positive antiproliferative activity against malignant cells and inhibit kinase enzymes. Growing interest in new half-sandwich iridium complexes has been shown recently [2,3]. In particular, half-sandwich organo-metallic Ir^{III} compounds display high versatility and display promising anticancer activity.[4] Their potency can be tuned by varying the quelating ligands [5] or changing the substituents on Cp*[6].

Three analogous half-sandwich benzimidazole [(η⁵-Cp*)Ir(LAL')Z]^{0/n+}, LAL' being a bidentate ligand with nitrogen or carbon donor atoms, for example NAN-, or CAN-chelating ligands complexes, have been studied with ctDNA by a set of kinetic, circular dichroism spectroscopy, melting and viscosity experiments. In addition, the cytotoxic activity was evaluated towards A2780 (human ovarian carcinoma), A2780cis (cisplatin resistant) and SW480 (human colon carcinoma) cell lines to elucidate the role of different atoms in their mode of action. The covalent binding with the N7 guanine site takes place in the three studied examples. Furthermore, two of them are bifunctional complexes since both intercalate into the DNA double helix. We can then conclude that the modification of only a single atom in the structure of the complexes determine the mode of binding with DNA.

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Development of BPA-free epoxy-silica resins enriched with Ce or Gd doped TiO₂ as stone conservation multifunctional materials

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The built heritage is involved into constant and irreversible deterioration processes, both of natural and anthropogenic origin, that affect the long-term conservation of lithic materials [1]. Once the stones start to decay, they ought to be treated with products able to improve their resistance against ageing. For this purpose, during the last decades, organic materials such as acrylic polymers, epoxy resins, polyurethanes and perfluoropolyethers have been employed. However, it is well known that in the long term, their thermal and photochemical instability cause chromatic and mechanical alterations to the treated surfaces. On the other hand, the use of silica-based materials obtained by in situ sol gel reactions have partially solved the cited drawbacks, yet they have often displayed cracking upon drying, reducing the consolidation efficiency. To combine the good features coming from both kinds of materials, i.e. organic and inorganic, hybrid materials have been introduced and successfully applied to stone restoration [2-3]. Nevertheless, other characteristics are currently requested to the new materials for conservation, such as multifunctionality and easy handling, with a particular care towards the environmental issues.

The aim of the work here presented was the development of conservation materials based on nanostructured Bisphenol A-free epoxy-silica hybrids. These materials have been synthesized using an epoxy precursor, 1,4-cyclohexanedimethanol diglycidyl ether (CHDM-DGE), by reaction with 1,8-diamineoctane (DAO) as epoxy hardener, in the presence of different siloxane precursors, i.e. glycidoxypropylmethyldiethoxysilane (GPTMS), tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) and isobutyltrimethoxysilane (iBuTMS). The syntheses have been carried out in two different solvents, methanol and chloroform, to establish how the medium can influence the properties of the resulting epoxy-silica resins.

Furthermore, TiO₂, Cerium-doped TiO₂ and Gadolinium-doped TiO₂ nanoparticles, in the anatase form, have been also synthesized and then incorporated into the reaction mixtures during the sol-gel hybrid materials synthesis. The presence of titania should improve not only the self-cleaning and antimicrobial properties of the hybrids, but also their photocatalytic activity under the daylight [4]. In order to select which are the nanoparticles (NPs) with the most suitable properties for the above purposes, the photocatalytic degradation of methyl orange (MO) under both visible and UV light, for each ratio of NPs employed, has been followed by ultraviolet–visible spectroscopy (UV-Vis).

After the selection of the most appropriate synthetic parameters, the interpenetration of the organic and inorganic networks as well as the homogeneity of the NPs distribution into the hybrid matrixes have been studied by a combination of Raman spectroscopy and SEM-EDS analysis. Moreover, the thermal behaviour and water repellence capability of the most promising samples have been investigated by means of TGA, DSC, DMA and contact angles measurements.

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Spectral characterization of polyamidoamine dendrimer Cu(II) complex and its application as bactericide on cotton fabric

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We report on 17 copper ions chelation by polyamidoamine dendrimer modified with eight 1,8-naphthalimide units which was synthesized and investigated by infrared, fluorescent and EPR spectroscopy [1, 2]. The results obtained allow the assumption that the binding sites are in the dendrimer core (the amide and amine groups) and at the receptor fragments [$-\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$] of 1,8-naphthalimide units. The dendrimer ligand and its copper complex were deposited onto a cotton fabric. The regular distribution of metallodendrimers over the fiber surface was observed by scanning electron microscope.

The dendrimers formed clusters with tendency to agglomerate into spherical nanoparticles smaller than 50 nm. In vitro antimicrobial activity of the dendrimer ligand and the metallodendrimer were tested against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and yeast strains. The results showed that inhibitory activity of Cu(II) complex had enhanced in comparison with that of the ligand free of metal ions and was better expressed against the test Gram-positive bacteria and yeasts. Deposition of the metallodendrimers on the textile fabric was found to prevent the formation of a biofilm, which a good indicator that the dendrimer is suitable production of antibacterial cotton fabric.

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New insights into the interaction of anthracene polyaza macrocyclic derivatives with hairpin-DNA.

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Great efforts have been made in order to understand the interaction of polyamines with nucleic acids since it was found, in the 1960s, that they were bound to various cellular anions, including DNA and RNA.[1]

In this line, we have previously prepared a polyamine compound based on a macrocyclic core appended with an arm containing extra donor atoms. The pendant arm has been further functionalized with an aromatic unit. Anthracene was the choice for this aromatic moiety (Scheme 1) (**L3**), for several reasons: other anthracene derivatives show antitumor activity; it has good absorption in the near-UV region and strong fluorescence; and the planar anthracene ring is suitable for intercalation.[2] Recent studies performed in our group, showed that **L3**, and similar compounds, bind efficiently and selectively to mononucleotides,[3] as well as to calf thymus DNA (ctDNA). We also showed how the metal-induced conformational changes of these compounds could be used to modulate their interaction with ctDNA, by hampering the intercalation of the aromatic unit, and how this allosteric effect had an important impact on the *in vitro* cytotoxicity of the compounds.[4]

Scheme 1

In this regard, a new poly-aza macrocycle derivative presenting two anthracene units at the end of the central chain has been synthesized (**L1**), with the main aim to go deeper into the study on the influence of the presence of an extra aromatic ring to the interaction towards DNA. Once synthesized, its acid base behavior has been determined by potentiometric and spectroscopic UV-Vis and Fluorometric studies.

Four specific 29-mer oligonucleotides were selected in order to perform the study about the interaction with the selected polyamines (Scheme 1) towards hairpin-DNA secondary conformations. An A-T rich sequence (AAAATT), G-C rich sequence (GGCCC), the intermediate A-T rich with G-C base pairs (AAGCTT) and the G-C rich with A-T base pairs (GAAGGC).

Figure 1. Cartoon-sticks representation from molecular dynamic studies for the interaction of **L1-L3** towards *AAAATT* 29-mer oligonucleotide, overlapped to free sequence conformation.

Ligand-oligonucleotide interactions have been studied by means of fluorometric titrations, melting point displacement assays, circular dichroism and molecular dynamic studies. The results lead to the conclusion that while interaction of **L2** towards the four sequences under study is mainly driven by electrostatic interactions, **L1** and **L3** interact with hairpin-DNA not only by electrostatic forces but also by intercalation of the anthracene towards the bases-pairs (Figure 1).

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Designing of semiconductor-Cu(0)NPs materials based on graphene oxide for photocatalytic water reduction.

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The availability of renewable energy resources able to replace the use of fossil fuels, is an important challenge. To this purpose, photocatalytic water splitting induced by visible light for the obtaining of H₂ is a promising strategy that is attracting increasing interest due to low cost of the H₂ sources.

The designing of potential photocatalysts for water splitting based in the use of semiconducting materials has to fit the conditions of suitable band gap energies (higher than 1,23 eV) but also it is required both that the separation of charges be efficient and the material to have large surface for chemical reactions to be efficient. Concerning the former issue a limiting factor is the longer time for water oxidation (about five orders of magnitude than for H₂) which favors the electron-hole recombination so limiting the efficiency of the energy conversion [1]. One way by which charge separation can be stabilized consists of depositing suitable materials on the surface of the semiconductor photocatalyst, between which the charge carriers induced by photoadsorption can migrate through the junction between the two components, allowing higher stability to the photoinduced electron-hole pairs [2, 3]. This is the case when, i.e., metal nanoparticles are deposited on a semiconductor surface. In this case, the stabilization of the separated charges induced by photoadsorption is driven by the trend to equilibrate the Fermi level of both materials, which is determined by a Schottky barrier [1].

One of the possibilities for the designing of photocatalysts of Semiconductors-Metals type can be addressed using graphene as the semiconductor partner. The pure graphene behaves as a conductor, which results from the overlapping of bond valence and conduction bands generated by a sufficiently high number (which is the case of a graphene sheet of few nanometers) of 2p_z orbitals of the Csp² atoms of the hexagonal network. Nevertheless, partial blocking of p_z orbitals should result in the appearing of a band gap between the frontier orbitals whose size should depend on the extension of the p_z-blocking.

In this work, it was studied the effect of the adsorption of pyrimidine derivatives on graphene surface (resulting from plane to plane interactions, see Scheme 1) of a reduced graphene oxide (rGO), which results in the formation of rGO-HIS hybrid materials, in the conducting behavior of the last. This gives rise to the semiconducting behavior of the hybrid material due to the reduction in the extension of π -resonant system in the surface of pristine rGO. It was found that the band gap values of rGO-HIS hybrids increases with the amount of adsorbed HIS.

Scheme 1. rGO-HIS-M(II) material.

In a subsequent study it was demonstrated that adsorption of Cu^{2+} on rGO-HIS hybrid is directed by the reactivity of the metal ion with the histidine residues of the anchored HIS, which allows a strict control of the Cu^{2+} adsorption process. Further reduction of rGO-HIS-Cu(II) material with H_2 -plasma let us obtain an rGO-HIS-Cu(0) hybrid material in which rGO surface is decorated with Cu(0) nanoparticles (NPs) with very uniform sizes of c.a 5 nm, which are stabilized by the histidine residues. This material exhibits both semiconducting character and strong optical adsorption due to the plasmon resonance of Cu(0)-nanoparticles. Finally the photocatalytic activities of the obtained materials (rGO-HIS, rGO-HIS-Cu(II) and rGO-HIS-Cu(0) in water reduction are being studied at the moment.

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Lanthanide Complexes of hybrid Schiff-base/Calix[4]arene Ligands: Synthesis, Structures and Properties

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The host-guest chemistry of calix[4]arenes has been well-investigated over the past several decades.[1] The ease of functionalization and versatile complexation properties along with unique three-dimensional structures has also aroused considerable attention in the field of coordination chemistry.[2] To modify the coordination behavior of the parent calix[4]arenes, derivatives with up to four dangling ligand arms at the lower rim have been synthesized.[3] Recently, we have investigated the coordination behavior of calix[4]arene-based ligands exhibiting dangling phosphonate ester and picolinamide groups positions towards a series of lanthanide ions.[4,5] We have now focused our attention on calix[4]arene ligands carrying Schiff bases as dangling units at the lower rim.[6] A series of monofunctionalized compounds of the general type **1** has been synthesized. Herein, we report on the synthesis of these ligands and demonstrate their ability to act as effective supporting ligands for dinuclear lanthanide complexes.

Fig. 1: Structure of ligand **1** and its corresponding terbium(III) complex.

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Mixed-ligand metal complexes of fluorosalicylic acids and 2,6-pyridindimetanol

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Increasing number of researches focus on the optimization of therapeutically active compounds. Optimized effect can be achieved by modification of the compound's structure, composition or complexation by metal ions. Salicylic acid is commonly used in medicine, one of its derivatives, acetylsalicylic acid (Aspirin) known worldwide as a painkiller, anti-inflammatory and antipyretic agent. Recent studies have shown that the introduction of fluorine into the otherwise biologically active molecule may further increase its efficiency.

Previously, our research group studied the complexation of fluorosalicylic acid (FSA) isomers with Cu²⁺ ions [1]. The solution structure and stability constants of the complexes have been determined. Furthermore, we specified that FSA and pyridine derivatives mutually promote each other's metal ion coordination forming Cu(FSA)₂(B)₂ (B = N,N-diethyl-nicotinamide or 3-pyridylmethanol) mixed-ligand complexes around physiological pH [2, 3].

In this study we investigated the formation of ternary complexes of FSA isomers and 2,6-pyridindimetanol (pydime) with transition metal ions such as Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺ ions in solution and in solid state. Their behavior towards DNA and their effect on various cancer cell lines were explored under various conditions, by pH-potentiometry, spectroscopic methods, X-ray diffractometry, agarose gel electrophoresis and MTT cell viability assay. Most recent results will be presented.

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Expression and purification of Cx-ZF-Ny NColE7-based zinc-finger nucleases

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One of the aims of our research group is to develop a catalytic metalloenzyme with a safe control mechanism, able to cleave nucleic acids at a selected specific site. Based on the results of molecular dynamics calculations [1] we investigated the Cx-ZF-Ny type zinc-finger (ZF) nucleases for this purpose. In these enzymes the x C-terminal and y N-terminal amino acids of the nuclease domain of Colicin E7 (NColE7) are supposed to form the regulated catalytic domain. These are joined by linker sequences to an array of three zinc-fingers, which serve as the specific DNA recognizing and binding domain of this novel nuclease.

By OD₆₀₀ measurements during the protein expression in *E. coli* the x and y values were optimized. We were searching for a Cx-ZF-Ny protein, which is not cytotoxic without its Ny part, even though the catalytic center is the Cx part itself. This behavior points to the positive allosteric control by the N-terminal part. Previous results suggested that the mutation of a tryptophan (W) amino acid to alanine (A) in the N-terminal region of NColE7 distorts the structure of the protein, but the interaction with the substrate can induce the native folding [2, 3]. After performing this mutation, a series of Cx-ZF-Ny, Cx-ZF and Cx-ZF-Ny W/A mutant proteins was selected for further experiments. These were expressed in BL21 *E. coli* cells and their purification was attempted by batch ion exchange purification and gel filtration. Catalytic activity of these enzymes was explored to help understanding and optimization of the allosteric activation. The most recent results will be presented.

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Autoxidation of Alkyd Resins Catalyzed by Oxovanadium(IV) Acetylacetonate and Its Derivatives

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Oxovanadium(IV) pentane-2,4-dionate [VO(acac)₂] has been investigated extensively due to its on physical-chemical properties and effects on biological species. Its insulin-mimetic properties have been utilized in treatment of diabetes [1] and oxygen-transfer properties found its application in organic syntheses [2]. Recently, our research group has revealed that [VO(acac)₂] accelerates curing of air-drying paints through catalysis of autoxidation process [3]. The compound has a promising potential in paint-producing industry as potential replacement of currently used toxic cobalt compounds.

This work is focused on derivatives of [VO(acac)₂] bearing benzyl substituents, namely [VO(3-Bz-acac)₂] and [VO(3-(4-MeOBz)-acac)₂] (Scheme 1). These compounds have been prepared and characterized by the spectroscopic methods and the X-ray crystallography. Their catalytic activity was investigated on solvent-borne alkyd resins modified with soybean oil. The detailed study of the drying process reveals their excellent performance at considerably lower concentrations than usual for commercial cobalt-based driers. Furthermore, the modified compounds show lower sensitivity to precise dosage that helps to avoid the overdose effects observed for cobalt-based drier currently used in paint producing industry.

Scheme 1: Structures of oxovanadium(IV) compounds under the study.

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Binding ability of bifunctional 3-hydroxy-4-pyridinone ligands towards divalent metal cations of biological interest

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The 3-hydroxy-4-pyridinones are an important family of compounds that have been developed in view of several pharmaceutical applications, but mainly for metal-chelation therapy and for the detoxification of human body from *hard* metal cations, as the drug Deferiprone [1-3]. They represent a good alternative to the use of Deferoxamine [4], since they are effective in all biological conditions, not involving relevant undesired effects [5-8].

On the sequence of our previous studies on the ability of a set of five bifunctional 3-hydroxy-4-pyridinone ligands (*L1-L5*) for the Al³⁺ sequestration [8], the potential competition with biologically relevant divalent metal cations appears as a quite relevant issue.

These ligands are derivatives of Deferiprone, thus featuring an aromatoid *N*-heterocyclic ring with a hydroxyl and a ketone group in *ortho* position, conferring them a high complexing ability towards M²⁺ and M³⁺ [9]. Furthermore, these 3-hydroxy-4-pyridinones are *N*-extrafunctionalized with alkyl-(amino-carboxylic) groups aimed to introduce differentiation in terms of pharmacokinetic parameters and potential interaction with proteins.

Since the synthesis and acid-base properties were already reported, this contribution is focused on the results of a speciation study in aqueous solution in the presence of three divalent metal cations of biological interest, namely Ca²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺.

The investigation on the binding ability of the ligands towards Ca²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺ was performed by means of potentiometric (ISE-H⁺), UV-Vis spectrophotometric and ¹H NMR spectroscopic measurements at *I* = 0.15 mol L⁻¹ in NaCl_(aq) and *T* = 298.15 K. The elaboration of the experimental data led to the determination of speciation models consisting of M_pL_qH_r species with different stoichiometry, considered the best possible ones on the base of some criteria, such as simplicity, probability, formation percentages of the species, statistical parameters and, if possible, literature data comparison. The stability constants (logβ) determined were in good agreement among the different analytical techniques and, as an example, for the common [ML]^(2-z) species the values follow the trend: Cu²⁺ > Zn²⁺ > Ca²⁺. Furthermore, the sequestering ability of the ligands towards the metal cations was investigated by the determination, at different pH conditions, of an empirical parameter, pL_{0.5}, already proposed by the research group. It represents the total concentration of ligand required to sequester the 50% of the metal cation present in trace in solution [10].

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Metal catalyzed oxidation of a prion protein mutant peptide

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Metal-catalyzed oxidation (MCO) can lead to damage of bio-molecules and this is implicated in oxidative stress, biological aging and neurodegenerative diseases, such as Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease [1]. MCO of proteins is mainly a site-specific process in which only one or a few amino acids at the metal-binding sites of the protein are preferentially oxidized. The amino acid residues of histidine and methionine have been proposed to play important roles in metal mediated oxidative stress. Histidine oxidation predominantly forms oxo-histidine [2], methionine oxidation forms methionine sulfoxide and under extreme conditions, sulfone [3].

Oxidation of a human prion mutant fragment (Ac-SPKTNMKHA-NH₂) was studied. Potentiometric and spectroscopic techniques (UV-Vis, CD) were used to study the speciation, and bonding details of copper(II) complexes, the oxidation of the peptide in the presence of copper(II) ions were studied by HPLC-ESI-MS and MS/MS methods.

Only 1:1 complexes are formed, where the histidine residue is the anchoring binding site and the cooperative deprotonation and coordination of amide functions takes place toward the N-termini. The thioether donor atom of the methionine residue may be also involved in the binding.

(M/L)/hydrogen peroxide and/or ascorbic acid (M is Cu(II) or Fe(III) ion) as oxidizing agents were applied at pH 7.4 where CuL and CuH₋₁L complexes with (S,N⁻,N⁻,N_{im}) and (N⁻,N⁻,N⁻,N_{im}) coordination modes are formed in the copper(II) ion containing systems. The aim of our research was to optimize the condition of oxidation and identify the products of oxidation. The results are presented on the Figure.

It can be stated that the oxidation of methionine is the most preferred, it occurs even in the absence of any metal ion. However, copper(II) and iron(III) ions catalyze this process, which is more effective in the first case, and methionine sulfoxide is the only product at 10-folded H₂O₂ excess.

The oxidation of histidine residue takes place in the presence of ascorbic acid or a large excess of H₂O₂. The formation of an ascorbic acid-ligand adduct promotes, while the high concentration of copper(II) ions hinders the oxidation of the histidine residue. The MS spectra prove that in addition to the 2-oxo-histidine, doubly oxidized form of this side chain also forms. Therefore a product with three additional oxygen atoms is also present in the reaction mixture, in which methionine is oxidized to methionine sulfoxide, while histidine is oxidized to dioxo-histidine.

Figure: The ratio of products after 30 minutes oxidation

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Novel di- and tetranuclear transition metal complexes of a macrocyclic hexaaza-(bis)thiophenolato ligand containing photoswitchable azobenzenes

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Thiophenolate-based dinuclear complexes have been intensively investigated over the past decades. Their biological relevance as model compounds for dinuclear metalloenzymes along with their interesting magnetic and electronic properties arouse considerable attention in the field of macrocyclic coordination chemistry.[1] Since the end of the 1990s, the KERSTING group has focused on the synthesis and characterization of metal complexes of the 24-membered hexaaza-(bis)thiophenolato ligand H_2L^{Me} . [2,3] The ligand system is able to selectively bind a variety of divalent 3d transition metal ions. Herein, carboxylate ions function as coligands, thus creating an octahedral coordination sphere. By coordinating two transition metal centers, preorganized dinuclear complexes with a defined hydrophobic binding pocket are formed in the cavity of the macrocyclic ligand H_2L^{Me} . [3]

Figure 1: Synthesized complexes containing various azobenzene derivatives (left); Molecular structure of $[Ni_2L^{Me}[\mu-Azo-2]]^+$ (right).

In addition to previous studies on the coordination behavior, molecular and electronic structure, and reactivity of the macrocyclic ligand system, the photochromic [4] and magnetic properties [5] of the complexes are of current interest. The synthesized di- and tetranuclear Cd(II)-, Mn(II)-, and Ni(II)-complexes with azobenzene derivatives as coligands were identified by mass spectrometry and elemental analyses and characterized by NMR-, IR-, UV-vis spectroscopy, temperature dependent magnetic susceptibility measurements and by X-ray structure analysis.

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Determination of the Stoichiometric Constant of the Indicator Dye Phenol Red for Spectrophotometric Determination of pH in Estuarine Waters

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CO₂ is being produced and emitted to the atmosphere in important quantities. One of the most important effects is the phenomenon known as ocean acidification, which has produced a decrease of pH of about 0.1 units from pre-industrial levels (about a 30% increase in the concentration of hydrogen ions). There are four measurable parameters for CO₂ studies in seawater: total alkalinity (TA), dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC), pH and partial pressure of CO₂ (pCO₂). Given their thermodynamic relation, it is only necessary to experimentally measure two of them to calculate the others [1],[2].

For oceanographic studies the spectrophotometric technique with the use of pH indicator dyes is the most used for the determination of pH. This technique is based on the measurement of the absorbance spectrum of an indicator dye whose pK_a value assures the presence of the protonated and deprotonated species at the pH of the sample. In order to use those dyes in estuarine waters, it is essential to have the pK_a values in a wider range (0 < S < 40), according to the salinity variation in estuaries [3]. For seawater two are the most widely used dyes: meta-cresol purple and thymol blue. Nonetheless, in estuarine waters the pH could reach lower values and, hence, in this work it was seen necessary to study the suitability of another dye with a lower pK_a. In this sense, phenol red could be more appropriate for estuarine waters due to its usability in the pH range 6.5 - 8.5 [4]. Unfortunately, this is not a well studied dye and therefore, the variation of the pK_a of the phenol red indicator dye with ionic strength and salinity was studied. Once this variation is empirically established, a thermodynamic model was used to get an equation relating the pK_a with the ionic strength. In this sense a polynomial expansion function of the ionic strength of the extended Debye-Hückel equation was used [5].

Two different matrixes were used: NaCl and synthetic seawater (SSW) [6]. For the determination of the pK_a, it was necessary to measure the absorbance of the solutions containing phenol red at different pHs (from pH 4 to 10). These pH values were measured potentiometrically. For the calibration of the potentiometric system three buffers were prepared at each one of the ionic strengths and media studied: A) Sodium acetate 0.1 mol. L⁻¹ at pH = 4.5; B) Tris 0.1 mol. L⁻¹ at pH = 7.5 and C) boric acid 0.1 mol. L⁻¹ at pH = 10. After each addition, the electromotive force (e.m.f) and the spectra were measured. The program HypSpec was used for the calculation of the stability constants of the phenol red at each media and ionic strength. Considering that the thermodynamic constant should be the same in both media, the refinement was performed forcing it to be the same. The experimental pK_a values together with the calculated ones are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Representation of the experimental pK_a values and the fitting of the results in NaCl medium (blue) and SSW medium (red) when the same pK^0 value is forced.

The equations obtained for the ionic strength dependence of the pK_a of phenol red in NaCl and SSW are the following:

$$pK_{NaCl} = 8.011 + 4DH + 1.43 \cdot I - 3.20 \cdot I^{3/2} + 2.19 \cdot I^2$$

$$pK_{SSW} = 8.011 + 4DH - 0.29 \cdot I + 0.55 \cdot I^{3/2}$$

where

$$DH = \frac{0.509\sqrt{I}}{1 + 1.5\sqrt{I}}$$

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Copper(II) complexes with fragments of P1 protein from *Fusobacterium nucleatum* containing histidine and glutamic acids residues. Coordination pattern and physicochemical properties.

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Copper is the most studied metal, because of its biological and chemical significance in proteins. It is worth mentioning, copper is an essential metal ion for biological functions. Due to the presence of many donor atoms the peptides can be very efficient for binding a range of metal (eg. Cu(II), Cu(I), Zn(II)). The coexistence of different donor atoms (amino nitrogen, imidazole nitrogen, carboxylate oxygen and thiolate sulfur) in a peptide sequence allows the formation of a diverse complexes [1]. Peptides have a very broad spectrum of biological activities which can be used, eg. in drug design. It is therefore important to find effective metal ion binding site and determining the importance of individual amino acids. Histidine has the strongest metal coordinating site due to the imidazole nitrogen and can initiate the copper coordination [2]. Although glutamic acid has a carboxylate group side chain that acts as an additional potential donor atom and allows to start the coordination at the more acidic pH. What is worth of note, the data indicate that the effect of the histidine and glutamic acid on the complex formation process depends on the number and location of these amino acids in the peptide sequence [1, 3].

Herein, we present the coordination of peptides from *Fusobacterium nucleatum* outer membrane protein P1 containing histidyl and glutamyl residues with copper(II) ions. Physicochemical properties of the obtained complexes were confirmed by UV-Vis, CD and EPR spectroscopy. Potentiometric titration was used to calculate the stability constants and stoichiometry of complexes. In the solution only the formation of mononuclear complexes are observed. All of the peptides effectively bind metal ion. The glutamic acid has a small influence on the peptide ability to coordinate copper(II). The coordination process begins at pH around 4 by anchoring copper (II) ions by imidazole nitrogen. Then the coordination sphere is complemented by amide nitrogen. The stable five- and six-membered chelate ring are formed, what is an important key in the coordination of metals.

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Mesoporous silica materials functionalized with metal chelating agents for water treatment of toxic metals.

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Ordered mesoporous silicas (OMSs) are very versatile materials, which display high surface areas (up to 1000 m²/g), narrow pore size distributions (2– 20 nm), and high pore volumes (1–3 cm³/g) (Scheme 1). Moreover, the occurrence of surface silanol groups makes possible the introduction several types of surface functional groups. All these features have allowed the use of OMSs for different applications, such as: catalysis, biocatalysis, nanomedicine, and adsorption [1-3]. With increasing environmental concerns worldwide, mesoporous materials have become more important and useful for the separation of polluting species and the recovery of useful ones.

Scheme 1. Schematic representation of functionalized nanoparticles as metal sequestering agents for water treatment and TEM image of SBA-15 ordered mesoporous silica (right).

Previous works have shown the potential of several chelating agents (CA) of low toxicity (TRIEN [4], Kojic acid [5], Cystein, Glutamate, BAL and DMSA [6, 7]) to form stable complexes with different toxic metal ions: copper, zinc, lead, manganese, iron, aluminum, cadmium and nickel, etc. [6, 7].

In this project different CA were grafted on OMS to obtain highly specific and efficient adsorbent matrices (CA@OMS) for the removal of toxic metals from polluted water. The CA@OMS adsorbents were characterized through TEM, SAXS, BET, FTIR, TGA, etc. Then, the metal

sequestering ability was studied with potentiometric and spectroscopic techniques in order to establish the metal-CA@OMS complexes stability and the metal adsorption isotherm and kinetics.

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Coordination Pattern and Reactivity of Copper(II) Complexes with Peptide Fragments of Foma Protein of *Fusobacterium Nucleatum*.

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The colorectal cancer is the third most common cancer in the worldwide and ranks the second because of mortality [1]. In 2012, two separate research teams confirmed for the first time the relationship between *Fusobacterium nucleatum* (*Fn*) and colorectal cancer (CRC). An anaerobe, Gram-negative *Fn* constitutes a part of the natural human flora of the mouth [2]. This bacterium can migrate with blood from oral cavity to different parts of the body (e.g. to colon) [3, 4]. There, it can adhere to host cells through its adhesive proteins located on its outer membrane such as FadA, Fap2 and others. FomA is the major outer membrane protein of *Fn*, which coaggregates with other bacteria [5, 6]. Furthermore, the strong correlation between a diet and cancer diseases exists. Cu(II) ions are uptaken from food and medicines and can be bounded by proteins. Copper ions and their complexes are known to promote oxidative stress and inflammation that can play a role in the development of various cancers [7]. The involvement of copper in colorectal cancer may result from its ability to cycling between two stages (Cu(II) and Cu(I)) and ROS formation [8].

A coordination process of copper(II) ion by Ac-KGHGNG-NH₂ (**1L**) and Ac-PTVHNE-NH₂ (**2L**) peptides (FomA protein fragments) was studied. The stoichiometry of both complexes suggested the 3N {N_{im}, 2×N_{am}} binding mode at pH~7 (colon pH). The formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the solution was confirmed by (i) UV-Vis (NDMA- N,N-dimethyl-p-nitrosoaniline as a reporter molecule of HO·), (ii) fluorescence spectroscopies (DIP-dipyridamole as a detector of HO·, O₂^{·-}, ROO·) in the presence of hydrogen peroxide and ascorbic acid and (iii) gel electrophoresis (HO· and ¹O₂) with/without DMSO and sodium azide. In those experiments proved, that studied complexes generate ROS in much higher level than free ligands and copper(II) ions. Additionally, ROS generated by complexes take part in radical mechanism of action on the plasmid degradation processes [9]. Those oxidative damages can be partially responsible for cancerogenesis processes in colon cells.

Moreover, the influence of studied compounds on mouse colon carcinoma cells line (CT26) were studied by (i) fluorescence spectroscopies (MTT assay) to determinate the cytotoxic activity of compounds, two commercial tests: H2DCF-DA and CYTO-ID Hypoxia/Oxidative Stress Test to asses, whether the compounds stimulate cells to ROS and oxidative stress generation, lipid peroxidation assay with/without NAC- N-acetylcysteine (ii) EPR spin trapping study (with DMPO) to detect the specific free radicals, (iii) ICP-MS analysis to determine an intracellular copper concentration. Ligands and complexes did not exhibit cytotoxic activity against CT26. The Cu(II)-Ac-KGHGNG-NH₂ (**1Cu**) and Cu(II)-Ac-PTVHNE-NH₂ (**2Cu**) stimulated cells to ROS and oxidative stress generation. In addition, the EPR spin trapping study proved, that both copper(II) complexes stimulated CT26 cells to produce hydroxyl radical in interior and in exterior the cell. Furthermore, it was proven that ROS produced by CT26 cells can cause lipid peroxidation. The ICP-MS studies confirmed that **1Cu** and **2Cu** were located outside the cells, only a small part of them penetrated into the interior.

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DNA and RNA binding tests of highly positively or negatively charged phthalocyanines

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Phthalocyanines have the potential to act as anticancer drugs, thanks to their interactions with proteins and polynucleotides [1]. Their strong and specific interaction with G-quadruplex structures may be responsible for inhibiting cancer cells proliferation [2].

Phthalocyanines are excellent macrocyclic ligands for transition metals and metal coordination deeply modulates their chemical and photophysical properties. In particular, phthalocyanines metal complexes have gained high interest as photosensitizers in photodynamic therapy [3].

This work is focused on the interactions between nucleic acids (NA) and two copper phthalocyanines that may have anticancer activity [4]. Alcian Blue is a common dye used in biological tests to stain tissues, thanks to its affinity for polysaccharides [5]. We tested the NA binding of its commercially-available derivative, Alcian Blue-tetrakis(methylpyridinium) chloride (ABTP), which has four positive charges. ABTP properties were then compared with those of copper phthalocyanine-3,4',4'',4'''-tetrasulfonic acid tetrasodium salt (CuPCTS), which, instead, bears four negatively charged substituents.

Fig. 1. Molecular structures of Alcian Blue-tetrakis(methylpyridinium) chloride (ABTP) and Cu(II) phthalocyanine-3,4',4'',4'''-tetrasulfonic acid tetrasodium salt (CuPCTS)

The affinity for polynucleotides such as calf-thymus DNA and poly(A)poly(U) was evaluated for both ligands. Spectrophotometric titrations, viscosimetric studies and thermal denaturation tests were performed. The measurements were repeated at different temperatures and ionic strengths in order to obtain information on the binding modes.

The spectrophotometric titrations suggested a major role of electrostatic forces, both as for NA binding and as for auto-aggregation of the dye. The interaction between NA and ABTP can be better enlightened at low ionic strength, whereas CuPCTS/NA studies were found to need higher ionic strength. In the spectrophotometric titrations, the lack of perfect isosbestic points indicates non-simple binding processes. Circular dichroism spectroscopy confirmed that the binding does occur. In fact, the interaction between the achiral phtalocyanines and the chiral polynucleotides produced induced signals.

The obtained results are encouraging and further investigations will be performed in order to explain the mechanistic details of the processes. The selected molecules will be also tested for affinity to proteins and non-canonical polynucleotides forms.

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Interaction of Divalent Metal Cations with HEIDA at Different Temperatures and Ionic Strengths

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Aminopolycarboxylate chelants (APCs) are used in several industrial processes, including the treatment of toxic metal-contaminated solid waste materials. Biodegradable chelating agents have been extensively studied in the last three decades and it has been proved that they can be used in several fields of application such as: biocides, agriculture, detergents, electroplating, oxidative bleaching, waste treatment, oil industry and remediation of soils [1]. This work has been performed in order to improve the knowledge of the acid-base properties of N-(2-hydroxyethyl)iminodiacetic acid (HEIDA) as a biodegradable ligand and its binding ability towards metal cations. Therefore the complexation of Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Sn^{2+} with HEIDA has been studied at various ionic strengths in $\text{NaCl}_{(\text{aq})}$, $0.12 \leq I/\text{mol}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1} \leq 4.84$ and different temperatures $283.15 \leq T/\text{K} \leq 383.15$ by potentiometric technique and taking into account different models, such as Debye-Hückel type equation, Specific Ion Interaction Theory, Pitzer and Van't Hoff equations for the modeling and interpretation of experimental data. The stability constant of a weak complex species, Na^+ -HEIDA at infinite dilution was 0.78 ± 0.23 and the protonation reactions resulted exothermic in nature. For instance, the stability constant values were determined for CaHHEIDA (11.11 ± 0.02), CaHEIDA (4.92 ± 0.01), $\text{Ca}(\text{HEIDA})_2$ (7.84 ± 0.03) species at $T = 298.15\text{K}$ and $I = 0.150 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$. The results were compared with literature data of other complexing agents. The purpose of this work was to define the speciation models and to give an improvement of the picture of the thermodynamic properties of these systems, defining also the dependence on ionic strength and temperature. These results will give the opportunity to evaluate and predict the distribution of species in any experimental condition. Moreover, the knowledge of the speciation of an element is the basis of biological studies, since it influences the availability, the solubility, the cell membrane permeability and the toxicity of the element itself.

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Syntheses and structural evaluation of phosphine coordinated *fac*-[Re(CO)₃]⁺ complexes, using “2+1” mixed ligand model approach.

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The well reported on *fac*-[M(H₂O)₃(CO)₃]⁺ (M = Re, Tc) synthon, developed in 1998, [1-2] is particularly attractive for its possible uses in diagnostic (Tc) and therapeutic (Re) radiopharmaceuticals and also because of its coordinated water molecules, which can easily be replaced or substituted with suitable derivatized and/or novel ligand systems. This feature presents opportunities to produce new metal complexes with high *in vivo* stability, favourable pharmacokinetic properties and target tissue specificity. [3-4] To complete the coordination sphere of the *fac*-[M(CO)₃]⁺ core, usually tridentate ligands are used, but combinations of bidentate and monodentate ligands, also known as the ‘2+1’ mixed ligand approach are also investigated. [5] These tridentate ligands are comprised of combinations of various donor atom groups including amines, imines, thiols, carboxylates, thioethers etc. to yield relatively stable octahedral complexes. [6] With the ‘2+1’ mixed ligand approach, combinations of *N,N'*-, *O,O'*-, *N,O*-, *N,S*- etc. donor bidentate ligands are coordinated to the metal tricarbonyl core and the sixth position is open for the coordination of numerous donor types of monodentate ligands. The use of the ‘2+1’ mixed ligand system, supported the production of a number of very interesting multifunctional compounds. [7-12]

Figure 1: O,O'-bid = Acac, Benzac, Tfaa and Hfaa; P = PPh₂Cy and PPhCy₂

In this study, a range of Re(I) tricarbonyl complexes as indicated in Figure 1 are synthesized and characterized by IR, UV/Vis ¹H, ¹³C and ³¹P NMR, and single crystal X-ray diffraction. The bidentate ligands used in this investigation are *O,O'*-donor ligands (acetylacetonone (Acac), benzoylacetonone (BenzacH), trifluoroacetylacetonone (TfaaH) and hexafluoroacetylacetonone (HfaaH) and the monodentate ligands are either aqua or phosphine ligands (cyclohexyldiphenyl phosphine (PPh₂Cy) and dicyclohexylphenyl phosphine (PPhCy₂)). The *O,O'*-donor ligands can be synthetically altered to join target biomolecules at the alkyl and the edge carbon atoms on the ligand back bone

[12] and the phosphine ligands were chosen because they coordinate with the low valent ^{99m}Tc/Re carbonyl complexes to form strong bonds and also the fact that the substituents on the phosphorous atoms are chemically flexible. [14-18]

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Structural and magnetic characterization of three novel copper(II) complexes with methyl(2-pyridyl)ketone oxime and pseudohalides

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The family of 2-pyridyl oximes, of general formula (py)RC=NOH with py = pyridine and R = H, alkyl or aryl group, are very popular ligands in the field of molecular magnetism. This is due to their ability to form polynuclear complexes, acting as versatile and flexible bridging ligands that efficiently mediate magnetic exchange between paramagnetic ions. [1] Within this family, our research group have studied the synthesis of polynuclear compounds with methyl(2-pyridyl)ketone oxime (mpkOH) as ligand, which has been less explored than paOH, ppkOH or dpkOH (R = H, Ph and py, respectively). Whereas several manganese or nickel compounds have been characterised, there are only a handful of copper complexes with mpkOH whose X-ray structures have been reported. [2-4]

In this work, we present the synthesis, structural and magnetic characterization of three new copper complexes with mpkOH and azide or thiocyanate as co-ligands. Reaction of a methanolic solution of copper perchlorate or nitrate with mpkOH and sodium azide leads to the formation of the mononuclear complex [Cu(N₃)(mpkO)(mpkOH)] (1).

Figure 1: Perspective drawing of [Cu(SCN)(mpkO)(mpkOH)] (2) and [Cu(SCN)₂(mpkOH)]_n (3).

When potassium thiocyanate is employed instead of sodium azide, two different products are isolated depending both on the starting copper salt and the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}:\text{SCN}^-$ molar ratio. Mononuclear complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})(\text{mpkO})(\text{mpkOH})]$ (**2**) is obtained only if copper perchlorate is used. However, copper nitrate in 1:2 $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}:\text{SCN}^-$ molar ratio, leads to the formation of the chain $[\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{mpkOH})]_n$ (**3**).

In all cases, copper ions are pentacoordinated in a square-pyramidal geometry. In **1** and **2**, four N atoms from one neutral mpkOH molecule and one mpkO^- anion are at the base of the pyramid, the apical position being occupied by the pseudohalide. The distortion from the ideal geometry is larger in complex **1** ($\tau = 0.37$) than in **2** ($\tau = 0.25$).

Complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{SCN})_2(\text{mpkOH})]_n$ (**3**) can be described as a zig-zag chain of Cu^{II} ions. The base of the pyramid is also defined by four N atoms, two of them from a bidentate mpkOH, and the remaining ones from two thiocyanate anions. The coordination sphere is completed at the apical site by the S atom from one SCN^- which is N-bonded to the base of the neighbour Cu^{II} ions. This way, half of the thiocyanate anions act as end-to-end bridges between metal centers, establishing a $\cdots\text{Cu}-\text{SCN}^- - \text{Cu}\cdots$ regular 1D motif, as depicted in figure 1.

Characterization of all complexes was carried out through vibrational and electronic spectroscopy and their magnetic behaviour was studied through variable temperature susceptibility measurements and electron paramagnetic resonance. Weak antiferromagnetic intramolecular interactions between copper ions have been found in **3**.

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Molecular recognition aspects between N9-(2-hydroxyethyl)adenine (9heade) and the di-copper(II)- μ -EDTA chelate.

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By equimolar reaction of $\text{Cu}_2\text{CO}_3(\text{OH})_2$, H_4EDTA and 9heade in water, the novel compound $[\text{Cu}_2(\mu_2\text{-EDTA})(9\text{heade})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been obtained. It crystallizes in the orthorhombic system, space group P_{nma} , as binuclear complex molecules and non-coordinated water molecules. The complex molecule is centrosymmetric (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Asymmetric unit of the compound $[\text{Cu}_2(\mu_2\text{-EDTA})(9\text{heade})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Solvent water molecules have been omitted for clarity.

The metal atom exhibits a markedly asymmetric elongated coordination, best described as type 4+1+1* where * refers to the longest distance Cu-O2 2.816(6) Å, which is similar to the sum of van der Waals radii of Cu (1.40) and O (1.50) atoms. Each half μ -EDTA acts as a tridentate- NO_2 chelator in *mer*-conformation (Cu-O21 1.943(4), Cu-O11 1.978(4), Cu-N10 2.039(6) Å) while the 9heade ligand binds via its N7 donor. Thus, both referred ligands fulfill the four shortest coordination bonds.

The distal O1-aqua bond (2.331(9) Å) is significantly shorter than the above referred *trans*-Cu-O2 interaction. Disregarding such weak Cu···O2(aqua) interaction, the coordination polyhedron agrees with a square-based pyramid. The *trans*-basal coordination angles N7-Cu-N10 174.8(2)° and O11-Cu-O21 164.4(2)° yield an Addison-Reedijk parameter $\tau = 0.17$. The bridging-dinucleating μ -EDTA role in the novel compound has been previously reported for about 45 distinct transition metal derivatives, including the ‘binary’ complex of $\{[\text{Cu}_2(\mu_2\text{-EDTA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}\}_n$ (CUEDTA01 and CUEDTA10 in CSD database), $[\text{Cu}_2(\mu_2\text{-EDTA})(\text{py})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (NAMJOB and NAMJOD01 in CSD [1]) and $\{[\text{Cu}_2(\mu_4\text{-EDTA})(3(\text{HO})\text{-py})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}\}_n$ (PEZRES in CSD).

Regarding the molecular recognition of the 9heade-Cu(II) chelate, it is featured by the cooperation of the Cu-N7 bond (2.032(6) Å and the (9heade)N6-H6B···O21(EDTA) intra-molecular interligand interaction (2.790(8) Å, 168.0°). This H-bond is among the shortest within the crystal. π - π stacking interactions between the purine moieties of 9heade ligands are missing (Figure 2). In the previously reported Cd-9heade complex polymer $[[\text{Cd}(1,2\text{-CHDA})(9\text{-heade})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (1,2-CHDA = 1,2-cyclohexanedicarboxylate) [2], the bridging mode $\mu_2\text{-N1,N7-9heade}$ was reported. In this compound, both Cd-N1 and Cd-N7 bonds cooperate with two (9heade)N6-H···O interligand interactions. Surprisingly, these interactions were not considered by the authors. π,π -stacking interactions are also missing in this crystal.

Figure 2. Architecture of the crystal of $[\text{Cu}_2(\mu_2\text{-EDTA})(9\text{heade})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ along the *a* axis.

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Trapping Deleterious Cl⁻ Anions through Structural Modifications at the Rh Catalyst Site.

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Rh^{III}(NN)₂Cl₂ complexes have been shown to be ideal H₂O reduction catalysts in photocatalytic systems due to its robust nature and tunable redox potentials via ligand modification [1]. The Rh^{III} complex undergoes reduction to form a square planar Rh^I active catalyst, which dissociates the Cl⁻ leaving groups [2]. Recent reports suggest that Cl⁻ ions in solution have a role in Cu^I photosensitizer degradation, so one of our research goals is to find a neutral anionic binding platform for Cl⁻ ions to prolong the longevity of a Cu^I photosensitizer/ Rh^{III} catalyst photocatalytic system (Cu^I photosensitizer = [Cu(Xantphos)(biq)]⁺) [3].

Figure 1. Electronic absorption spectra of 360 μM [Cu(Xantphos)(biq)]⁺ and TBACl (0, 72, 180, 360, 720, 1800 μM) in the dark. Each spectrum corresponds to a fresh solution of Cu(I) PS and TBACl in DMF solvent prepared in the dark to simulate the effect of free Cl⁻ in solution following photoinduced electron transfer to reduce Rh(III) to Rh(I) with concomitant Cl⁻-dissociation.

It is hypothesized that H-bonding sites at modified bpy-(calix[4]arene)₂ ligands covalently coupled to Rh^{III} catalysts are capable of Cl⁻ trapping [4,5]. By synthesizing modified [Rh^{III}(NN)(NN')Cl₂]PF₆ (NN = 2,2'-bipyridine, NN' = 4,4'; 5,5'; 6,6'-bisCalix[4]arene-2,2'-bipyridine) catalysts, we can study the effect of proximity of calix[4]arenes to Cl⁻ trapping and comparing it to a control and free calix[4]arene in solution.

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Synthesis and Complexation Studies of Novel Disubstituted Calix[4]arenes as rare earth metal receptors

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Calixarenes are an important part of the host-guest chemistry. They offer the possibility to build-up binding pockets for guest molecules step-by-step. Calixarenes, foremost calix[4]arenes, have been widely used as scaffold for the synthesis of versatile ligand systems, due to their conformational properties and their feature to exhibit reactive positions for attaching functional groups with various chemical and physical characteristics.[1-3] We are interested in calix[4]arene based ligands regarding to their extraction behavior towards rare earth metals. Previous investigations focused on tetrasubstituted calix[4]arenes with phosphonate ester and picolinamide.[4] Based on the work of Ullmann *et al.* on hybrid Schiff-base calix[4]arene [5-6] we use other Schiff-bases to design bifunctionalized calix[4]arenes.

Herein, we report on the synthesis of two ligands and indicate their ability to act as effective ligands for lanthanide complexes. We show complexation studies and interaction experiments.

Figure 1.: Structure of ligand 1 and structure of ligand 2.

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Synthesis and solution equilibrium studies of half-sandwich Rh-complexes containing bidentate (N,N) and monodentate N-donor ligands

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Selectivity is a crucial factor for the anticancer drugs. These compounds often are very cytotoxic and due to the lack of proper selectivity they can kill healthy cells too. As a result, a lot of patients suffer from severe side effects, *e.g.* neurotoxicity, nephrotoxicity, ototoxicity and vomiting in the case of Pt(II)-containing drugs. [1] There are different strategies to improve selectivity: the drug is administered in an inactive form ('prodrug'), when reaching the target tissue or cells it becomes activated. The mechanism of action for the activation of some Ru(III)-, Pt(IV)- and Co(III)-complexes is reduction [1-3]: when they access the site of action, they can be reduced in the hypoxic environment of cancerous tissue. Probably the resulting Pt(II)- and Ru(II)-complexes are the active forms, while the ligands in the kinetically inert and inactive Co(III)-complex can be liberated upon the reduction, and the free ligand is the active drug.

Acidosis is another characteristic property of the cancerous cells: the metabolism is changed in the hypoxic environment and without the Krebs cycle only glycolysis occurs. It means that higher amount of lactic acid and other oncometabolites are in the cytoplasm in a higher concentration, and the pH can go below 6.5. [4]

Our motivation was to reach the selectivity of organorhodium complexes through activation by acidosis. Herein we report the synthesis and comparative X-ray structural characterization in addition to solution equilibrium studies of Rh-complexes with the structure of $[\text{Rh}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{Me}_5)(\text{N,N})(\text{N})]^{2+}$, where (N,N) is ethylenediamine or 1,10-phenanthroline and (N) is a monodentate ligand. Different ligands bearing N donors were tested to optimize the structure, where the Rh-N bond is hydrolyzed at a higher extent at this acidic pH: benzylamine, methylamine, acetonitrile and several heterocyclic compounds were tested, the latter ones showed the most promising properties. Synthesis and structures determined from single crystal XRD will be presented as well as the results of the solution equilibrium measurements performed by the combined use of pH-potentiometry and ¹H NMR spectroscopy.

Molecular structure of the [Rh(η⁵-C₅Me₅)(phen)(N-Me-imidazole)]²⁺ and the general formula for the [Rh(η⁵-C₅Me₅)(N,N)(N)]²⁺ complexes

Dual targeting can be reached *in situ*: when the complex is hydrolysed, the [Rh(η⁵-C₅Me₅)Cl(phen)]⁺ complex is active against cancer cell lines [5] and if the N-donor ligand is also active synergism is possible. By means of ¹H NMR spectroscopy we have examined the potential sensitivity of the Rh-complex formed with a commercially available drug zoledronic acid, which can act as N-donor via its imidazole moiety.

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NEWLIA: an Excel-VBA version of LIANA Program for Linear and Nonlinear Analysis

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The use of computer programs for the fitting of chemical data to different functions is very common in many branches of chemistry. Nowadays, even the most common spreadsheet applications and programs are able to perform basic calculations accompanied by graphical tools and other interesting features, while complex data analyses and particular procedures are referred to more advanced and specific software, which often results too complex to common users. In between, user-friendly but comprehensive fitting programs are very rare, and they are usually of “home-made” origin and/or of limited diffusion (such as, for example, some Microsoft Excel – VBA macros). Among them, the LIANA program [1], developed by this group in the mid ‘90s, has been extensively used to solve all kinds of linear and nonlinear issues, with particular reference to chemical speciation, equilibrium analysis and many other chemical thermodynamic studies. LIANA was written in Pascal language, using the Levenberg-Marquardt-Gauss-Newton method. Among its relevant features, worth of mentioning was the possibility to:

- 1) refine parameters (up to 30) for any linear and nonlinear equation defined by the user or selected from a library of preset equations;
- 2) divide the main equations in subfunctions;
- 3) consider simultaneously up to 15 different equations, having all or some fitting parameters in common (constrained);
- 4) work with up to 30 independent variables;
- 5) assign different weights to experimental data and/or to perform extra refinement cycles with weights different from the first cycle, to compare various results;
- 6) offer graphical facilities;
- 7) perform functions’ optimization.

Moreover, LIANA output was also planned in such a way to offer an immediate but comprehensive picture of results obtained: total fitting time; original equations and subfunctions; original and refined parameters with corresponding std. devs. and percent error, std. dev., mean dev. and R of Hamilton for the whole fit and for single equations; experimental and calculated data with their differences, weights, and relative error for each exp. point; calculated partial functions for each exp. point; calculated functions at desired values of the independent variables. Some of these features were very uncommon and that time for programs running in small personal computers, and are still very useful nowadays. Unfortunately, LIANA was working under DOS environment and its use is therefore forbidden for more recent operating systems, unless some emulators or virtual machines are installed (and sometimes problems occur anyway). That is why we decided to provide a new version of this

program, which we called NEWLIA. Among all possibilities, we opted to develop it as a free Microsoft Excel-VBA macro, with the aim of facilitating its diffusion, of making it fully compatible with most common Excel-like spreadsheets and data collectors, and of exploiting all Excel features, including all its graphical possibilities, as well as data visualization, organization and analysis, but maintaining and implementing all main LIANA peculiarities. Of course, this option bypassed all previous LIANA limits concerning the number of data to elaborate, the number of equations, of partial functions and parameters to refine. Basically, NEWLIA exploits and brings together in an easy-to-use manner all fitting options of Solver add-in with the important addition of all old LIANA features, implemented by the help of some macros and functions available in the MacroBundle package (e.g., SolverAid) [2].

In this communication, all main features of NEWLIA are presented, together with some examples of applications relevant for people involved in chemical thermodynamic studies.

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Discriminating the intra-molecular interligand H-bond nature in the cooperative molecular recognition pattern of acv

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Acyclovir (hereafter acv) is a synthetic purine nucleoside with active antiviral properties against *Herpesviridae* viruses. This drug, also called acycloguanosine, has an N9 pendant arm with remarkable chemical stability (see Scheme), being considered as a promising ligand. In this context, our researcher group has devoted recent efforts to study the molecular recognition pattern of acv towards various metal chelates [1-4 and references therein]. These and other findings strongly emphasize the tendency of acv to feature the coordination bond M-N7(acv) along with an intra-molecular interligand D-H...O6(acv) interaction (D = O or N donor atom). However, recent results extend the metal binding abilities of acv to the N7,O6-chelating mode of the acv anion in a Ni(II) compound [5] and an unprecedented tetradentate μ_3 -N7,O6,O(e),O(ol) mode for a copper(II) polymer [6]

The main aim of this work is to design and crystallize novel acv-copper(II) compounds with tridentate chelators in order to force the competition within the reinforcement of the Cu-N7(acv) coordination bond with either an (amino)N-H...O6(acv) or an (alcohol)O-H...O6(acv) intra-molecular interligand interaction. To this purpose we reacted copper(II) oxo-salts (nitrate, perchlorate or sulfate) with N-(2-hydroxyethyl)-ethylenediamine (hen, see scheme).

Scheme. Formulas of acv and hen. Acyclovir shows conventional purine numbering. Hen shows the numbering assigned in the structure.

The compound $[\text{Cu}(\text{hen})(\text{acv})(\text{H}_2\text{O})](\text{NO}_3)_2$ was obtained by slow evaporation of a methanol solution having equimolar amounts of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, hen and $\text{acv} \cdot 0.66\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (yield ~80%). It crystallizes in the monoclinic system, space group $\text{P}2_1/\text{c}$. The asymmetric unit (Figure 1) agrees with the compound formula, with a nitrate ion being disordered in two positions, with 70:30 occupancies. In the complex cation, the Cu(II) atom exhibits a square base pyramidal coordination, with hen in *mer*-conformation and an aqua as apical ligand (Cu-O 2.241(4) Å). The most relevant structural feature is the cooperation between the Cu-N7(acv) bond (2.010(5) Å) and the interligand (hen)O4-H4 \cdots O26(acv) (2.648(5) Å), 131.0° interaction.

Figure 1: Molecular recognition between the Cu(hen) chelate and acv. Left: Asymmetric unit of the novel compound showing the cooperation of the Cu-N7(acv) bond with the intra-molecular (hen)O-H \cdots O6(acv) interligand interaction. Right: Fragment of a chain of complex cations with π,π -stacking interactions between the six-membered rings of acv ligands along the *c* axis of the crystal.

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Copper complexes of vitamin B₆ related compounds as anticancer agents

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Transition metals complexes, in particular derived from copper(II), are promising candidates to platinum-based drugs due to its general lower toxicity and distinct electrochemical properties. Copper-complexes, as therapeutic agents, have shown great ability to stimulate oxidative stress and their cytotoxicity revealed to be suitable for cancer treatment [1].

Coenzyme vitamin-B₆ is an antioxidant that assists a multiplicity of biochemical reactions involved in cell metabolic processes. Pyridoxal phosphate has shown significant reduction in cell-proliferation when incubated in high doses with cancer cells [2]. Also, systems containing pyridoxal and appropriate metal ions - as catalysts - have successfully mimicked enzymatic reactions [3] by formation of Schiff base (SB) complexes [4]. The VO(IV) metal center coordinated with a SB containing pyridoxal has shown high selectivity and cytotoxicity for two carcinoma cells lines, which probably involve apoptosis through ROS formation [5]. Furthermore, significant tumor regression, as well as ability to cleave DNA by oxidation of a guanine residue was observed [6].

The aim of this work was to combine non-toxic ligands involved in biologically relevant metabolic processes with a transition metal center to obtain a synergistic effect, yielding cytotoxic and selective metallodrugs. A new series of five copper(II) complexes containing a Schiff base derived from pyridoxal or pyridoxamine and salicylaldehyde or 2-amino-phenol, with or without 1,10-phenanthroline as co-ligand was synthesized and characterized by several techniques (Figure 1). Preliminary results on stability in aqueous buffered solutions (pH=7.4), antioxidant activity, interactions with DNA and cytotoxicity against two cancer cell lines (MCF7 and A2780) are reported.

Most complexes show moderate to good antioxidant activity with compounds containing the phenanthroline co-ligands presenting the best results. The Schiff base derived from pyridoxal and 2-aminophenol has antioxidant activity higher than ascorbic acid, the positive reference. DNA interaction studies suggest that the complexes containing phenanthroline intercalate into the DNA double helix. Cytotoxicity evaluation shows that the compounds display moderate to high cytotoxicity against breast cancer cells, MCF7, with the compounds containing the phenanthroline co-ligands showing the lowest IC₅₀ values in both cell lines. Overall, the copper complexes show properties, which makes them suitable candidates for further studies on their anticancer potential.

Figure 1.

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Evidence for heavy metals pollution in surface sediments of the estuary in Bilbao metropolitan area: origin and geographical distribution

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Heavy metal pollution in estuaries is an issue of high concern for scientists, local stakeholders and authorities. Sediments have been frequently used as sentinels of chemical pollution [1-2]. The estuary of the Nerbioi-Ibaizabal River (Bilbao metropolitan area, Basque Country) was subjected to an important input of metals since the late 19th century until about 1975 [3-7]. Afterwards, a significant decrease in chemical pollution has occurred due to a progressive closure of the most polluting activities and the pre-treatment of waste waters. However, an important actuation, including a large movement of highly polluted sediments, has recently started in order to reduce the effects of floods and improve the urban image of the city. It is therefore of interest to have a precise description of the situation in terms of chemical pollution, in order to make feasible a future quantification of the effects derived from the above-mentioned actuation. With this aim, we collected sediments at about 49 sites in the inter-tidal part of the estuary in January 2018, and the concentration of fourteen elements (Al, As, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mg, Mn, Ni, Pb, Sn, V and Zn) in the acidic extract of the samples was simultaneously measured by Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS).

Geoaccumulation indexes to estimate the metal fraction of anthropogenic origin, Normalized and Weighed Average Concentrations (NWAC's) to identify areas of higher concern and mean Effect-Range-Median quotients (mERMq's) to estimate the toxicity associated to the samples were computed. The results show that *i)* the geographical distribution of heavy metals is rather heterogeneous within the estuary with relatively high concentrations only in a few points and *ii)* the toxicological risk associated to these sediments goes from slight to moderate.

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Promising cytotoxic activity of Lanthanide Monensinates against cultured human breast cancer

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Monensin is a naturally occurring polyether ionophore used as coccidiostatic agent in veterinary medicine. Antibiotic and its metal complexes possess antiparasitic, antibacterial and antiviral activity as well as promising cytotoxicity against cancer cell lines of various origin [1-7]. Recently we found that Monensic acid (MonH) reacts with trivalent metal ions to form complexes of composition $[M(\text{Mon})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ ($M = \text{La}(\text{III}), \text{Gd}(\text{III}), \text{Nd}(\text{III}), \text{Tb}(\text{III})$; Fig. 1), which structure was characterized by various spectroscopic techniques. Results revealed that the ligand acts in bidentate coordination manner encapsulating trivalent metal ions in the form of neutral complex species able to cross cell membrane of microorganisms. We extended our studies on biological properties of Lanthanide Monensinates evaluating their influence on viability and proliferation of cultured human cancer cells.

Figure 1. Structure of Lanthanide Monensinates

Antitumor properties of MonH and its complexes were assessed using permanent cell line MBA-MB-231 (human triple negative breast cancer) as model system in our experiments. The effect of compounds on cell viability and proliferation (CC_{50} , CC_{90} , μM) was evaluated using MTT test, neutral red (NR) uptake cytotoxicity assay and crystal violet (CV) staining.

The results obtained reveal that the metal complexes examined possess significant cytotoxic activity (as compared to non-coordinated ligand) when applied at a concentration range from 0.5 to 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in short-term experiments with monolayer cell cultures. As an example, the hierarchic order of species studied is shown on Table 1.

Table 1. Hierarchic order of compounds studied according to their cytotoxic activity

Assay	Cytotoxic concentration 50 (CC ₅₀ [μM], 48 h)
MTT	Tb (0.76) > Gd (0.86) > Nd (1.4) ~ La (1.5) > MonH (> 30)
CV	Nd (1.3) > Tb (1.7) > La (1.9) > Gd (2.0) > MonH (6.2)
NR	Gd (0.57) > Tb (1.7) > La (1.9) > MonH (2.4) > Nd (2.5)

In conclusion, we demonstrate for the first time that Monensic acid (MonH) and its complexes with trivalent metal ions of rare elements (Ln(III), Gd(III), Nd(III), Tb(III)) reduce significantly viability and proliferation of cultured human triple negative breast cancer cells. Additional study is necessary to be performed to understand more deeply antitumor potential of these compounds as well as their molecular / cellular targets and mechanism of action.

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Natural scaffolds with potential metal chelating activity for the multi-target therapy of Alzheimer's Disease: a preliminary study

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According to the theory of the multifactorial origin of Alzheimer's Disease (AD), in recent years many scientists focused their studies on multi-target agents, acting on features such as the inhibition of acetylcholinesterase (AChE), monoamine oxidases (MAOs) or β -amyloid ($A\beta$) aggregation, the N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptor antagonism, and the antioxidant activity, which have been recognized as important at the onset of the pathology [1, 2]. However, recent evidence has shown that the removal and/or redistribution of metal ions at the level of the nervous system can significantly reduce the formation of $A\beta$ and thus of reactive oxygen species, which are typical of AD and other neurodegenerative diseases. For this reason, the chelation of copper and/or zinc cations is a new fascinating, attractive target for innovative therapies [3].

Therefore, five secondary metabolites of plants or fungi (**1** tenuazonic acid, **2** mycophenolic acid, **3** 2-epiradicinol, **4** radicinin, **5** 6-methoxymellein) with suitable structural characteristics have been selected and assayed in order to preliminarily evaluate their metal chelating properties (**Figure 1**). These molecules have been also tested on other targets, considering that many natural compounds are able to inhibit the $A\beta$ aggregation as well as possess an anti-oxidant and anticholinesterase activity [4]. In this Communication we will present the promising results obtained with some selected hit compounds which will address our future studies of Structure-Activity Relationships.

Figure 1

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New Cu(II) complexes of phytate with 2,4,6-tris(2-pyridyl)-s-triazine: structural diversity from their versatile coordinating ability

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myo-inositol phosphates are an important group of biomolecules present in all eukaryotic cells, whose biological functions are not yet fully understood [1]. The most abundant member of this family is phytate (L^{12-}), which interacts strongly with biologically relevant cations. This interaction is essential for determining the possible functions of this biomolecule. Until recently, the structural analysis of the phytate's multifaceted coordination ability could not be carried out by X-ray diffraction (XRD), due to the amorphous characteristic of the phytate-metal complexes at the solid state. Our group made a breakthrough in this field, reporting four new crystalline structures of phytate-metal complexes determined by XRD [2-4]. These compounds were obtained by the use of an aromatic rigid amine, which acts as an auxiliary ligand, satisfying some of the metal coordination sites and promoting the crystallization. In this work, we expanded on our earlier findings, extending the study to include another aromatic amine: 2,4,6-tris(2-pyridyl)-*s*-triazine (tptz). This coligand is slowly hydrolyzed in the presence of Cu(II), producing bis(2-pyridylcarbonyl)amine (bpca), increasing *in situ* the ligand's structural versatility.

The compounds $K[Cu(H_8L)(tptz)] \cdot 0.5H_2tptz \cdot 9H_2O$ (**1**) and $K[Cu_3(H_8L)(bpca)_3] \cdot 10H_2O$ (**2**), were synthesized at pH = 2 upon diffusion of acetonitrile into the Cu(II):phytate:coligand aqueous solutions. They were characterized by elemental analysis, infrared spectroscopy, thermogravimetric analysis and XRD. The phosphate groups coordinated to the metal ion are P4 and P6 in **1**, and P1, P3 and P4 in **2** (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Crystal structures of both phytate-Cu(II) complexes with tptz and bpca.

The chemical speciation of phytate-Cu(II)-bpca system was analyzed by potentiometry (37.0 °C, 0.15 M NME₄Cl). This allowed us to identify the most abundant chemical species present under the synthetic conditions (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. A possible mechanism for the self-assembly of Cu(II)-phytate-bpca soluble species to form **2** ([bpca] = [Cu(II)] = 30 mM; [phytate] = 10 mM; UB3LYP/LANL2DZ SMD geometries).

In order to furnish a general picture of the assembling mechanism during the synthesis of **2**, different Cu(II)-bpca-phytate microspheres were DFT optimized in solution, starting from the associated chemical speciation of the system and the XRD structural parameters of **2** (Figure 2). It is likely that the anion $[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_8\text{L})(\text{bpca})]^{3-}$ binds the neutral complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{bpca})(\text{OH})]$ to give rise to the trinuclear complex $[\text{Cu}_3(\text{H}_3\text{L})(\text{bpca})_3]^{6-}$, which in turn produces **2** upon charge neutralization by proton and K^+ binding. These results give relevant information about the multifaceted coordination ability of phytate and allow gaining insights into the mechanism of the molecular recognition of phytate by cations.

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Photophysical and biological evaluation of a Zinc(II)-5-methyl-1*H*-pyrazole Schiff base complex

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Evaluation of plasma protein binding is a required step in drug development as it can lead to increased drug solubility, decreased toxicity and protection against metabolic pathways. Human serum albumin (HSA) is the most important non-specific carrier protein in blood plasma. [1] The speciation of metal-based drugs in incubation media, and particularly their binding to albumin present therein, is normally a neglected aspect when trying to understand a metallodrug's mechanism of action. However, the relevance of a more careful speciation evaluation of metal based drugs in cell culture media has been highlighted [2] and is thus a subject that deserves more attention.

A Schiff base (HL) synthesized by condensation of 5-methyl-1*H*-pyrazole-3-carbohydrazide and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde was coordinated to zinc(II) ion in a 2:1 ligand:metal stoichiometry. DFT/TDDFT calculations with a CAMB3LYP functional were used to understand the experimental differences found in the emission profiles of the compounds. The photophysics of HL are ruled by an excited state keto-tautomer, more stable than the enol-tautomer by 4 kJ mol⁻¹, in which the highly probable intersystem crossing to an energetically accessible triplet state precludes the emission of fluorescence, while its Zn(II)-complex (**1**) appears as a fluorescence emitter.

Scheme 1 General synthesis of HL and complex **1**.

This intrinsic characteristic of **1** allowed an extensive study by fluorescence spectroscopy on its interaction with HSA, both in steady-state and time-resolved conditions, revealing a mixed quenching mechanism with strong prevalence of the static process ($K_b = 3.20 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$; $n \approx 1$). Circular dichroism spectroscopy revealed the presence of induced signals in the absorption region of the complex, corroborating adduct formation at site I, close to the protein's tryptophan residue. Quenching studies at different temperatures showed the spontaneity of the association between **1** and HSA ($\Delta G \approx -31.2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ at 298 K), in which several types of interaction forces take place.

The cytotoxicity of HL and **1** were evaluated on human PC3 prostate cancer and MCF7 breast cancer cells. Although HL is cytotoxic for the MCF7 cell line, coordination to Zn(II) increased its

cytotoxicity and an IC_{50} value in the submicromolar range ($IC_{50} = 0.53 \pm 0.21 \mu\text{M}$) was obtained. Considerably higher IC_{50} values were obtained for the prostate cancer cell line, probably due in part to the lack of albumin binding receptors on these cells' membranes. In fact, the very low IC_{50} value against MCF7 cells determined for **1** appears to be at least partly related to the binding of **1** to bovine serum albumin, present in the cell culture medium and to the presence of albumin receptors in the MCF7 cells' membranes.

Figure 1 (Left) - Fluorescence emission spectra measured for solutions containing HSA (*ca.* 32.5 μM) and increasing amounts of **1** (0, 6, 13, 31, 75, 132 μM). As the amount of complex increases, the Trp emission of HSA at 326 nm decreases and the emission of **1** at 485 nm increases. The emission spectra were obtained with excitation at 280 nm. (Right) Stern-Volmer plot for the fluorescence quenching of HSA (I_0/I data were corrected for inner filter effects), $\lambda_{em}^{max} = 326$ nm. Inset: Stern-Volmer plot obtained from time-resolved fluorescence measurements, using $\lambda_{ex} = 280$ nm and collecting the emission at $\lambda_{em} = 340$ nm.

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The urease biosensor based on Eu(III) ternary complex of DO3A ligand

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Specific spectroscopic, electrochemical and magnetic properties of Ln(III) ions make them perfect candidates for use in many chemical, biological and environmental systems. Ln(III) complexes with macrocyclic ligands (mainly DOTA derivatives) are commonly utilized in medicinal chemistry as radiopharmaceuticals (⁹⁰Y, ¹⁵³Sm, ¹⁶⁶Ho, ¹⁷⁷Lu) [1,2] and contrast agents for MRI (Gd) [3].

The 1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane-1,4,7-triacetic acid (H₃DO3A) as heptadentate ligand forms a stable complex with europium(III)/terbium(III) aqua ion. The ternary [Ln(DO3A)L] complex exhibits a high luminescence due to antenna effect leading to sensitization of Eu(III)/Tb(III) luminescence by a fluorophore (e.g. picolinic or isoquinolic acid) via efficient energy transfer from ligand to Ln(III) ion. The utilization of those ternary Eu(III) and Tb(III) complexes as selective dual luminescence/electrochemical sensors for determination of carbonate/oxalate using substitution reaction was reported [4, 5]. This was also employed for indirect determination of carbonate formed in the course of urea hydrolysis catalyzed by the urease enzyme (see Scheme). This new analytical procedure was proposed for the determination of both analytes (urea, urease) and the luminescence-based biosensor can be used in both kinetic time-dependent as well as equilibrium end-point modes [6].

Scheme: The cascade reaction of the ternary [Eu(DO3A)(Pic)]- complex employed for enzymatic determination of urea.

The inhibition effect of some metal ions (*e.g.* Ag⁺, Pb²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺) on enzymatic reaction can be employed for their analytical determination [6]. The proposed analytical procedure is fast, selective and sensitive with metrological parameters comparable for other urea biosensors. As it is known to authors, this new biosensor is the first example of biosensor using the bicarbonate detection as the product of urea hydrolytic reaction catalyzed by urease.

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**Eu³⁺ and Tb³⁺ complexes with polyaminocarboxylate ligands:
a spectroscopic and thermodynamic study**

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Lanthanide complexes (Ln³⁺ = Sm³⁺, Eu³⁺, Tb³⁺, Dy³⁺, Yb³⁺) have been extensively studied as luminescent and optical sensors for cell imaging. The long emission lifetimes of Ln³⁺ ions are favourable for reducing interference from light scattering or autofluorescence in complex microenvironments such as cells, tissue or animals *via* time-gated detection [1-4]. Complexes of Ln³⁺ ions present an efficient intramolecular energy transfer from a donor state (usually triplet) of the coordinated organic ligand (*antenna*) to the acceptor excited states of Ln³⁺ ion giving rise to an efficient Ln³⁺ excitation, bypassing the Laporte-forbidden nature of the f-f transitions. The large energy shift between absorbed and emitted radiations and the very narrow emission bands allow the discrimination between Ln³⁺ luminescence and short-lived background fluorescence.

Luminescent complexes of Eu³⁺ and Tb³⁺ are the most employed due to the low sensitivity of their excited state towards vibrational quenching effects caused by OH, NH, or CH oscillators, frequently present in solution and imaging environments [1,2].

For these reasons, Eu³⁺ and Tb³⁺ complexes have been extensively exploited also as sensors in both aqueous solutions [5] and organic solvents [6]. When the environment around Ln³⁺ is chiral, the metal may display circularly polarized luminescence (CPL), a chiroptical phenomenon, which is rapidly gaining interest thanks to its biomedical and technological applications [7].

Recently, some of us reported a structural and spectroscopic study on a promising chiroptical probe based on a Tb³⁺ complex of a polyaminocarboxylate ligand, *i.e.* N,N'-bis(2-pyridilmethyl)-trans-1,2-diaminocyclohexane-N,N'-diacetic acid (H₂bpcd), where the chiral diaminocyclohexane (DACH) backbone is present [8].

In this work we present the synthesis, the optical spectroscopy and the thermodynamic study in aqueous solution of Eu³⁺ and Tb³⁺ complexes with N,N'-bis(2-quinolilmethyl)-trans-1,2-diaminocyclohexane-N,N'-diacetic acid (H₂bQcd) (Fig.1a). This ligand differs from the previously studied H₂bpcd (Fig.1b) for the *antenna* which is changed from pyridine to quinoline. This structural modification affects several important parameters such as the excitation condition (*i.e.* the excitation wavelength) and the hydrophobicity.

The Ln(bQcd) complexes are also tested for the luminescent sensing of bicarbonate ion, whose concentration is critical in assessing metabolic acidosis [9].

Figure 1 Ligands discussed in this work: a) bQcd and b) bpcd.

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The adsorption study of Cu(II) and Pd(II) ions from aqueous solution on the functionalized graphene derivatives is also presented. In all the cases the kinetic data of the adsorption processes fit well to the pseudo-second order model, suggesting that the adsorption overall rates are controlled by chemical bindings of the metal ions to the surface chemical functions [5]. Moreover, the adsorption isotherms fit the Langmuir equation which has allowed calculating the corresponding maximum adsorption capacities that show an enhanced adsorption capacity of the functionalized materials in relation to that of the original rGO and GO. This fact proves that the metal complexing properties of the anchored organic compounds have been efficiently transferred to the surface graphene.

In addition, the reduction with NaBH₄ of the metal ions supported on the functionalized materials has allowed the obtaining of metal nanoparticles (MNPs) homogeneously distributed on the materials, stabilized by the presence of the chemical surface functions which also reduce the MNPs mobility, what results in a final small particle size.

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Influence of the phosphines groups in the anti-cancer activity of palladium(II) compounds bearing thiosemicarbazones

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The palladium(II) complexes have been studied for their anticancer activities, due to their similarity with the platinum(II) metal complexes [1]. The thiosemicarbazones (TSCs) appear to be promising ligands in the syntheses of metal compounds, with a possible action against the enzyme topoisomerase II (TopoII) [2]. Topo II has participated in several nuclear processes, such as DNA replication, transcription, chromosome condensation and chromosome segregation. Moreover, TopoII is present as an over expression in some kinds of cell lines [3]. An incorporation of the voluminous phosphanes has been a strategy that has been adopted by many researchers in the planning of metal complex candidates, in order to act as enzymatic inhibitors.

In this work five new palladium(II) complexes bearing thiosemicarbazone and phosphanes as ligands were synthesized and fully characterized by IR, NMR, UV-Vis spectroscopy, elemental analysis and X-ray diffraction, where upon single crystals were obtained, for the compounds without X-ray diffraction DFT calculations were performed to obtain their structure. The metal complexes were tested against a tumor breast cancer cell and a non-tumor lung cell. The cytotoxicity and the selectivity indexes of the palladium(II) complexes were compared to cisplatin. Furthermore, the mechanisms of action were investigated.

The precursor $[\text{PdCl}_2(\text{MeCN})_2]$ reacted with the TSC_CC in acetonitrile to afford the intermediate $[\text{PdCl}(\text{TSC_CC})]_2$. The complexes $[\text{PdCl}(\text{PR}_3)(\text{TSC_CC})]$ were obtained by adding equimolar amounts of the appropriate phosphane [triphenylphosphine (PPh₃); tri(p-tolyl)phosphine (Pp-T); tri(o-tolyl)phosphine (Po-T); tris(4-fluorophenyl)phosphine (Pp-4F)]. The chloride was replaced by an iodine ion in complex **5** by adding potassium salt in excess. The structure of complexes **2** and **3** were obtained by X-ray diffraction (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Structure for complexes **2** and **3**.

In order to investigate the inhibition of cell growth, the palladium(II) complexes were tested against the two human cells lines MDA-MB-231 and MRC-5 (non-tumor cell). Their IC₅₀ values and selective indexes (SI) were compared to cisplatin. Compound **4** presented a lower IC₅₀ value of 0.56 μM, being four-fold more active than the standard drug. Substitution of the phosphane groups in the complex structures demonstrated a slight change in the cytotoxicity. A donated electron density group, like methyl (**3**), decreased the IC₅₀ values when compared to the non-substituted phosphane (**1**), while a withdrawn electron density group increased the activity (**4**). DNA interaction assays were performed, the titration curves (Figure 2A) and the mobility of the supercoiled pBR322 plasmid in a gel electrophoresis (Figure 2B) demonstrated the weak interaction between metal complexes and DNA. However, complexes **1**, **4** and **5** showed a total inhibition of the Topo II enzyme at 12.5 μM (Figure 2C) better than etoposide.

These results have indicated that the use of thiosemicarbazone and phosphane groups as ligands was an interesting strategy to synthesize new complexes with a high cytotoxicity and with different mechanisms of action.

Figure 2. (A) DNA titration; (B) DNA electrophoresis mobility; (C) Topoisomerase II inhibition assay.

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Thiacalix[4]arenes with Dangling Phosphorylated Substituents at the Lower Rim for *f*-Element Complexation

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Thiacalixarenes, subclass of calixarenes, gain a lot of interest since their first come out in 1997.^[1,2] New phosphorylated lower rim modified thiacalixarene were synthesized. Therefore the thiacalixarene reacted with a halogenated phosphonate ester under basic conditions. The spacer length between phosphorous of the phosphonate ester group and the oxygen of the thiacalixarene were varied as well. The exchange of the methylene bridge with four sulfur atoms and therewith the enlarge of the ring size makes it possible to do that tetrasubstitution in a one pot synthesis instead of a two-step synthesis like the classical calixarenes needed.^[3-5]

Figure 1: Synthesis of tetrasubstituted phosphorylated thiacalixarene

In our working group we are focused to introduce dangling substituents at the lower rim in order to investigate *f*-element complexation. This ligand was used for *f*-element complexation which will be presented as well.

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Novel chelators based on bisamidopyridine azacrown compounds: Synthesis and complex formation properties.

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Macrocyclic ligands have wide applications in catalysis, metal separation, molecular recognition, biomedicine due to their ability to form complexes with different metal ions or anionic species. The binding properties of ligands are determined by the nature and arrangement of donor atoms, the ring size and conformational rigidity of the molecule.

This work presents the synthesis of a novel bisamidopyridine containing azacrown compounds and their derivatives comprising carboxylic or pyridine pendant arms. The potentiometric, NMR, ESI-MS and X-ray analysis were carried to study the binding properties towards a wide range of metal ions (Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Y^{3+} , Eu^{3+} , Ac^{3+} , Bi^{3+}).

These ligands form less stable complexes with metal ions in comparison with similar amine macrocyclic compounds [1]. The modification of amide macrocycles with additional coordination groups improves the binding properties of these ligands (Table 1) [2].

Table 1. Stability constants (log K) of the complexes of 1–2 with metal ions, 25.0 °C, $\mu = 0.10$ mol·dm⁻³ in NaClO₄

ion	log K				
	1	2	1a	2a	1b
Ni^{2+}	5.5	6.0	9.5	14.3	6.5
Cu^{2+}	8.8	10.8	11.2	15.8	8.9
Zn^{2+}	3.9	4.1	11.5	12.6	-
Cd^{2+}	3.6	4.2	7.3	11.7	-
Pb^{2+}	-	4.9	8.7	14.1	4.9
Y^{3+}	-	-	7.0	6.9	-
Eu^{3+}	-	-	7.1	8.2	-
Ac^{3+}	-	-	6.6	7.4	-
Bi^{3+}	12.5	14.4	16.4	21.3	15.0

The introduction of carboxyl groups into the bisamidopyridine macrocycles (**1a**, **2a**) not only increases stability of complexes with divalent ions in compare with **1** and **2**, but also provides the coordination with trivalent ions. Crown compound with two pyridine pendant arms **1b** binds with Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Bi^{3+} ions more effective then **1**. From the presented data we can conclude about the highest values of stability constant for Cu^{2+} and Bi^{3+} complexes.

Scheme 1. Crystal structure of chelator 2a and complex 2a·Pb²⁺

The X-ray analyses of the prepared crown compounds showed that introducing of rigid aromatic fragment into macrocyclic backbone provides the formation of open cavity preorganized for complex formation (Scheme 1, 2). This explains the high rate of complex formation of pyridine-containing azacrown compounds with metal ion. Coordination of metal occurs via the amine nitrogens and arms outside of macrocycle. In case of complex of **2a**, metal ion is located in macrocyclic cavity and surrounded by carboxylic groups on both sides. This increases stability constants by chelating effect.

Scheme 2. Crystal structure of complexes 1b·Pb²⁺ and 2a·Cu²⁺

In case of Cu²⁺ and Bi³⁺ we found values of stability constant sufficient to use ligand **2a** as component of radiopharmaceuticals. Cytotoxicity, radiolysis resistance, *in vitro* and *in vivo* experiments were investigated [3]. Semi-lethal concentrations of **2a** for cancer and normal cells showed that it is not cytotoxicity. The complex **2a**·Bi³⁺ is stable in isotonic solution for 3 days and in bovine serum no re-chelation was detected. Also it demonstrates fast clearance *in vivo*. The results of *in vitro* serum stability and *in vivo* biodistribution studies suggest that the novel ligand **2a** can be promising as chelator for the preparation of radiopharmaceutical with ²¹³Bi.

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Cyclen-based fluorescent chemosensors for Zn(II) and Cd(II)

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Fluorescence sensing has attracted much attention owing to sensitivity, selectivity, simplicity, high degree of specificity and low detection limit [1,2]. In particular, fluorescent ligands bearing nitrogen heterocycles are often chosen for metal binding and sensing [3,4].

Metal ions play indeed important roles in the normal physiological activities, such as inducing apoptosis, enzyme regulation, gene expression and oxygen transport. Some ions are instead harmful to human body. In fact, elevated levels of certain metal ions within regions of the brain are found in Alzheimer's disease [5]. In this respect, the design and synthesis of new fluorescent probes for metal cations in solution and in biological environments, such as cells and tissues, still remain subject of great interest.

We have recently synthesized a family of cyclen-based metal receptors containing 2-(2'-hydroxy-3'-naphthyl)benzoxazole (HNBO) and 6,7-dimethoxycoumarin as fluorescent units (**L1**, **L2** and **L3** in Figure 1, cyclen = 1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclododecane).

All ligands are able to form remarkably stable complexes with the investigated transition and post-transition metal cations, among which Zn(II), Cd(II), Cu(II) and Pb(II). In all cases and for all ligands, the nitrogen donor atoms of the macrocycle coordinate to the metal cation, while the oxygen atom of the deprotonated OH group of at least one HNBO moiety is involved in the coordination of Zn(II), and in the case of **L1**, of Cd(II).

Figure 1: line drawings of ligands **L1**, **L2** and **L3**.

Figure 2: I/I_0 values of **L1** and **L2** in the presence of different metal cations.

Ligands **L1** and **L2** have proved to be good selective 'turn-on' fluorescent chemosensor for Zn(II), **L1** being also able to signal Cd(II) (Figure 2). Since complex formation implies both the deprotonation of the naphtholic group of the HNBO unit and its coordination to the metal cation, we propose that the involvement of the fluorophore moiety is crucial to its switching from the OFF to the ON state. As for **L3**, it did not exhibit any

fluorescent sensing ability towards the investigated metal ions, as expected considering that the fluorogenic unit is known for its poor ability to bind metals.

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Deferoxamine as Zr(IV) Chelator: the *K* to Understanding.

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Due to its own emission properties, cyclotron preparation of ⁸⁹Zr was saluted as a major breakthrough for PET imaging. Much of the initial success of this radionuclide was due to the quick recognition of Deferoxamine (DFO) as an effective chelator: a true godsend. Among the advantages it provided there is the huge shortcut offered by using a long-time FDA approved drug, not to mention the fact that this ligand is considerably cheap to manufacture, needing only a few chemists, if any, to supervise the peaceful synthetic work of *Streptomyces* bacteria.

Concerning the Zr(IV)-DFO system, most of chemists' remarks were misunderstood by part of the Bio-Medical community. When somebody asserted that expected stability constants for complexes of 4+ ions are higher than those for 3+ ones (read Fe³⁺, the ion DFO was approved for) [1], or that they exceed impressive values (e.g. 10³¹, meaning only that they could not be determined) [2], or that pM values are extremely low (yet estimated within a 3 orders of magnitude indetermination) [3], or even that “water further stabilize the Zr-DFO complex” (2 water molecules appear to be needed to complete Zr(IV) coordination environment according to DFT calculations) [4], the take home message was understood by non-chemists as: Zr(IV)-DFO complex is more stable than Fe(III)-DFO complex; since everything is fine for Fe(III), and FDA has our backs on that, then everything is going to work even better for Zr(IV) [5]. Problem solved.

Fallacies leads to false expectations, and their delusion leads to titles like “Alternative chelator for ⁸⁹Zr Radiopharmaceuticals” [6], with more and more people involved in the effort of surpassing DFO limitations. But what is the nature of such limitations? In the best-case scenario, we read concepts like: “[...] Data have led us to conclude that a ligand designed specifically with the chemistry of Zr⁴⁺ in mind may demonstrate improved stability upon complexation with Zr⁴⁺. Furthermore [...], a more stable complex should be less prone to demetalation in vivo, resulting in [...] a safer and more efficient ⁸⁹Zr-based PET tracer [6].” Now, having the chemistry of Zr⁴⁺ in mind and obtaining more stable complexes than those of DFO is quite a harsh task when no (zero, 0, Ø) equilibrium constants have been determined.

The pursuit for clarity prompted us to go back to the few data available for complex formation with the Zr⁴⁺ ion, dating back to some of the most eminent papers on the topic. Among them, a 1964 paper by Martell et al. [7] provided a reliable ground for the EDTA-Zr(IV) system. EDTA complexes, partially owing to their solubility in water, have historically been widely studied and well-characterized systems, oftentimes providing the key to the determination of stability constants of more troublesome ligands, providing a solid background for competition experiments. Most of the observations of Martell and coworkers have been found to be quantitatively accurate, yet we were able to overcome several limitations of their work, providing numerical solutions accounting for multiple simultaneous equilibria which were beyond the possibilities of the computing power of the '60s. Full speciation of Zr(IV)-EDTA systems is now available, including a detailed description of

polynuclear Zr(IV)-EDTA complexes, an already observed phenomenon [7] which was in need of a proper quantification.

Unluckily, knowledge of Zr(IV)-EDTA complexes stability has been proved of no use for the determination of the binding constants for the Zr(IV)-DFO system, due to the higher stability of DFO complex (5-6 orders of magnitude, *vide infra*) compared to EDTA one.

A sufficiently strong competing ligand was recognized in the OH⁻ anion. It is well known that Zr(IV) forms very stable hydroxide complexes, which can and have been previously characterized. According to literature information, some of Zr(IV) hydroxo species may be from quite to very insoluble [8]. However, it remains unclear whether such insolubility is real (i.e. intrinsic) or due to the polymerization process tied to theolation of the cation. Re-determined hydrolysis constants of monomeric soluble species are found fully congruent with those published by Baes and Mesmer in their cornerstone handbook for Inorganic Chemistry [9], confirming that solubility issues do not prevent their determination.

Owing to the high stability of the Zr(IV)-DFO complex, it is possible to conduct experiments where such hydroxo complexes are non-existent in solution below pH 7-8 and titrations can be prosecuted in alkaline media until a significant percentage of the cation is present as Zr(OH)₄. Establishment of such equilibrium, which has been studied for several metal:ligand ratios, allows the determination of the Zr(IV)-DFO stability constant and the backward complete speciation of the Zr(IV)-DFO system.

Turns out that, similarly to what observed by Martell for EDTA complexes [7] and quite reasonably according to the unsaturated coordination sphere of Zr(IV) in the DFT model of its DFO complex [4], the most abundant species at physiological pH is not a 1:1 complex, but its 2:2 dimer! On this basis, with the complete speciation of the system at hand, we anticipate not only a long-term blooming of the research field in producing more fit ligands, but also a short term major revision of clinical protocols for the preparation of DFO-based Zr(IV) PET agents.

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Antioxidant and redox activity of deferiprone and its chelate complexes with iron and copper ions

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The presented report is devoted to physicochemical study of redox and photochemical activity of chelate complexes of deferiprone with copper and iron ions in the presence of biologically important electron donors and acceptors. Deferiprone (L1) is an effective iron chelating drug widely used for the treatment of iron overload diseases such as thalassemia. Deferiprone has also high affinity for copper binding and can be considered for the treatment of copper toxicity and overloading conditions, such as Wilson's disease. It is well established that iron and copper ions can catalyze the production of highly toxic free oxygen radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$ and $\bullet\text{OOH}$) through the Fenton-like reactions. However, the experimental data on redox activity of L1 chelate complexes with iron and copper ions in Fenton-like reactions were absent. The study of the photochemical stability of L1 metal complexes is also particularly important, since iron-related diseases, such as thalassemia, are prevalent in the Mediterranean, Middle East and Southeast Asian countries, where the level of irradiation with sunlight is extremely high. The ability of iron complexes with various ligands to produce highly toxic free radicals under irradiation is well established. Nevertheless, there were no experimental data on the phototoxicity of the L1 chelate complexes, or the ability of L1 to prevent the phototoxic effects of other iron complexes. Although deferiprone itself does not absorb light in the visible region of the spectrum, its chelate complexes with Fe ions demonstrate a new absorption band between 500 and 800 nm which might be responsible for phototoxic effects. Light in this region of the spectrum can penetrate the skin and reach the capillaries.

As a result, we have shown that deferiprone and its complexes with Fe^{3+} ions are photochemically unstable under light irradiating below 380 nm [1, 2]. The formation of photodegradation products and free radicals of deferiprone have been detected by nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) and chemically induced dynamic nuclear polarization (CIDNP) techniques. The photoinduced electron transfer between L1 and various electron donors and acceptors (NADH, Trp, AQDS) under irradiation by UV light was proved by CIDNP method. But, and it is important, no photochemical activity of L1 chelate complexes with iron was detected under irradiation by visible light at 400–800 nm [1–2].

Electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) method is widely used to detect short lived free oxygen radicals (hydroxyl and peroxy radicals) formed in physiological conditions in the presence of metal ions. Using EPR spin trapping technique, we have demonstrated that deferiprone completely inhibits the formation of highly toxic hydroxyl radicals in dark (Fenton-like) and photoinduced (photo-Fenton) reaction initiated by Cu and Fe ions [2, 3]. Overall, L1 works as an antioxidant by preventing

copper and iron induced free radicals formation via Fenton-like reactions. These findings confirm previous findings of the antioxidant potential of L1 in diseases related to metal induced oxidative damage [4].

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P 34. Molecular recognition aspects between N9-(2-hydroxyethyl)adenine (9heade) and the di-copper(II)- μ -EDTA chelate.

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